

AN EXPLORATION AROUND COMPLETENESS OF
THE INTERNATIONAL ACCOUNTING STANDARDS BOARD'S
QUALITATIVE CHARACTERISTICS

GARETH CHRISTOPHER EVANS

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Professional Doctorate

October 2019

Dedication

For my wife Jackie, children Kirsten and Christopher, and my mother, Joyce. Thank you for all your love and support.

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Acknowledgements

I would like to express my sincere thanks to a number of individuals who have provided me with support and encouragement throughout the period of my doctoral studies. I would first like to pay tribute to my supervisors Dr. Jo Lusher and Dr. Stephen Day to whom I owe a massive debt of gratitude and support in helping me with this dissertation through their consideration and encouragement.

I would like to express my thanks to the University and to my professional work colleagues, especially my critical friend Sean McGrogan, and Dr. Becky Rowley's Academic Writing Group within Learning and Development of the Isle of Man Government, for the support they too have given me during my studies. I am also immensely grateful to those who participated in interviews for their time, hospitality and interest in my research.

Finally, I would like to thank my wife Jackie, my mother Joyce, and my children Kirsten and Christopher, all whose love and support has been invaluable.

Declaration

I hereby declare that I am the author of this thesis, that the work of which this thesis is a record, has been done by myself, and that it has not previously been accepted for a higher degree.

Signed

Date...10 October 2019

Mr G. C. Evans

Certificate

We certify that G. C. Evans has worked the equivalent of four academic years on this research, and that the conditions of the relevant ordinance and regulation have been fulfilled.

Signed

Date...10 October 2019

Dr J. Lusher

Signed

Date...10 October 2019

Dr S. Day

Abstract

The Qualitative Characteristics of decision-useful financial information, as set out in the revised March 2018 Conceptual Framework for financial reporting of the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), are fundamental for standard setting, relied on by companies when making accounting policy changes and choices. This thesis set out to explore the completeness of these qualitative characteristics after the literature review showed no overarching conceptual context of the qualitative characteristics that was universally agreed upon.

This research used both Foucauldian critical discourse analysis and content analysis paradigms to elucidate the inclusion conundrum. Foucauldian analysis allowed focus on power relationships, governmentality and subjectification in accounting society, as expressed through language and practices of the IASB who ultimately decide on the qualitative characteristics, and the IASB's interaction with professional accountants preparing international, domestic UK and local Isle of Man (IOM) banks' annual reports. Content analysis was used to analyse data collected via interviews with preparers and users of banks' accounts, changes in banks' accounting policies after the conceptual framework was published, and comment letters from banks' who wrote to the IASB. Geographical and cultural spread was attained by exploring the annual reports of both building societies and regulated banks' listed on the UK FTSE, South African JSE, and Australian stock exchange main boards, in addition to those of local IOM banks'.

The original contribution to knowledge found was the potential significant omissions of the constraints of 'materiality', 'transparency', and 'regulatory or supervisory framework' surrounding the qualitative characteristics having been shown to be valid and includable, the adjective 'decision-useful' reinstated in the chapter title, and the IASB project's team technical writers needing to show completeness of attention to all comments.

From these findings, a freshly formulated chapter in the conceptual framework on the qualitative characteristics can be submitted for consideration by the IASB, with potential for implementation internationally on post-implementation review.

Keywords

Accounting, qualitative characteristics, Conceptual Framework, financial reporting, relevance, faithful representation, prudence, matching, transparency, stewardship, reliability, content analysis, Foucault, Foucauldian lens, critical discourse analysis, constraints.

Disciplines

Accounting Science | Social and Behavioural Sciences

Key abbreviations and acronyms

AAOIFI	Accounting and Auditing Organisation for Islamic Financial Institutions
AASB	Auditing and Assurance Standards Board
ACCA	Association of Chartered Certified Accountants
AICPA	American Institute of Certified Public Accountants
APB	Accounting Principles Board
BBA	British Bankers Association
Board	International Accounting Standards Board
BoE	Bank of England
CAQDAS	Computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software
CDA	Critical Discourse Analysis
CF	Conceptual Framework
DP	Discussion Paper
ECB	European Central Bank
EFRAG	European Financial Reporting Action Group
ED	Exposure Draft
ESRC	Economic and Social Research Council
EU	European Union
FASB	Financial Accounting Standards Board
FSA	Financial Services Authority
FRC	Financial Reporting Council (replaced by a new regulator, the Audit, Reporting and Governance Authority from 1 April 2019)
FRS	Financial Reporting Standards
FTSE	The Financial Times Stock Exchange index
FVA	Fair Value Accounting
GAAP	Generally Accepted Accounting Practice

GPFR	General Purpose Financial Reporting
IAASB	International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board
IAS	International Accounting Standards
IASB	International Accounting Standards Board
IASC	International Accounting Standards Committee
ICAEW	Institute of Chartered Accountants of England and Wales
ICAS	Institute of Chartered Accountants of Scotland
IFAC	International Federation of Accountants
IFRIC	International Financial Reporting Interpretations Committee
IFRS	International Financial Reporting Standards
IMF	International Monetary Fund
IOM	Isle of Man
IPASB	International Public Accounting Standards Board
JSE	Johannesburg Stock Exchange
PRA	Prudential Regulatory Authority
QCs	Qualitative Characteristics
SAICA	South African Institute of Chartered Accountants
SEC	Securities and Exchange Commission (US)
SFAC	Statement of Financial Accounting Concepts
SME	Small and Medium Entities
SORP	Statement of Recommended Practice
SSAP	Statement of Standard Accounting Practice
UK	United Kingdom
US	United States

Publications associated with this research

Evans, G.C., Lusher, J., and Day, S., (2017), Examination of the International Accounting Standards Board's Qualitative Characteristics. Poster presentation, 29 November 2017, HNM Student Research Conference, Paisley, University of the West of Scotland.

Evans, G.C., Lusher, J., Day, S. (2019c), Comment Details – Relevant and faithful under the microscope. The Accountant, ICAEW. [Online] Available: <http://www.theaccountant-online.com/comments/relevant-and-faithful-under-the-microscope-7347776> [Accessed: 2 August 2019].

Publications in preparation

Evans, G.C., Lusher, J., Day, S. (2019a), A critical review of the nature of accounting professionalism. (*In preparation*).

Evans, G.C., Lusher, J., Day, S. (2019b), A current literature review of the IASB's qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial reporting. (*In preparation*).

Evans, G.C., Lusher, J., Day, S. (2019d), The International Accounting Standards Board's due process through a Foucauldian lens. Advances in Accounting, Elsevier.com. (*In preparation*).

Evans, G.C., Lusher, J., Day, S. (2019e), Ranking the qualitative characteristics and the gap between preparers and users' perceptions of useful financial information using DECFIN©. Critical Perspectives on Accounting, Elsevier.com. (*In preparation*).

Chapter 1 Introduction

‘The truth is rarely pure, and never simple.’

(Oscar Wilde in ‘The Importance of being Earnest’, 1895).

1.1 Preamble

Following the IASC’s initial Conceptual Framework in 1989, its then merger with FASB, and subsequent divorce from FASB in 2010, the qualitative characteristics have been questioned given the lack of confidence by users and preparers over the main purpose of annual reports being stewardship or financial strength (Cascino, 2016), the completeness of the characteristics (Nobes and Stadler, 2014, questioning whether ‘transparency’ should now be included as a qualitative characteristic), the terminology used (Sutton, Cordery and van Zijl, 2015, ‘faithful representation’ v ‘reliability’), and the definitions of those characteristic terms that were used (Deller, 2018a, on ‘prudence’).

A personal view, also expressed by others (e.g. Williams, 2018; Whittington, 2016; van Beest et al., 2009), was that the 2010 Conceptual Framework remained incomplete and under-emphasized concepts such as ‘prudence’ and ‘matching’. Emerging research by Nobes and Stadler (2014) reflected on the QC of ‘transparency’, meaning enhanced disclosure, additional information, improved visibility of information, and non-secrecy by companies and countries of registration, having been omitted from the 2010 Conceptual Framework. Indeed, the Financial Conduct Authority has recently issued its own ‘Disclosure and Transparency’ rules for its regulated banks’. If these significant omissions are shown to be correct after both evidential content analysis and further mixed methods paradigm studies, following in part Parasuraman, Zeithamel and Berry (1985) seminal paper’s methodology on Service Quality characteristics, and Foucauldian Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), then a revised chapter in the international Conceptual Framework on ‘The qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information’ could be formulated by the researcher, and submitted to the IASB for due consideration and possible implementation internationally on its post-implementation review in a few years’ time.

The remainder of the introductory chapter is structured as follows. Section 1.2 outlines the key research questions that are investigated in the current study. The

methodology and method used are also briefly discussed. A brief description of the structure of the thesis concludes the chapter.

1.2 Scope of the research

The primary objective of this study is to explore the completeness of the IASB's qualitative characteristics in order to improve financial information in annual reports of companies, specifically accounting policies and their changes, all within the overarching requirement of decision-useful financial reporting. This objective is facilitated in three ways: (a) by interviewing preparers and users of banks financial statements; (b) by content analysis of banks accounting policy changes both before and after revision of the conceptual framework; and, (c) by analysis of the content of the comment letters written in to the IASB prior to revision of the QCs late March 2018. All the while, a Foucauldian discourse analysis is applied to try to understand the power, governmentality and subjectification forces in play moulding chapter two on the QCs in the CF.

The research questions asked are as follows:

Which qualitative characteristics do 'preparers' refer to when explaining their accounting decisions, and when do they refer to these qualitative characteristics?

And are the qualitative characteristics complete?

The research questions were informed by the researcher's ontological and epistemological standpoint and familiarisation with and critiquing of the literature, both of which helped to rationalise why the area of the IASB's QCs requires further research.

'As a reflexive researcher, it is important to write in a way that makes explicit your beliefs and assumptions, the theories that informed your work, and how you came to understand and interpret the data' (Paulus, Lester and Dempster, 2014, pp. 166-167).

While each data source of the thesis is reported upon separately, there may emerge a comprehensive evaluation of whether the revised QCs are complete, as well as the completeness of the constraints around the QCs. This research aims to improve the QCs noted in the CF, on post-implementation review, through evidence from the study, which together with further input from others in the accounting research community, shall possibly persuade the IASB to change the QCs based on this truthful, applicable, consistent, and neutral, authentic research.

1.3 Structure of the thesis

This thesis is organised into eight main chapters, outlined below to ensure that the reader is provided with a roadmap to make the journey easier:

Following the current introductory chapter, Chapter two provides a review of the literature concerning all the background issues to be explored in the present study. Specifically, it explores the development of the QCs over the last nearly ten years since the split of the IASB and the American Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB), looking at the seminal literature on the QCs of decision-useful financial information.¹ Chapter two has also considered Foucault and his key ideas by an overview of studies which have explored his concepts such as ‘governmentality’, ‘power’ and ‘subjectification’ as they involve the IASB and the CF.

Chapter three considers the research methodology, the transdisciplinary philosophical assumptions under which the research was contextualised in order to achieve a more complete, planned and meaningful research result. A theoretical background of both Foucauldian critical discourse analysis and content analysis in the context of the thesis is outlined.

¹ The composition of the IASB and a further discussion on its governance have been included under Appendix B, p. 214, at the end in order not to take away from the pith of this thesis’s message, but to add to it on the periphery, providing more background in-depth material on the IASB’s composition.

Chapter four considers the methods used, the data collection from interviews held with preparers and users, collection of changes in accounting policy notes from banks' sampled, together with the sampling of comment letters to be analysed.

Chapter five reports on the findings from a Foucauldian CDA of the semi-structured interviews, specifically looking at power, governmentality, and subjectification, all with an eye on what implications can be constructively gleaned for the IASB's consultation processes in the future. Foucault enables us to look at aspects of the IASB's interaction and outreach which affect the QCs used in the Conceptual Framework and it's issued standards.

Chapter six reports on the findings using content analysis from the semi-structured interviews, changes in accounting policy notes, and analysis of content of comment letters.

Chapter seven discusses the summary findings from the interviews, changes in accounting policy notes, and comment letters.

Chapter eight presents a metasummary, examines policy implications and recommendations made from the research, and provides avenues for further research.

1.4 Summary

This chapter has sought to introduce the reader of this thesis to the research topic being explored. The broad research area was outlined, and the structure of the present study discussed, providing a signposting for the remainder of the thesis so that the reader's journey might be more easily mapped.

Chapter 2 The International Accounting Standards Board, its Qualitative Characteristics, and Foucault – a Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The regulatory framework is the most important element in ensuring relevant and faithfully presented financial information and thus meeting the needs of shareholders and other users.

Without a single body, such as the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), being overall responsible for producing financial reporting standards and a framework of general principles within which they can be produced, the Conceptual Framework (CF), there would be no means of enforcing compliance with accounting regulations. Also, accounting regulations would be unable to evolve in any structured way in response to changes in economic conditions. In order to keep this thesis to a manageable size, coverage of the considerable literature pre-1970's in the United States and Britain has not been included, nor have accounting regulation objectives been addressed in detail for the public sector. Research has been positioned just prior to and immediately after the revised CF issued by the IASB late March 2018. Comment has been excluded in so far as it is not directly relevant to the objectives of what is known as 'general purpose financial reporting', the elements of financial statements being recognition and derecognition, measurement, presentation and disclosure, and all remaining aspects of the CF other than the qualitative characteristics.

In chapter two the discourse is established through which the Conceptual Framework was developed, using the Foucauldian concept of 'archaeology' (Foucault, 1982a) 'being the process of uncovering and unpicking the rules of discourse at any one time' (Gillies, 2013). It is this historical archaeology / genealogy of the development of the IASB's conceptual framework that needs to be discussed initially, through a Foucauldian lens, before again coming back to the key ideas of Foucault at the end of chapter two, page 41 onwards. It is important to do this in order to follow an archaeological understanding of how we have come to be where we are. Why the

use of Foucauldian analysis? Foucault's curiosity towards power, the art of governmentality, and subjectification as analytical tools allowed further focussed and detailed, methodical thinking about the discourse construction of the IASB and its relationships with its members and professional accountants.

2.2 The historical development of the IASB's Conceptual Framework

Much research on trying to formulate a Conceptual Framework for financial reporting was conducted in the United States since the establishment of the Financial Accounting Standards Committee (IASC) in 1973, founded in London, to assist accountants in the selection of appropriate accounting policies for given situations. Accountants found themselves ill-equipped because of a failure to agree on the fundamental principles of accounting (Everingham and Hopkins, 1992). The United States' Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB) published in 1985 what it thought was its final statement in its Conceptual Framework project, which was followed a few years later by a statement from the International Accounting Standards Committee on the topic in 1989, called 'Framework for the Preparation and Presentation of Financial Statements'. This framework was adopted by South Africa the following year and is when the researcher was introduced to its concepts. The IASC was a non-governmental body, created by professional accountants and other professional bodies, as well as securities regulators from many countries. The IASC was replaced by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) in April 2001.

The former IASC's creation was in response to the trend towards increasing globalisation and the concomitant need for financial reports prepared in different countries to be comparable, and to have a 'common language of accounting' (Whittington, 2016, p. 2). Such comparability reduced both costs and risks for preparers of accounts of international holding companies. The IASC developed its Conceptual Framework in 1989, as it attempted to lead rather than follow the existing practices internationally. The IASC drew on national standards, which at the time 'were most strongly developed in the English-speaking (Anglo-Saxon) world' (Whittington, 2016, p. 2). There, stock markets, and the consequent transparent financial reporting, had the greatest import.

The framework has many ancestors, but a key grandparent is the UK statement of standard accounting practice (SSAP) 2, Disclosure of Accounting Policies, published in 1971. SSAP 2 defined four fundamental accounting concepts: going concern, accruals, consistency and prudence. 'Maybe today we would consider adding disclosure or transparency to that list to ensure the implied duty of reporting to stakeholders is more explicit' (Williams, 2018, p. 24). The CF of the IASC drew upon that of the USA's Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB), as FASB was well resourced with technical experts from Anglo-Saxon countries. The IASC's own standards were being produced by similar technical experts, this time from the UK, the USA, Canada, Australia and New Zealand, and from within the IASC itself.

Whilst the FASB and IASC efforts were the most influential towards achieving an agreed accounting framework, there were many other efforts, most notable of these historically being:

- a. Studies commissioned by the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA) in 1961 and 1962 respectively entitled 'The Basic Postulates of Accounting' and 'A Tentative Set of Broad Accounting Principles for Business Enterprises';
- b. The FASB's predecessor, the Accounting Principles Board (APB), in 1970 issuing general qualitative objectives of financial statements;
- c. The Trueblood Report in 1979, set up by the AICPA came up with seven qualitative characteristics, finding their way into the FASB's Conceptual Framework project.

FASB's Statement of Financial Accounting Concepts (SFAC) No.2 in 1980, Figure 2.1, set out to discuss the qualities that financial accounting data should possess in order to render accounting information useful. The selected qualities are depicted below in Figure 2.1, forming an outline for evaluating information for inclusion in published financial statements. FASB's figure of qualitative characteristics from 1980 is the last time the qualitative characteristics were depicted figuratively. This section of the literature review concerned with the historical development of the Conceptual Framework shall continue with this depiction, and faithfully record below the best

efforts of the researcher to pictorially depict any updates upon milestones being reached, using the same figure as adapted for the relevant movements.

The IASC struggled to continue to lead with its thin technical resources, and large committees, particularly in complex areas such as financial instruments. The IASB replaced the IASC in 2001, cutting its Board numbers to twelve full-time and two half-time members, supported by a larger technical staff than the IASC, with greater income. The Trustees of the IASC Foundation raised large funds from preparers and users of accounts. Balanced representation within the IASB by preparers and users was an objective of the IASB, as well as geographical representation. The thinking of the Board was nevertheless bound to be dominated by its capitalist Anglo-Saxon country members (Table 2.1), over 70% of members, and the composition of its members by profession (Table 2.2), 60% between Regulators and the banking profession. The individual actors within the IASB's governance network have the largest number of professional ties to banking with 216, followed by 201 ties to national governmental regulators.

Figure 2.1 A hierarchy of accounting qualities

Reference: FASB's Statement of Financial Accounting Concepts (SFAC) No.2 in 1980

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Table 2. 1 IASB Members, 2001, by country of residence

USA	5
UK	2
Australia, Canada, South Africa	3
'Anglo-Saxon' sub-total	10
France, Germany, Switzerland	3
Japan	1
'The Rest'	4
Total	14

Table 2. 2 Professions of IASB's governance network

	Regulator	Banking	Academia	Business	Accounting	Other
International Accounting Standards Board	48	68	18	29	60	13
Public Interest Oversight Board	6	6	3	1	1	0
International Federation of Accountants	19	14	14	17	92	3
Bank of International Settlements	66	77	9	1	0	4
World Bank	32	48	4	3	2	10
International Association of Insurance Supervisors	11	0	0	0	0	1
International Organisation of Securities Commissions	19	3	0	1	0	0
Total	201	216	48	52	155	31
Percentage	29%	31%	7%	7%	22%	4%

Ref. to Tables 2.1 and 2.2: Goedl, P.A. (2012) Defining the IASB's governance network: a social network analysis. International Journal of Critical Accounting, Inderscience, 4(1), p. 39. Inderscience retains the copyright of the article and tables.

The Board had three tasks in the early 2000's (Whittington, 2016). They were, an 'improvements project', the adoption by the European Union (EU) of international standards, and thirdly, convergence with FASB standards. The 'improvements project' was a process whereby existing standards of the IASB were effectively 'patched' in order to allow EU adopters to have a stable platform when they adopted the IASB's standards from 2005 onwards. Adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) was not automatic, each standard having to be endorsed as being suitable for the needs of the EU. For example, IAS 39 (Financial Instruments) included hedge accounting provisions that were unpopular with the banks', and certain of these provisions were 'carved out' (i.e. omitted) from the IAS 39 version that was adopted and approved by the EU. Furthermore, the American-led 'Fair Value Option' also proved to be controversial in Europe. The European Central Bank (ECB), regulator to the EU banking system, opposed on prudential grounds the extension of fair value measurement for certain financial instruments. This dichotomy between the EU and America over fair value, has played out in tensions that arose internationally over the withdrawal of matching as a tenet of accounting in the early 2000's.

Running parallel with the creation of the IASB, was a convergence commitment arising from a Memorandum of Understanding Agreement signed by FASB and the IASB in 2002, the 'Norwalk Agreement'. This Agreement however constrained the IASB's scope, with the dominating Anglo-Saxon FASB having input to the IASB's agenda and resulting formulations towards Standard implementations and further recommendations. FASB's governmentality and power over the IASB arose out of the privileged 'inner circle' status it had attained through membership of the IASB and the number of support staff the FASB brought with it, as well as the momentum of the FASB's own continuing improvements projects. The IASB had become a follower rather than a leader, (adapted from Whittington, 2016, p. 180), who stated that in the late 1980s, the IASB...'attempting to lead rather than follow').

FASB's influence over the IASB was evidenced in the creation of a new, joint, Conceptual Framework for both the IASB and FASB, Figure 2.2. FASB sought to elevate 'decision-usefulness to investors' as the sole objective of financial statements, removing the stewardship objective. Financial reporting in the US was geared towards investors, whilst in the EU existing shareholders were the target audience of useful financial information for proper stewardship to be partly evidenced. Also proposed

was substituting 'faithful representation' for 'reliability' as a fundamental qualitative characteristic of accounting information. 'Prudence' was eliminated at this stage due to FASB's influence. These were fundamental differences when it came to the merging of both bodies Conceptual Framework's.

It is important to understand the fundamental differences that remained between the FASB approach and the IASB approach to the Conceptual Framework. A Conceptual Framework provides the background of principles within which standards can be developed. A CF is intended to ensure that standards are not produced which conflict with each other, and that any departure from a Standard can be judged based on whether or not it is in keeping with the principles set out in the CF. This is a **principles-based** system, favoured by the IASB. In the absence of a reporting framework, a more **rules-based** approach has to be adopted. This leads to a large mass of regulation designed to cover every eventuality, as in the United States under FASB, while a large volume of regulatory measures does not always detect or prevent financial irregularity. The exercise of professional judgement is minimised in a rules-based system, such that a principles-based system, the International approach, may be more appropriate for controversial areas of accounting as it allows the focussing on flexible overarching principles for guiding judgement (Carter & Warren, 2018).

Figure 2.2 IASB and FASBs combined qualitative characteristics, 2010

Reference: Updated and adapted from FASB (1980), Statement of Financial Accounting Concepts (SFAC) No.2.

2.3 Divorce of FASB from IASB in 2010

FASB and the IASB had initially hoped to develop a common set of standards that would be acceptable around the world (Camfferman and Zeff, 2018). Indeed, the IASB followed FASB in bringing fair value accounting into its own standards, thereby risking alienating its 'rest of the world' membership, by having a Conceptual Framework compatible with Fair Value accounting. The 'rest of the world' membership of the IASB, those that believed in stewardship as being the main usefulness of financial reporting, regaled against the SEC's belief that as its (the SEC's) markets were considered by them to be the most efficient in the world, that US generally accepted accounting practice (GAAP) was the most appropriate system of accounting, and IFRS accounts had to be reconciled with US GAAP, rather than the reverse. The CF is unlikely to offer solutions to accounting problems, although it should guide standard-setters in prioritising information as to decision-usefulness for investors, or stewardship for shareholders, or both.

Although joint work continued up until 2010 and even past that, convergence was becoming more difficult and time-consuming, particularly as US companies were not going to adopt IFRS, and other countries national practices embedded by their national institutions, complicated co-operation, with some aspects of the US's fair value not being adopted by other nations. The IASB began to work more independently of FASB on revising its own Conceptual Framework, along with downplaying the importance of fair value accounting in standards such as IAS 39 for banks', post the financial crash of 2008, as it was widely discussed at the time (Andre, Cazavan-Jeny, Dick, Richard and Walton, 2009) that the premise for fair value accounting, efficient markets, was not exactly true, and historical cost needed to be reinstated as a permissible valuation option, particularly in the EU. Indeed, it was premised that fair value accounting was a contributory factor in the financial crash (Plantin, Sapra and Shin, 2008), although other writers remained unconvinced by the evidence (Barth and Landsman 2010).

Since formal IASB-FASB convergence ended in 2010 (FASB, 2020), and leasing and insurance standards that both had worked on together had been issued, divergence started to occur, for example with minor amendments to IFRS 15 on Revenue Recognition, and more substantially with IFRS 9 on Financial Instruments. The

compromise remains that the FASB will remain the standards issuer for the United States, while endorsing IFRS rules and guidelines issued by the IASB to accommodate international companies and other countries reporting under IFRS.

2.4 Current developments involving the IASB

EU listed companies adopted International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in their consolidated statements beginning 2005. Within those countries whose national accounting setters have adopted IFRS, different versions of IFRS have arisen. IFRS as adopted by the EU for example, differs in several respects from the original IFRS as issued by the IASB, most notably on IFRS 9. Nobes (2006, 2013) surveys have revealed variations across jurisdictions in the exact version of IFRS formally adopted, especially as IFRS translated into different languages reflects nuances in the concepts raised, in enforcement, in accounting policy treatments and choices. (A full list of the issued IFRS's at the time of this research is shown in Appendix A).

There appeared to be and still appears to be a lack of support for the voluntary adoption of IFRSs' by the United States and China, certainly not for a mandatory adoption. Annual financial reports in China have to be prepared under Chinese Accounting Standards, similar to US GAAP and IFRS (Dezan Shira & Associates, 2017). Arguments put forward against the adoption of IFRS by the US include but are not limited to:

- a. IFRSs' are not sufficiently detailed and comprehensive;
- b. IFRSs' do not include industry standards;
- c. IFRSs' including IFRSs' for Small and Medium Entities (SME) are considered by some to be too costly to implement for small listed companies;
- d. Voluntary adoption would lead to non-comparability in US markets;
- e. IFRSs' would not necessarily be responsive to the needs of US firms;
- f. Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) and Congress would lose direct oversight over standard setting.

It is however to be noted that some 500 foreign issuers of annual reports listed or traded in New York already used IFRS, and the SEC chief accountant made a recommendation to domestic issuers to allow the adoption of IFRS in 'supplementary'

financial statements (Nobes, 2013), whilst in China, the opening of its stock exchanges to international listings may gradually soften China's resistance to go further with IFRSs' (Dezan Shira & Associates, 2017).

Nevertheless, informal consultations continue between the two Boards, even if formal consultations have ceased. This has resulted in FASB holding meetings unilaterally with a network of standard setters that it is building up, involving the UK, Germany, Canada, and Japan amongst others. The aim is of course to share experiences in order to promote worldwide comparability of accounting standards. Direct comparability of FASB's and IASB's qualitative characteristics diverged after 2010, with FASB publishing an updated hierarchy of accounting qualities in 2014, Figure 2.3, while the IASB reissued their accounting qualities in 2015, Figure 2.4, on publication of an exposure draft on the Conceptual Framework. Neither body provided a figure, only narratives, so the adaptations are by the researcher using the 1980 publication, as updated.

The revised Conceptual Framework has reiterated the need for those reporting under IFRS to continue to be principles-based, not rules-based as with the FASB, and the IASB has not increased the fair value principle as yet in its standards that were championed by the FASB. In the EU, companies and auditors are required by law to affirm compliance with 'IFRSs' as adopted by the EU'.

Due to globalisation and the demand for comparability of financial statements, more than 130 jurisdictions world-wide have now adopted IFRS for their domestic listed companies (IASPlus, 2018a), even though IFRS usually requires companies to publish more extensive disclosure information than under local GAAP. Both the FASB and IASB have now recommended that the disclosures in standards be reduced and

streamlined, after input from expert panel members, experienced practitioners, preparers and users' groups.²

² Indeed, the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Scotland (ICAS) and the New Zealand accounting bodies issued a report on just such 'excess baggage' (IASPlus, 2011).

Figure 2.3 FASB's qualitative characteristics, 2014

Reference: Adapted from FASB (2014), Concepts Statement No.8

Figure 2. 4 IASB's qualitative characteristics, 2015

Reference: Adapted from IASB (2015), Exposure Draft ED/2015/3, Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting.

2.5 Small island economies and the IASB

Globalisation is a strong economic and political force, which in turn drives the demand for globalisation in accounting. However, 'most political and commercial activity remains local, so adoption of uniform rules does not by itself lead to uniform reporting behaviour around the world' (Ball, 2016, p. 567). The adoption more than 19 years ago of the International Accounting Standards Board's (IASB's) IFRS and Conceptual Framework by many countries, essentially uniform rules, has not led to the claimed benefits of IFRS adoption being realised, due mainly to non-uniform implementation, from evidence gained by Ball, 2016.

Although the three largest economies have not adopted IFRS to date (US, China and Japan), likewise the four most populous countries (US, China, India, Indonesia), the overall record of formal adoption by jurisdictions is impressive, with 132 jurisdictions permitting or requiring IFRSs' for domestic listed companies (IASPlus, 2019a). As the Conceptual Framework implies, the conjectured benefits of IFRS adoption includes more efficient cross-jurisdictional transacting, increased transparency (being enhanced informativeness of financial reports), greater inter-company or inter-bank comparability of financial data, amongst other benefits and efficiencies.

Ball (2016) propounds that the actors in financial reporting which include preparers, auditors, regulators, users and others, are incentivised by political and economic forces. Ball's (2016) thesis, citing Ball (2006, p. 27) is that:

'politics and commerce are in large and varying degrees local, as distinct from global, leading to incentives and institutional structures that are likely to differ across IFRS adopting countries and to implementation that is likely to differ also as a consequence.'

Ball (2016, p. 547), notes that 'One benefit of widespread adoption has been that in some quarters (notably, Europe) adoption has been associated with increased attention being given to governmental regulatory enforcement mechanisms.' Ball (2016, p. 547) raises the concerns that have already come about such as the testing of Fair Value accounting (which records economic gains and losses more timeously) by the major financial crisis of 2008, and the 'effect on the IFRS brand name of

permitting its use by regimes without a strong interest in implementation and with low financial reporting quality, and the composition of the IASB governance in the long term.’

The IFRS brand name is in use by many economies that can be classified as small island economies. The Isle of Man (IOM) on the other hand, has not adopted IFRS for its own Government Accounts’, preferring to remain with FRS 102, which are technically simpler to account and report under. This too would be the stance of many of the IOM registered banks’, save for the fact that many of these banks’ are held by UK holding banks’, already reporting under IFRS, and whose accounting standards they are normally obliged to follow to make group accounts consistent by way of accounting standards used. Using IFRS, specifically IFRS 9 on Financial Instruments, demands timelier and more transparent consequences of loss recognition of banks’ financial instruments held, enhancing monitoring by analysts.

To achieve the gold standard of complete comparability requires adoption of identical versions of IFRS and their consistent implementation across jurisdictions. Small island economies make up a significant proportion of the jurisdictions where national standards have been retained, or IFRSs’ required for all banks’ required to report in those jurisdictions.

Table 2. 3 Use of IFRS by jurisdiction

IFRS status	No. of jurisdictions
IFRSs’ not permitted – national standards retained	22
IFRSs’ permitted	25
IFRSs’ required for all banks’	98
IFRSs’ required for some banks’	9

Adapted and extracted from IASPlus (2019a).

Local forces continue to exert what can be a considerable influence on actual financial reporting practice, notwithstanding the increased demand for convergence in accounting discourse and reporting standards, notably in Europe as political

processes have become more trans-national, aside from Brexit. European island economies for instance, which are members of the European Union's Island Commission, are not directly represented within the IASB, as the Island Commission itself has vires only to 'urge the European Institutions and Member States to pay special attention to the islands', particularly as regards economic and social cohesion.³ Not being directly represented within the IASB allows European island economies to avoid IFRS convergence if their own circumstances and regulations allow different financial reporting practices.

The pursuit of nissology, 'the study of islands on their own terms', Veenendaal (2018) citing McCall (1994, pp. 1-14), is an emerging area of academic research. The University of the West of Scotland houses the Scottish Centre for Island Studies⁴, and two of its areas of interest are firstly, considering the nature of islandness, and secondly and even more pertinently for this study, is island governance. The typology of islands as an ontological category has been shown by studies conducted by the university to have distinctive self-governing economies and cultures divergent from those of their continents in many cases, topical to this study. Veenendaal (2018) states that 'island nations tend to have significantly more liberal regimes than their continental counterparts'. The unique story of the concept of self-governance for islands is reflected again throughout this thesis.

2.6 Pre-eminent literature on the qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information

The main aim of a study performed by van Beest, Braam and Boelens (2009) was to contribute to improving measurement of financial reporting quality. There are very few papers which investigate more than two QCs, van Beest et al. (2009) does so by splitting the main QCs into twenty-one items (using IASB and other empirical literature before 2009 defining financial reporting quality in terms of the fundamental and enhancing qualitative characteristics underlying decision-usefulness), examining to what extent financial reports met each of the QCs separately and in combination?

³ Article 174 of the Lisbon Treaty

⁴ Reference: <https://scotcis.wordpress.com/island-studies/>

These twenty-one items were each operationalised using predictive and confirmatory statements. Van Beest et al. (2009) applied their approach by scoring these items for one hundred and twenty firms.

Van Beest et al. (2009) constructed a quantitative compound measurement tool to comprehensively assess the quality of financial reporting in terms of the underlying fundamental QCs (i.e. 'relevance' and 'faithful representation') and the enhancing QCs (i.e. 'understandability', 'comparability', 'verifiability' and 'timeliness'). Weighting the scores on the fundamental QCs higher than the scores on the enhancing QCs, they found a significant factor relationship between size and industry. Using two hundred and thirty-one annual reports from these companies listed on US, UK, and Dutch stock markets in 2005 and 2007, van Beest et al's (2009) compound measurement tool on internal validity, inter-rater reliability (Krippendorff's alpha) and internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha) was tested for internal reliability of the measurement scales, both alpha's being above that required to ensure reliable results. Their findings suggested that the measurement tool used in their study was a valid and reliable approach to assessing the quality of financial reports. The measurement tool contributes to improving the quality assessment of financial reporting information, fulfilling a request from both the FASB and the IASB to make the QCs operationally measurable. Van Beest et al's (2009) study contributed to the literature in several ways, firstly constructing a comprehensive measurement tool, based on the QCs, to assess the quality of financial reporting, improving on other measurement methods from prior research (Leuz 2003) (Roychowdhury 2006). Moreover, the quality of financial reporting was assessed to have been improving over the short three-year period reviewed. Limitations of van Beest et al. (2009)'s study are that it is based on a relatively small sample, and that the study's validity should be compared by measuring its results to the decision-usefulness of financial reporting as perceived by stakeholders such as equity providers or lenders. Alternatively, given that QCs are abstract and difficult to measure via empirical proxies or in an experiment, conducting a survey or interviews can be used to generate data about QCs. Dichev et al. (2013, p. 11) asked chief financial officers open-ended questions such as 'What does the concept of earnings quality mean?' 'Accuracy', 'faithful representation', and 'transparency' were amongst the most frequent concepts raised by chief operating officers in the context of reporting around good earnings quality.

The first empirical study using publicly available data to provide direct evidence about the role of QCs of financial information in accounting decisions, was done by Nobes and Stadler (2014). They asked the following two research questions in the context of IFRS accounting policy changes:

- 1) Which QCs do managers refer to when explaining their accounting decisions?
And
- 2) When do they refer to QCs?

Nobes and Stadler's (2014) hypothesis was therefore that managers more frequently explain a policy change by referring to QCs when the change concerned a measurement choice rather than a presentation choice, as size of accounting numbers is more important than presentation. In Nobes and Stadler's (2014) empirical analysis, they also investigated whether firm size, leverage, profitability and country factors such as cultural differences were associated with references to QCs. Nobes and Stadler (2014) hand-collected forty thousand, eight hundred and ninety-five IFRS policy choices on sixteen topics as found in the 2005-2011 financial statements of five hundred and fourteen firms from ten countries. These countries had large stock markets and firms using IFRS since 2005 or earlier. Nobes and Stadler (2014) employed content analysis in order to find the reasons given for IFRS policy changes. They found that more than half the reasons for accounting policy changes given referred to 'relevance', 'faithful representation', 'comparability' and 'understandability'. Firms also frequently referred to 'transparency', which is not directly mentioned in the CF. Nobes and Stadler (2014) also found that references to QCs in accounting policy changes were positively associated with a firm's size, and with a measure of transparency. This was also found by Barth and Schipper (2008). Nobes and Stadler (2014) commented that 'prudence' was seldom referred to, given the controversy about its removal from the CF in 2010. Logistic regression models with QCs given as a reason for change, along with topic, country, industry, size, leverage, profitability, and listing denoted as variables, were used to find statistically significant variables associated with references to QCs. Further regression analyses using measurement as a variable were used to test the hypothesis. Nobes and Stadler's (2014) regressions showed that references to QCs are positively and robustly associated with 'transparency' at a statistically significant 5% level. Nobes and Stadler (2014)'s scope for their empirical work was wider than in prior literature, because their methodology

allowed them to analyse a large set of QCs instead of just one or a limited number, for example, 'relevance' (Koonce, Nelson and Shakespeare, 2011), 'understandability' (Jones and Smith, 2014), and 'transparency' (Barth, Konchitchki, and Landsman, 2013). Other papers analyse two QCs together, such as Kadous, Koonce and Thayer (2012) who suggest, using experiments, that users do not view 'relevance' and 'reliability' independently. The overall findings of Nobes and Stadler (2014) should still be of importance to the IASB, even after revision of its Conceptual Framework, on post-implementation review, and indeed, it is in the researcher's mind the most important paper written on the topic of the qualitative characteristics in recent years.

Sutton, Cordery and van Zijl (2015, p. 117), also writing before the revised Conceptual Framework was published March 2018, proposed as their research problem the development of the CF as a foundation for developing accounting standards, not concentrating on the characteristics of decision-useful financial information. The paper reviewed developments in CFs' and general purpose financial reporting (GPFR), and asked the question 'if a coherent CF drives the development of GPFR standards, then specific standards would not require tight codification through extensive lists of rules', benefitting from examples instead to demonstrate the appropriate application of the principles. They further asked the questions of why a CF is important, and why the development of a coherent CF has been elusive. Discussion of 'reliability', now superseded by 'faithful representation', was also discussed in the context of Fair Value accounting (FVA) and perceived volatility introduced by FVA in financial reporting.

Sutton et al., (2015), to support their findings, did not collect data or do any analysis at all outside of providing what is essentially a discussion paper of concepts and thoughts, both from themselves, and from numerous other commentators such as Gebhardt, Mora and Wagenhofer (2014), Cascino et al. (2013), Zeff (2013), IASB (2010, 2013), and European Financial Reporting Action Group (EFRAG) (2007). Sutton et al. (2015) made the case that the primary purpose of a CF is to provide the principles for the development of accounting standards that will result in financial reporting which is useful to investors. They also argue that the diversity of users entails separating public entity financial reporting from general purpose for-profit entity financial reporting, even though there would ideally be coherent consistent general qualitative characteristics. Another area of intractable debate is in the dichotomy

between stewardship (a company's track record) and decision usefulness (linked to a company's prospects). This theme is explored further in this thesis, with data from interviewees and comment letters, and concluded upon, with recommendations made.

Carrying on the debate of Sutton et al. (2015) further, the European Financial Reporting Action Group (EFRAG) and the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Scotland (ICAS) issued a research report (Cascino et al. 2016), 'Professional investors and the decision usefulness of financial reporting', which examined the use of financial reporting by professional investors making valuation or stewardship decisions, and showed how the results of the research may have standard-setting implications. The empirical investigative evidence was based on both quantitative and qualitative data obtained from a series of eighty-one face-to-face interviews with professional investors based in sixteen countries. The research design permitted causal tests of five research questions, inclusive of the following two research questions (Cascino et al. 2016, p. 17) directly applicable to the CF:

- a. *'Does investors' information acquisition objective, valuation or stewardship, affect the assessed relevance of financial accounting information?'*
- b. *'Do professional investors assess information presented in the income statement and statement of financial position to be equally relevant and faithfully represented for the purposes of valuation and stewardship?'*

In assessing the research questions of Cascino et al., 2016, above, a large sample of professional investors were interviewed. The interviews were structured around a simple qualitative case study, where participants were asked to assume the role of one of the owners of a large European private manufacturing company. After reading the case, participants evaluated the usefulness of eight financial statement items as well as the usefulness of alternative information sources. The objectives of valuation or stewardship were randomly assigned to the participants. The case itself contained a summary balance sheet, annual income statement, and an outline of relevant IFRS accounting policies, as well as key points on areas where management may have exercised judgement in measuring and recognising financial statement items. More than half of the participants chosen by EFRAG and ICAS were characterised as accounting experts since they had either an accounting degree or a professional

accounting qualification (five with PhD's), and their occupational responsibilities involved some aspect of financial reporting from a preparer's perspective, as well as from a user's. The participants assessed the financial accounting information on a scale of one (strongly disagree) to seven (strongly agree), and the results graphically reported at 95% confidence levels. Cascino et al.'s (2016, pp. 5-6) research report discovered that:

- a. 'The objective of investors (valuation or stewardship) does matter, confirming much earlier seminal papers (Lennard 2007) and (Gjesdal 1981).
- b. Investors have strong reservations about the representational faithfulness of bottom line figures. This contradicts earlier research by Bauer, O'Brien and Saeed (2014).
- c. Regardless of its shortcomings, financial accounting information is a key input factor for investors' decision making. (Gassen and Schwedler, 2010).
- d. The quality of corporate governance, including audit, influences investors' assessment of the representational faithfulness.
- e. Different objectives for financial reporting need to be prioritised by standard setters;
- f. Investors' perceptions of corporate governance significantly affect their views of representational faithfulness.'

The EFRAG and ICAS issued another research report (Cascino et al., 2017) the following year, 'The Usefulness of Financial Accounting Information: Evidence from the Field' which examines whether 'relevance' and 'representational faithfulness', the fundamental qualitative characteristics of financial accounting information, are affected by investment professionals' information acquisition objectives. Cascino et al., 2017 found that investment professionals with a managerial performance evaluation objective (governance) assessed financial accounting information to have been less 'relevant' than those investment professionals with a valuation objective.

Furthermore, Cascino et al., 2017 found that investment professionals' views of 'representational faithfulness' were found to have been positively associated with governance, and negatively associated with the complexity of the accounting measurement system, improving understanding of users' views of fundamental qualitative characteristics of financial accounting information. These views of Cascino et al., 2017, are different from that of Gjesdal (1981) who earlier demonstrated that an accounting system designed for investment decisions will generally differ from one designed for managerial performance evaluation and control. The IASB has currently proposed through its revised CF to place more emphasis on providing information for assessing management performance (stewardship) (IASB 2105), which prompted Cascino et al. (2017)'s research looking into the fundamental question in financial accounting: whether a single set of general purpose financial statements can satisfy heterogeneous user needs, a question underlying the import of this thesis, and concluded upon in chapter eight with recommendations made for the title of the Conceptual Framework's chapter two on Qualitative Characteristics.

2.7 Other literature on the qualitative characteristics

Barker and Penman (2017) argue that the Framework's QCs are not so much a description of the properties of accounting information but, rather, of useful information in general. They state that it is reasonable that information should 'faithfully represent the phenomena that it purports to represent' (para.2.14), be 'complete, neutral and free from error' (para.2.15), and be 'relevant', that is, 'capable of making a difference in the decisions made by users' (para.28). These QCs can be characterised as virtuous but not concrete because they do not lead to discriminating decisions about how the accounting is actually to be done. Brouwer et al. (2015) argue that the individual standards are left to draw the line on uncertainty, without the benefit of explicit guidance from the CF.

Tenets of Good Corporate Reporting (ACCA, 2018), sets out ACCA's view of the general issues that affect the quality of corporate reports, along with the qualitative characteristics of good corporate reporting. The ACCA notes that however good the framework and diligent the preparers of (banks') corporate reports, tension inevitably exists between some of these characteristics: 'completeness' conflicts with conciseness and 'understandability', while entity-specific information may conflict with

'comparability' with other entities. Overall, good financial reporting maintains a balance between the qualitative characteristics. The ACCA (2018, p. 5) went on to state in its Tenets of good reporting that:

'A report will be more useful and understandable if only relevant matters are included and less significant matters are excluded. With online reporting, it is possible to structure the presentation in such a way that links to greater detail on any aspect can be provided for those users who want them.'

'It is a tenet of good corporate reporting that a reasonable balance is maintained between the various characteristics: relevance versus reliability, relevance versus comparability, and so on.'

In an effort to search for qualitative characteristics wherever they may be found, relevant articles on QCs under Islamic Finance were sought, none being found to be seminal. Most Islamic countries, about 120 including Malaysia and Saudi Arabia, use IFRS, and hence have adopted the IASB's CF along with its QCs, while only a few use the Accounting and Auditing Organisation for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI) (2015) Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting (Sori, 2017). In 2011 the IASB decided to establish a group called the Islamic Finance Consultative Group. The Group meets to focus on challenges that arise in the application of IFRS to Islamic Finance. No QC differences have yet been proffered by this Group, although AAOIFI's CF issued 2010 still uses the QCs of pre 2008 of the IASB, along with those rejected at the time of the IASB's ED 2008 on the CF, being 'high quality', 'true and fair', and more importantly, 'transparency', as tabulated by Sori (2017, pp. 6,7).

In developing the qualitative characteristics, the International Public Accounting Standards Board (IPASB) considered whether some characteristics should be identified as fundamental and others identified as enhancing, and whether the order of the QCs should be identified and/ or explained. IPASB were of the view that such approaches were not to be adopted, as otherwise characteristics identified (as they are by the IASB) as 'fundamental' or 'enhancing' may be perceived to be so weighted, even if not intended. IPASB believe 'all the qualitative characteristics are important,

and work together to contribute to the usefulness of information', with the 'relative importance of a particular qualitative characteristic in different circumstances being a matter of professional judgment'. Some QCs may not apply, such as when information that is not understandable, or is historic, cannot be deemed 'relevant'. IPSASB were of the view that 'the impact that legislation or other authority may have on the information included in GPFRs' is not itself a financial reporting concept' (IPSASB, 2014, p. 40). This is perplexing as preparers shall need to consider legislation as they prepare general purpose financial reports. Indeed, some disclosure items are required specifically by legislation outside of any accounting standard, and some legislation the IPASB submits may even prohibit disclosure of information, such as that classified as being subject to national security interests.

Considering the fundamental characteristic, 'relevance' individually, Beisland (2009) predicted that if no association exists between company value and accounting numbers, including disclosures, the financial report shall not be relevant for users and therefore unable to fulfil one of their primary objectives. This was corroborated by Tsalavoutas and Dionysiou (2014) who found that the level of compliance with IFRS disclosures is significantly positively associated with market values, thus indicating that IFRS mandatory disclosures are value relevant. ACCA (2018) states that reports should exclude immaterial detail, as this may obscure the significance of the relevant information they contain. The IASB itself has drawn up a Disclosure Initiative which aims to develop new principles of disclosure and guidance, and to clarify the existing principles. The IASB identified that there was not enough 'relevant' disclosure information, leading to inappropriate investing or lending decisions. Irrelevant information obscures 'relevant' information, reducing the 'understandability' of financial statements. Hezekiah (2019, p. 58) further clarifies that the revised Conceptual Framework states that '*hard-to-measure information, while not worthless, may not be as 'useful' as less 'relevant' but more definite information that is easier to measure*'.

Figure 2.5 Public Sector entities qualitative characteristics, 2014

Reference: IFAC (2014), The Conceptual Framework for General Purpose Financial Reporting.

'Reliability' as used in FASB's SFAC No.2 and the IASC's Framework was dropped in 2010, and 'faithful representation' was elevated to take its place as one of the two fundamental qualitative characteristics (together with 'relevance'). Both Board's believed that 'reliability' was too often mistaken for precision, and if 'reliability' were to outweigh 'relevance', the use of Fair Value measurement as advocated by FASB could be impeded. The revised CF defines 'faithful representation' over eight subsections, 2.12 to 2.19, referring to terms such as 'substance over legal form', 'complete', 'neutral', 'free from error', including all information necessary for a user to 'understand' the phenomenon being depicted, with 'neutrality' being supported by 'prudence', and where 'reliable' estimates need to be used where measurement uncertainty arises. The ACCA's Tenets of Good Corporate Reporting (2018, p. 4) states that:

'for users to be able to rely on the information in a report it should be unbiased in its presentation. A report will most often have to include estimates. Some of those may turn out to be inaccurate, but to be free from error those estimates should be based on the best evidence available at the time. Significant estimation uncertainties should be disclosed'.

After feedback received by the IASB, in the 2015 ED the Board proposed to expand the discussion of the effect of measurement uncertainty on the 'relevance' of financial information. The Board has published, alongside the revised CF, the fact that many stakeholders agreed that 'faithful representation' should continue to be identified as one of the two fundamental QCs of useful financial information. The Board admitted that some stakeholders continued to argue that 'reliability' should be reintroduced and that the following views had been expressed:

- a. 'reliability' is clearer and better understood (than 'faithful representation');
- b. 'faithful representation' incorrectly allows the recognition of items that cannot be measured 'reliably';
- c. the framework before 2010 had allowed a trade-off between the QCs of 'relevance' and 'reliability', such that 'relevant' information may lack 'reliability',

and 'reliable' information may lack 'relevance'. This balance was lost when 'reliability' was replaced with 'faithful representation'.

The Board itself concluded that it would continue to use the term 'faithful representation', as it more clearly sat with measurement uncertainty than did 'reliability'. An example the Board gave was of a situation where the level of measurement uncertainty involved in making an estimate may be so high that it may be questionable whether the estimate would provide a sufficiently 'faithful representation'. Barker and Penman (2017) state that to meet the objectives of financial reporting in the IASB's Conceptual Framework, the 'balance-sheet approach' embraced by the Framework is necessary but not sufficient. The profit and loss has equal status in the revised CF. By so doing, the revised CF reintroduces the impact of uncertainty on matching and mismatching in the income statement. Their paper argues that accrual accounting is inadequately captured, and that the matching concept would provide useful information to investors, yet the 'top-down' deductive approach embodied in the Framework, as the *modus operandi* of the IASB, rejects the matching concept. In recent years, the matching concept has fallen out of favour with both the IASB and the FASB (Zimmerman and Bloom, 2016), yet matching lends itself to certainty under historical cost measurement, because it can be understood as allocating incurred costs to recognised revenues. While imperfect matching cannot in practice be avoided, the concept of matching is nevertheless insightful. The concept of matching remains useful because it matters to users who need to understand when matching has not been applied.

IFRS (2018), Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting, s.5.5 p. 42, states that: *'matching of costs with income is not an objective of the Conceptual Framework. The Conceptual Framework does not allow the recognition in the statement of financial position of items that do not meet the definition of an asset, a liability or equity'*.

Barker (2015) provides examples where assets and liabilities are not capable of being matched in terms of applying IFRS.⁵ Barker asserts that as some internally generated intangible assets are not possible to have their cost reliably determined, nor their future economic benefits, such assets are not recognised. Yet, the exact opposite recognition outcome arises using IAS 37 where measurement of a provision is estimated as it is deemed to be an extremely rare case that an entity will not be able to determine a range of outcomes. Although the omission of the matching concept from the Framework has been emphasised, other 'traditional' accounting concepts such as 'stewardship' and 'historical cost accounting' have been overlooked.

Barker and Penman (2017) propose that consistent with the framework's 'enhancing' QC of 'verifiability', is that assets should be recognised with respect to a threshold for uncertainty. Indeed, Cade, Ikuta-Mendoza, and Koonce (2018) investigations found that individuals believed the probability of a future transfer of economic benefits must be above some meaningful threshold for an asset or a liability to exist, a belief which is contrary to standard setters' intent. Their experiments found that the majority of individuals used a high probability threshold to determine asset existence, whereas for liabilities, the majority use a very low threshold, even under *ceteris paribus* conditions. Liabilities are more frequently judged to exist than assets.

In more recent mission statements, the IASB emphasises the transparency of financial reports as part of the objectives of IFRS. However, it is unclear whether greater transparency translates to better quality financial statements, as mandating higher transparency requirements can lead firms to engage in costly real earnings management, i.e., structuring their transactions to hide information or achieve specific reporting goals. Although most empirical evidence suggests that transparency in financial statements is useful to capital market participants, these studies are silent as to how much transparency is optimal and whether greater transparency necessarily promotes overall efficiency. The European Parliament's Regulation 1606/2002 s.2.2.2 (2015), requiring the EU to adopt IFRS, states that IFRS adoption is intended to

⁵ Barker compared IAS 37 *Provisions, Contingent Liabilities and Contingent Assets* with IAS 38 on *Intangible Assets*.

achieve 'a high degree of transparency and comparability of financial statements'. This regulation is further enforced by the European Financial Reporting Action Group (EFRAG)'s concern with transparency for investors (Marshall, 2015, p.5). It is also the stated mission of the IFRS Foundation to develop standards that bring transparency, accountability and efficiency to financial markets around the world (IASB, 2018a, p.6). Earlier it was noted that the IFRS Trustees as a group have an interest in promoting and maintaining transparency in corporate reporting globally, IFRS Foundation Constitution s.7 (2016). This is not the same as 'transparency' as a pervasive qualitative characteristic of useful financial information. 'Contributing to transparency by enhancing the international comparability and quality of financial information...' is not the same as disclosing financial information that is transparent.

The Basis for Conclusions accompanying the IASB's Exposure Draft 2008 lists additional candidates for qualitative characteristics that were considered by the Boards, but not included in the proposals. One of them was 'transparency'. The combined IASB and FASB Board's, reacting to responses received from accountancy bodies, both concluded that this characteristic is subsumed within 'faithful representation' and 'understandability'. Indeed, FASB, 1980, has no mention of 'transparency', and FASB, 2018, p. 8, warns of the 'adverse economic consequences for some organisations, especially if that reporting sheds light on an area that was not previously transparent.' In the light of the collapse of the construction firm Carillion, and the review by the Financial Reporting Council (FRC) into the UK's corporate reporting standards under the UK's Corporate Governance Code, Paul George, the FRC's executive director of corporate governance and reporting, said: 'A lack of transparency in financial and governance reporting, undermines trust in business. More accurate reporting and better governance practices are needed to reverse this trend.' (City A.M.24/10/2018).

Within the industry of banking that is studied in this thesis, the British Bankers' Association (BBA) has published a new Code for Financial Reporting Disclosure setting out principles for providing clear and **transparent** information about the UK's largest lending institutions. In recent years, banks' have developed their disclosures to reflect not only new expectations under IFRS but also recommendations from market participants and regulators. In doing so they have worked through the BBA to

share good practice and enhance comparability. The BBA (2017) online under s.1 stated that:

*'Disclosures should be made at an appropriate level of granularity to aid understanding of the information or activity being explained. Judgements about the level of detail should balance the necessary need for aggregation to avoid information overload against the need for granularity to enhance understanding and increase **transparency** and should be based on information provided internally to key management personnel. Significant balances should not be left unexplained.'*

Reduced disclosures will represent reduced transparency. A way around this may be to provide information outside the financial statements subject to suitable safeguards, and conversely, for the banks' financial statements to contain information in certain cases that is beyond that required by the standards. Nevertheless, the IASB and FASB have both effectively ignored 'transparency', either as a qualitative characteristic, or as a 'constraint'. The only 'constraint' now referred to in the Conceptual Framework is the cost constraint. Although the Conceptual Framework does not define the term 'constraint', it can be equated in context to the term 'limitation' or to 'consideration'. Everingham and Hopkins (1992), p. 6-6, used in their graphical depiction of South Africa's 'AC000 hierarchy of accounting qualities' the term 'practical considerations' alongside the term 'constraint'. Supporting 'transparency' to be a qualitative characteristic has been the current literature mentioned above, in date order, Barth (2012), Dichev (2013), Nobes and Stadler (2014), AAOIFI (2015), Sori (2017) and lately, Williams (2018).

Even without necessarily improving reporting quality, IFRS may prove economically beneficial by narrowing cross-country differences and comparability of financial reports and promoting international trade. However, financial reporting quality is determined not only by accounting standards' but also by a country's legal system, culture, and institutions. As a result, researchers and practitioners have questioned the ability of a common accounting standard, even if mandated, to achieve convergence in the quality of reported financial statements. Several major IFRS-adopting economies have protected themselves from this concern by requiring a

national standard setter to review and, if needed, modify IFRS before they become the law of the land⁶. This approach to protecting legislative sovereignty may lead each national regulator to adopt certain standards while rejecting others and over time cause countries to diverge in their accounting standards. Many proponents of IFRS (De George and Shivakumar, 2018; Finningham, 2010) believe that IFRS reporting is of a higher quality than previous local GAAP and that its adoption improves financial ‘transparency’, lowers information asymmetry in capital markets, promotes cross-border ‘comparability’, attracts foreign capital flows, and consequently lowers the cost of capital for firms in adopting countries. Barth et al., (2012), also found that IFRS increases the ‘reliability’, ‘transparency’ and ‘comparability’ of financial reports. However, Jaggi and Low (2000) at an earlier time had found that international firms with more complex operations, have more to disclose to a wider array of stakeholders than purely domestic firms do. Even so, in difficult economic times, there is likely to be conflict between securities market regulators (for example Stock Exchanges) and prudential regulators (for example the Prudential Regulatory Authority (PRA) over accounting for financial assets and liabilities. This is where the big-four international audit firms play an important role by harmonising the interpretation and application across jurisdictions. The IFRS Foundation’s Constitution states that it is committed to ‘establishing international financial reporting standards that are of high quality, comparable and transparent’. This raises the question of why ‘transparency’ is not a QC? A further question is why ‘comparability’ is not more important a QC than the fundamental ones of ‘relevance’, and ‘faithful representation’? Also, under ‘comparability’ comes ‘consistency’ in the revised QCs.

“Consistency’ helps to achieve ‘comparability’. ‘Consistency’ refers to the use of the same methods for the same items, either from period to period within a reporting entity or in a single period across entities.’ (IASB 2018a, p. 18).

⁶ Publicly listed companies within the EU must comply only with IFRS endorsed by the European Commission (EC). The EC is not a national standard setter per se but a transnational EU committee.

The replacement of the term 'consistency' by similar terms, 'dependability' or 'trustworthy', due to similar taxonomy, has not been mooted by others, so shall not be further addressed in this thesis, as it does not have a groundswell of support from the literature.

In many countries, listed companies and banks' are required by their regulators to report at least quarterly, reflecting users' expectations as well, not for 'short termism' amongst investors, but to consider, regularly, progress against objectives of the bank. The increase in Regulators on the IASB Board may account in part for the ongoing discussion that is taking place over whether accounts should mandatorily be quarterly and not half-yearly as some stock exchanges require only, in order to meet the 'timeliness' characteristic. Ahmed, Neel and Wang (2013) found that IFRS-adopting companies have significantly decreased the timeliness of recognising losses due to income smoothing and the aggressive recognition of accruals.

The concept of stewardship or accountability is currently being discussed in the literature surrounding the ethos of the Conceptual Framework. The researcher's preferred term is 'Corporate Governance', a fresh, modern term that incorporates stewardship. The Institute of Chartered Accountants of England and Wales (ICAEW, 2019, p. 1) defines the term corporate governance as 'the system by which companies are directed and controlled'. Nevertheless, the literature began in the 1920's referring to stewardship, continuing to date in so doing. Stewardship is viewed as a key objective of financial reporting in addition to the objective of providing information useful for decision making. The matching of revenues with expenses in the income statement, which is accounting practice, respects a notion of stewardship in the balance sheet as opposed to one of decision-usefulness (Barker, 2015). A notable change in the IFRS framework was its exclusion of the stewardship role as an explicit goal of financial reporting, along with the claim that decision usefulness subsumes the stewardship role. The Board removed the term 'stewardship' from the CF in 2010, ostensibly because of translation difficulties across the EU and beyond. In response to feedback received by the CF project, the 2015 ED proposed to reintroduce the term 'stewardship' with an explanation of how the term is used, and to give more prominence to management's stewardship (Hezekiah, 2019) in describing the objective of financial reporting, which it did in section 1.3 of the revised Conceptual

Framework in March 2018. It has subsequently come to light that two IASB members, Chairman David Tweedie and Geoffrey Whittington, had filed views anonymously that supported stewardship and decision-useful to be two separate objectives, named as such in the CF. Although decision-usefulness could be broadly defined to include stewardship, a number of authors argue that the overlap between these objectives is incomplete and that the investment-related roles and stewardship roles for financial statements differ in terms of their needs for specific reporting attributes (Lennard, 2007).

While the concept of stewardship is not particularly well defined, in the research literature or elsewhere, the IASB's 2010 revision to its framework explicitly positioned decision-usefulness ahead of stewardship in the objectives of financial reporting (Zeff, 2013). It was Young (2006) who argued that decision-usefulness, as used in the US conceptual frameworks, leads to users who desire only information that the framework states is of interest to them, impeding the development of a broader societal role for accounting. Earlier writers commented on the fact that the FASB gave priority to investors through its use of 'decision-useful', perhaps because of the influence of the American Securities Acts' and the SEC, whose aim is to protect investors. On revision late March 2018, unshackled from FASB who believed in the term 'decision-useful' to preface the financial information that the qualitative characteristics form a coherent part of, the Board has 'dropped' the adjective 'decision' from the term 'decision-useful'. The Board now states that:

'The objective of financial statements is to provide financial information about the reporting entity's assets, liabilities, equity, income and expenses that is useful to users of financial statements in assessing the prospects for future net cash inflows to the reporting entity and in assessing management's stewardship of the entity's economic resources. (IASB 2018a, s.3.2)

The Conceptual Framework Feedback Statement (IASB, 2018b, p. 8) states that:

'In response to feedback, in the 2015 Exposure Draft the Board proposed to reintroduce the term 'stewardship' with an explanation of how the term

is used, and to give more prominence to stewardship in describing the objective of financial reporting.'

The interviews and comment letters have more on this subjugation of the term 'decision-useful' in chapter three.

The framework before 2010 identified the exercise of 'prudence' as a factor that can make financial information useful. 'Prudence' was described as 'the inclusion of a degree of caution in the exercise of the judgements needed in making the estimates required under conditions of uncertainty' (IFRS, 2015, p. 3). The Board removed the term in the 2010 CF, due to it being at odds with the FASB rules-based principles although it did not admit this was the reason, and in the 2013 Discussion Paper the term 'prudence' continued to remain omitted from the CF under revision because the Board itself decided not to consider at all the chapter on QCs of useful information. The Board states in its IFRS Feedback Statement (IASB, 2018b) that it was persuaded by those, both academics and practitioners, who argued that 'prudence' could help achieve 'neutrality' in selecting and applying accounting policies, and reintroduced the term for discussion in the 2015 ED. Some stakeholders tried to argue for the introduction of an asymmetric form of 'prudence', while the IASB stated that there is asymmetric 'prudence' within certain accounting standards, and that this should be allowed to remain (Deller, 2018b). That enabled the Board to reintroduce the term with a clear explanation, under 'neutrality', to bring clarity, that an asymmetric form of 'prudence' would conflict with the need for financial information to be 'relevant' and provide a 'faithful representation'. This is in line with FRS 102 in the UK, where it explicitly states that 'prudence' does not permit bias (FRC, 2015, p.29), which Hezekiah (2019, p. 58) defines as 'not allowing for overstatement or understatement of assets, liabilities, income or expenses'.

Finally, the Basis for Conclusions, accompanying the combined boards of IASB and FASB's Exposure Draft 2008 on the Conceptual Frameworks qualitative characteristics, listed additional candidates for qualitative characteristics that were considered by the Boards, but not included in the proposals. These include 'transparency', discussed above, and 'true and fair view' (this is equivalent to 'faithful representation'); 'credibility' (implied by verifiability); and 'high quality' (a term used by

the Islamic Finance Consultative Group). This is achieved by adherence to the objective and qualitative characteristics of financial reporting generally. One other candidate, 'internal consistency' was rejected because the Boards considered that such a requirement, although desirable and the goal of the Boards', could impede the evolution of financial reporting standards (IASPlus, 2008).

2.8 Foucault, the IASB, and the Conceptual Framework

2.8.1 Foucault: the key ideas

Foucault (1926-1984) was a prominent French philosopher in the structuralist and post-structuralist waves of French thought. Foucault's philosophical work oriented historical ideas that worked to our present understanding, to improve how we do things now. He looked back in the past to try sort out issues of his time, a philosophical historian, or archaeological genealogist, influenced in his approach by Friedrich Nietzsche (1874), and followed recently by Flyvbjerg (1998).

Foucault had no interest in business, however if he had he might have split companies into two categories: those that understand the power of taxonomies and those that don't, (Schumpeter, 2018). Foucauldian CDA concepts include but are not limited to power, problematisation, critique, scepticism, subjectification, textualism and governmentality. Foucault has his supporters and detractors in equal measure. Nevertheless, his work is valuable to help critique the discourse of the IASB and their Conceptual Framework in particular.

Although Foucault's ideas are expressed under linear titles below, there is a thread that binds power, governmentality and subjectivation. As the governing body of accountants, the IASB employs micro-practices to govern, with a governmental mentality underpinning those practices. Power emerges from such governmentality, with the processes of subjectification, also conceptually linked to governmentality, such as ethics, code of conduct and other governance structures.

2.8.2 Power

Foucault can be described as one of the most influential thinkers of our time (Faubion, 2019) through in part his work on power and institutional practices, particularly in the face of economic and cultural globalisation. Foucault's own work is aimed at challenging the forces that govern us in terms of the forms of language, apparatuses of power and other forces that shape how we think and act, the 'technologies of power'. Although Foucault combines the notion of power and domination in a Weberian⁷ tradition, he focuses primarily on structure. Structuralism, in its focus on cultural systems such as language, or familial networks and practices, showed how meanings did not emerge from a founding subject, but were generated from one's place in a system and relationship with others. Foucault would say one of the truly insidious things about the way power is wielded and people are controlled in modern times, is that simultaneously you are both a subject that is being controlled while also being an active participant in the system...an active participant that in some way, most times unknowingly, supports the existing power structure (Foucault, 1982b).

Foucault believed we (as professional accountants) live in a Panopticon, because we live our lives as though we are constantly being watched and held to those professional standards (Abraham and Bamber, 2017). Power works through accumulating a body of knowledge that helps to organise and legitimise a set of practices. Forms of knowledge are put to work to act on the consciousness of people so that their opinion is modified, and along with their opinion their way of doing things, their way of acting, their behaviour as economic subjects and as political subjects. Foucault's point about power is that if you can dictate the parameters that people use to understand the most fundamental things about their existence, the vocabulary they use to think about who they are, that is where true power lies. Foucault takes the concept of 'will to power' from Nietzsche; referring to the notion that meanings, ideas, rules, discourses,

⁷ German Marxist, who saw power as either authoritative or coercive, with authoritative power being the exercise of power which is seen to be legitimate.

knowledge and truths do not emerge naturally, but are produced in order to support, advantage or valorise a particular social group.

Four key principles informed Foucault's understanding of power. First, it is not a possession, but rather a relation, emerging as it does from governmentality and the processes of subjectification. Second, this relationship is not essentially repressive, on the contrary, it is largely productive in its effects. Power is productive in the sense that it shapes and moulds people, their dispositions and values, and their practices. Third, it can only be made sense of through its connection to forms of knowledge and discursive practices. Fourth, any relation of power can be resisted, if only because it necessarily constitutes and reproduces, in that relationship, oppositional categories, dispositions and forces.

Power for Foucault is not a thing, nor is it possessed by individuals or groups. Rather, it is both a complex flow and a set of relations between different groups and areas of society that changes with circumstances and time. Another important point Foucault makes about power is that it is not solely negative (working to repress or control people), it is also highly productive. Power produces resistance to itself. Power produces what we are and what we can do, influencing or determining how we see ourselves and the world. Foucault argues that forces of power are predicated upon, imbricated with and facilitated by various bodies of authorised knowledge (for example, the IASB's Conceptual Framework grounds knowledge and its discourses that proceed from certain background epistemological assumptions, ingrained within the culture that the accountant lives in). The thought that real power is today exercised behind 'closed doors', away from the public eye, is not what Foucault was saying. Foucault's point is that we imagine power as being a thing that can be possessed by individuals, as organised pyramidally, with one person (or committee) at the apex, operating via negative sanctions. However, people are as much products of power as they are wielders of it, and the IASB's power emerges from the actions of people within a network of power relations, mainly academics, the greater accounting profession, and user representatives (users of annual reports, in this case, banks' annual reports). Foucauldian analysis to the author's mind therefore asks the question of power and subordination, control and regulation of professional accountants, as well as the concomitant compilation of the Conceptual Framework Project's committee. Foucault

wished us to strive to build social structures (for example an IASB) that minimised the risk of domination, and to re-examine what we think we know in light of the effect that knowledge has on our lives. However, the main argument of Foucault's Repressive Hypothesis is that people's thoughts and behaviours surrounding, in this case, accountancy have been repressed by people in power.

Power is everywhere, and to Foucault, invisible. The ability for this power system to change behaviour has become so subtle, the micro-tactics of power have become so normalised in the (accountancy) world that most people don't even notice themselves gradually being shaped into a mould of normalcy. Foucault believed that power acts as a deformation of the individual, an exploitation suppressing individuality. In *Discipline and Punish*, 1975, cited by BBC Radio 4's Thinking Aloud programme (2019), Foucault proposes that power works through decentralised networks of institutions, where professionals have the right to institutionally classify individuals, through what he calls a disciplinary power, symbolised by the panopticon.

To Foucault, the people that are truly in power are the thought leaders within the sciences that control the dominant narratives about the way that things are in the universe (for example, the IASB within the accounting profession). Knowledge is intrinsically connected to power, and they, the IASB, are the ones that produce all the knowledge. The IASB control the parameters, the language, the concepts, the entire discourse that accountants use to determine who they are, what they care about and what things are worth spending effort on. The IASB controls the standard-setting process and even the Conceptual Framework (see Chapter 2.8.3 on Governmentality, and Appendix B, the IASB's Policy Development Process). Post the global financial crisis, ontologically, the IASB is suffering a legitimacy crisis due to accounting regulation being subject to unmatched political scrutiny, whilst its ideological strategy is operating to reinstitute its technocratic power, 'masked' as it is (Carter and Warren, 2018).

2.8.3 Governmentality

The IASB, headquartered in London's Canary Wharf, mirrors, in the parlance of Foucauldian times, the 'London Governmentalists' escaping the dead end of structuralist Marxism. Foucault believed that if a government (for government read

'IASB') is to function in a competent, effective, useful and economical manner, then there are areas that it should avoid, limits it should place on itself, and means that it should not employ.

Governmentality occurs when citizens are 'regulated' by the state and its institutions and discourses, educated to monitor and regulate their own behaviour. Power emerges from governmentality (and the processes of subjectification, see below) such that the notion of government for Foucault, like that of power, straddles a gap between 'government' today and personal conduct, so-called 'government of the self' (Gillies, 2013). The preparers of financial statements today do not govern themselves. To the extent that they disclose the qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information that they choose to use to explain the accounting policy choices made and accounting statements adopted, out of a smorgasbord of available characteristics, or not, is the limit of their independence. This relationship between 'upward government' (government for and by the people) versus 'downward government' (policing, enforcing the people, surveillance and control), is a Foucauldian discourse.

Many members of the Global Preparers Forum believe that the language used in many accounting standards is unhelpful (Deller, 2018a). The inclusion of terms such as 'shall' and 'as a minimum' mean that preparers and auditors feel they must include these disclosures, whether they are material or not. Preparers said they feel unable to apply judgement as to which are relevant, and which are not, and that it was unlikely that auditors would agree with this exercise of judgement. Allowing preparers to exercise judgement was crucial to finding a solution. Some felt that a measured approach would be useful, outlining which things must be disclosed by all entities, which should be disclosed if material, and which could be disclosed if it is felt helpful to the users.

'The whole forum discussion is a healthy part of the standards development process. By not making decisions itself in a closed discussion, the IASB intends to ensure that its new standards are more robust and fit for purpose. It may not be the easiest course of action, but it does allow a key conversation in setting and amending standards to take place' (Deller, 2018a, p. 51).

The IASB members are the key decision-makers in the development of IFRS standards. Table 2.4 below shows the backgrounds of current and past IASB members.

Table 2. 4 Where the IASB members come from

IASB members' background/ location	Number in 2017	2016 Constitution states	Number in 2012 (start of current chairman's term)	Number in 2002 (when IASB established)
Regulators	6	-	5	4
Preparers	4	-	3	4
Investors	1	-	3	1
Academics	1	-	0	2
Auditors	1	-	2	3
Total (Background)	13	-	13	14
Europe	4	4	4	5
Americas	4	4	5	6
Asia Pacific	4	4	3	2
Africa	1	1	1	1
Any area		1		
Total (Location)	13	14	13	14

Sourced from IASPlus <https://www.iasplus.com/en/resources/ifrsf/iasb-ifrs-ic/iasb-board>

Although the individuals rotate, the total number remains reasonably similar from year to year, at 13 or 14. In terms of where they were employed before joining the Board, there is a balance between those who have been regulators (either standard-setters or securities regulators), preparers of financial statements, investors, academics and those who have worked in audit. However, that balance has been changing, with a notable increase in the hegemony of regulators and a decline in auditors. Currently there seems too low a presence of investors, who are the ultimate customers for the IFRS financial statements, with a decline since 2012. The IASB's consultation due

process is meant to ensure voices from all stakeholders can be heard, but the ultimate decisions are being taken by a group of people dominated by those with a regulatory and standard-setting background. Investors, and auditors, seem increasingly under-represented. The final amendments to the 30 November 2016 IFRS Foundation Constitution saw changes in many areas including geographical distribution of the Trustees, professional background of the Trustees, size of the Board, professional background of the Board, and geographical distribution of the Board.

The regional respondents to the IASB's consultation processes illustrate the high European and low African and Oceania interest, while the respondents by entity illustrate the influence of national accounting standard-setting bodies, who allow their standards to converge with that of the IASB and hence are not independent of the IASB, while academics and preparers are in the minority of respondents. This convergence of national accounting regulations to international accounting standards, indeed, this delegation of governance over international accounting regulations in turn, to a private body, the IASB, is a significant example of what Goedl (2012) calls 'non-governmental global administrative law'. Stewart (2005) argues that non-governmental organisations (like the IASB), lack numerous procedural safeguards, such as accountability, oversight, participation in the (standards setting) process, and transparency of the decision-making process. This in turn means that users and preparers of financial statements should be concerned by the impact on international accounting standards of such lack of oversight.

The question for the near future is whether or not there shall be an attempt to exclude US representatives from the IASB Board, and from the IFRS Foundation Trustees, because even though FASB are members of both, FASB is engaging in international outreach of its own?

Governmentality by the IASB is also influenced by the appointment of a Chair and a Vice-Chair for the overarching body, the IFRS Foundation, being 'made with regard to maintaining a geographical balance', IFRS Constitution s.10 (2016). A review of the past nine years since the break by FASB from the IASB in 2010 has shown that the Chair and the Vice-Chair of the IFRS Foundation have come from Europe, and from the professions of Banking, which possibly could be deemed to have introduced bias.

Goedl (2012), p. 50, found during a social network analysis study that banking interests were more embedded within the governance network than any other professional, academic, or social group. Such intentional structural embeddedness in network governance may manifest itself as unbalanced, isolated cliques in which information is tightly controlled by in-member factions.

What is also of concern is that the Trustees are not forced to open all their meetings to the public, but may at their discretion 'hold certain discussions in private', IFRS Foundation Constitution, (2016), s.13(f). This non-opaqueness at the top of the international accounting profession brings with it its own claims of non-disputable bias in the Foundation's deliberations (Goedl, 2012). This is important to note, because even though the Foundation states in its Constitution s.15(d) that it may not determine the Board's agenda, the very next paragraph it openly states that it is the body that 'determines the basis for funding', an ominous phrase of governmentality, which may or may not have real world implications for the agenda of the Board.

The Monitoring Board of the IFRS Foundation, according to the IFRS Foundation Constitution ss.18,19 (2016), provides a formal link between the Trustees (who are approved by the Monitoring Board) and public authorities. The Chair of the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, acts as an observer to the Monitoring Board. Goedl (2012) found nearly 25% of the IASB's governance network came from the banking industry, specifically the World Bank and the Bank of International Settlements, holding the most influential positions of authority within the governance network. Goedl (2012, p. 49) presupposes that 'these banking institutions may exert a substantial influence to ensure that their interests are secured when it comes to international accounting regulations', which would come at the expense of other stakeholder groups. Another finding of Goedl (2012, p. 49) was in the type of banking ties noted. 'More ties were found in the investment banking subcategory than to academia, business, and other groups, which included unions, environmental, social and other interest groups not captured in another category' combined. This direct link at the top to the decision-makers of the accountancy profession by Bankers, which is controversial (Lazzarato, 2012), forms one of the bases for the selection of this research's one participant group, those heads of financial reporting at various UK and IOM banks', the 'preparers'.

Also, currently, five individual donors (the EU and the 'big Four' auditing firms) together provide 35% of the funding of the IASB. The key question is whether financial contributions give you influence at the IASB. The dependence on a few donors does not look right. As the constitutional separation of the Board from its Trustees is meant to guard against this, the IFRS Foundation trustees have more work to do on balancing the Board membership, and on spreading the financial burden (Martin, 2017). The Constitution of the IFRS Foundation states that one of its objectives, 2(d), is:

'to promote and facilitate adoption of the IFRS standards, being the standards and IFRIC Interpretations issued by the board, through the convergence of national accounting standards and IFRS standards.'

From this objective, it is clear that the IASB believes national accounting standards need to converge, further evidence of the governmentality of the IASB.

Each member of the Board has agreed contractually to 'act in the public interest' although 'public interest' is not defined, and to 'have regard to the Board's CF (as amended from time to time) in deciding on and revising the standards'. As for the IFRS Foundation, the appointment of a Chair and Vice-Chair(s) of the Board 'should be made with regard to maintaining a geographical balance', IFRS Foundation Constitution, (2016) s.29 p. 9. Although the Constitution in s.31 states that 'secondments and any rights to return to an employer would not be permitted', there is evidence that this section has not been strictly adhered to of late. Supporting this indirect but implied allegation of influence and non-impartiality, is the fact that 'part-time members of the Board are not expected to sever all of their employment arrangements' (s.31).

It is interesting that one of the objectives of the IFRS Foundation mentions transparency, while another continues with a governmentality theme, a) and d) respectively:

- a) *'To develop, in the public interest, a single set of high quality, understandable, enforceable, and globally accepted financial reporting standards based upon clearly articulated principles. These standards*

*should require high quality, **transparent** and comparable information in financial statements and other financial reporting to help investors, other participants in the world's capital markets and other users of financial information make economic decisions.'*

- d) *'to promote and facilitate adoption of the IFRS standards, being the standards and IFRIC Interpretations issued by the Board, through the convergence of national accounting standards and IFRS standards'.*

The IFRS Foundation Trustees 'comprise individuals that, as a group, provide a balance of professional backgrounds, and have an interest in promoting and maintaining **transparency** in corporate reporting globally'.

The IASB does consult with organised feedback groups including the Accounting Standards Advisory Forum (ASAF), the European Financial Reporting Advisory Group (EFRAG), national standard-setters throughout the world, the Capital Markets Advisory Committee, the Global Preparers Forum, and others, including Asian-Oceanic, Latin American, Pan African, and Islamic consultative groupings on standard-setting. This consultation goes somewhat towards ameliorating the adequacy or otherwise of the Board's budget, and quality and training of its own staff. The IFRS Trustees have arranged stable funding packages receivable from many countries individually and from the EU. Referenced by Zeff (2015) p. 26, updated to 2017, the total contributions of £25.1m were derived from the following main sponsors by geographical areas: 35% Europe, 35% international audit firms, and 25% Asia-Oceania. The main sponsors by jurisdiction were: European Union, collectively, from only nine of the member states, (£3.8m), Japan (via its Financial Accounting Standards Foundation of Japan) (£2.3m), China (£1.9m), France, additionally (£0.9m), UK (levies by FRC in addition) (£0.9m), Germany, additionally (£0.8m), and United States (£0.7m). What is of interest is the list of regions and countries who contributed little if any towards the running of the IASB. They include Dubai (UAE), Pakistan, and all Latin American countries and African countries except for Brazil (£0.2m) and South Africa (£0.1m). Paradoxically, China and Japan, two of the largest individual contributors in 2017, both do not require the use of full IFRSs'.

Eisenschmidt and Krasodomska (2017, p. 117) comment that there is still a lack of participation in the IASB's due process. 'Despite the huge impact of accounting norms on societies, only a limited number of constituents participate, and some constituent groups, like users or academics, participate less'. This was based on their study of comment letters written into the IASB and their length, as proxies for constituents' formal participation in the IASB's due process.

Figure 2. 6 Overview of the structure of the IFRS Foundation and IASB

Ref: IASPlus, Overview of the structure of the IFRS Foundation and IASB [Online]
 Available: <https://www.iasplus.com/en/resources/ifrsf> [Accessed: 8 September 2019]

2.8.3.1 Neoliberal governmentality and the IASB's 'rationality of rule'

Governmentality, derived from the work of Foucault, gained popularity within social policy in the decade after the millennium (McKee, 2009). Although applied by different people in different ways, Governmentality has nonetheless been embraced as a valuable theoretical perspective for understanding power and rule across diverse fields including parastatals such as the IASB (Clarke et al., 2007). Foucault's original essay on governmentality emerged from a lecture series that he presented at the College de France in the 1970s, which was concerned with tracing the historical shift in ways of thinking about and exercising power in certain societies (Elden, 2007). Foucault highlighted the emergence of a particular rationality of rule in early-modern Europe, in which the activity of government became separated from the self-preservation of the sovereign and redirected towards optimising the well-being of the population, hence making this population potentially more 'docile' and 'productive' (Foucault, 2003a, 2003b).

Foucault highlights that these centralising and decentralising forces are not necessarily mutually exclusive. Whilst he clearly rejects the state (or in this case, the IASB) as a unified and monolithic all-powerful ruler, Foucault nonetheless continues to emphasise its importance as a 'site at which power condenses' (Cowan and McDermont, 2006, p. 182). Centralising tendencies continue to coexist alongside decentred modes of neo-liberal governance (Stenson, 1998, p. 337). There is a strong paradoxical co-existence of governmental strategies by the IASB seeking to devolve control to the local users of its conceptual framework, whilst simultaneously recentralising control within its apparatus by deciding ultimately which revisions are made to the conceptual framework's qualitative characteristics. The IASB also holds onto a mode of power which is both voluntary and coercive, for whilst it is premised on the autonomy and independence of accountants, it nonetheless seeks to ensure compliance to governmental objectives through top-down modes of surveillance and (potentially) punitive statutory interventions vis-à-vis the accounting profession's regulation and inspection regime. Zhang, Y. (2011) went further by commenting upon the bias underlying the IASB's conceptual framework that promotes the interest of neoliberal financiers in neoliberal global free-markets.

This thesis contributes to current knowledge by revealing the governmentality role that the IASB plays during this period of neoliberal 'financialisation', exploring particular mentalities of rule in the context of banks' and banking associations' preparers of annual report accounting policies, and the users of the same annual reports.

2.8.4 **Subjectivity and subjugated knowledge**

Foucault (2002a), in *The Order of Things*, addresses three epistemological paradigms: reflexive knowledge (produced by and through authorised fields), the logics of everyday practice, and an in-between region. Foucault's work is concerned with formulating an understanding of how certain paradigms come to stand for and function as truth. Foucault points to the possible insurrection of subjectified forms of knowledge, that is, to historical contents that have been buried or masked in functional coherences or formal systematisations. These subjectified forms of knowledge are regarded as non-conceptual ways of knowing that are naive, inferior and insufficiently elaborated, and below the required level of erudition or scientificity.

Subjectified knowledge is a form of knowledge that has been 'buried' under the official or dominant forms of knowledge that emerge within a social order. When both the board's of FASB and the IASB issued a discussion paper in July 2006 and an exposure draft in May 2008 on the Conceptual Framework, neither board had held a public hearing, so the views of users, professionals and other academics had in the researcher's viewpoint been subjectified, which meant that the IASB / FASB board's could drive their Conceptual Framework projects in the direction they deemed most desirable for themselves, and not necessarily having users and preparers of financial reports requirements to heart. Furthermore, the Board has responsibility for approving and issuing International Financial Reporting Interpretations Committee (IFRIC) Interpretations, and Exposure Drafts, Figure 2.6, yet there is no oversight that any dissenting opinions are not suppressed. Horngren (1981), a former conceptual framework standard setter, argued that each member of a standard-setting board has his own 'individual conceptual framework' based on many years of professional experience. Regardless of the Board's agreed-upon framework, the members' individual frameworks may be the ones ultimately that shape standards and interpretations. These persons individual frameworks may carry such weight that they have an impact even on the selection of the objectives. It is a fact that Solomons

drafted Statement of Financial Accounting Concepts (SFAC) No. 2 for the FASB in 1980, and then served as a consultant to the IASC during the drafting of its Framework, while Tweedie chaired both the UK's ASB from 1990 to 2000, and then the IASB from 2001 to 2011. These 'intellectual linchpins' have played a role in two or more frameworks.

Foucault also analysed how individuals self-govern themselves, drawing on Nietzsche, so that truth is what is accepted in 'games of truth' (Foucault, 2000), and what it is that is required of an individual to be valorised within the discourse of accounting. Individual accountants not only come to occupy spaces in the social hierarchy, but through their continual subjectification positioned as they are professionally, through their profession's ethics and code of conduct within accounting's governance structures, come to know and accept their place. Subjectification's many forms coalesce on both direct grounds of performance management and accountability systems, and indirectly from leading and controlling or persuasive influential individuals or accounting bodies.

Other Foucauldian concepts, relative to the IASB, specifically problematisation, critique, scepticism and textualism, have all been explored and discussed for this thesis, yet allocated to an Appendix C, due only to the fact that a narrow emphasis is being placed herein on Foucault's concepts of power, governmentality and subjectification.

In summary, the apparent incongruity of bringing a Foucauldian lens to bear on the field of accounting can be justified by outlining exactly how Foucault's work can shed new light on the topic. On the one hand is the great challenge it mounts in terms of power, problematisation, critique, scepticism, subjectivity, textualism and governmentality; on the other hand, is the analytical reward that can be reaped by applying his tools and concepts to issues within accounting discourses (adapted from Gillies, 2013).

2.9 Summary

The literature review confirms that the last time the qualitative characteristics were figuratively shown was in FASB's Statement of Financial Accounting Concepts (SFAC) No.2 in 1980, Figure 2.1. FASB's influence over the IASB was evidenced in the later creation of a new, joint, Conceptual Framework for both the IASB and FASB, Figure 2.2 by 2010 where 'reliability' as a fundamental QC was replaced by 'faithful representation', while 'prudence' supporting 'reliability', was eliminated altogether. On these two bodies 'divorce' in 2010, direct comparability diverged, the literature on financial reporting further showing that the US (FASB) were geared towards investors with a decision-useful aim, while the EU dominated by the IASB required governance or stewardship to be financial reporting's underlying main aim.

FASB's governmentality and power over the IASB arose out of the privileged 'inner circle' status it had attained through membership of the IASB and the number of support staff the FASB brought with it on merging, as well as the momentum of the FASB's own continuing improvements projects (Whittington, 2016).

Pre-eminent literature around the qualitative characteristics included van Beest et al. (2009) who split the main QCs into twenty-one items, all within fundamental and enhancing classifications under a decision-usefulness approach, while the first empirical study using publicly available data to provide direct evidence about the role of QCs of financial information in accounting decisions, was done by Nobes and Stadler (2014). Sutton et al. (2015) made the case that the primary purpose of a CF is to provide the principles for the development of accounting standards that will result in financial reporting which is useful to investors, while the European Financial Reporting Action Group (EFRAG) and the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Scotland (ICAS) issued a research report (Cascino et al., 2016), 'Professional investors and the decision usefulness of financial reporting', which examined the use of financial reporting by professional investors making valuation or stewardship decisions, and showed how the results of the research may have standard-setting implications. This study also includes an exploration of the IASB's qualitative characteristics that have been used by banks' in a small island economy, an aspect of nissology (Veenendaal, 2018).

This thesis sets out to explore the completeness of these qualitative characteristics after the literature review showed no overarching conceptual context of the qualitative characteristics that was universally agreed upon, using both Foucauldian critical discourse analysis and content analysis paradigms to elucidate the inclusion conundrum. Foucauldian analysis allows a focus on power relationships, governmentality and subjectification in accounting society, as expressed through language and practices of the IASB who ultimately decide on the qualitative characteristics, and the IASB's interaction with professional accountants preparing international, domestic UK and local Isle of Man (IOM) banks' annual reports.

In conclusion, this literature review introduces the reader of this thesis to the topic being investigated. This study's exploration will attempt to contribute to the growing literature around the qualitative characteristics through the use of Foucauldian critical discourse analysis and content analysis, forming the theoretical underpinning of the current study. Chapter three will discuss the research methodology and approach adopted.

Chapter 3 Research Methodology and Methods

3.1 Introduction

Chapter one provided the historical background to the International Accounting Standards Board's (IASB's) qualitative characteristics, introducing Foucauldian concepts. This chapter two outlines the philosophical assumption and research methodologies adopted, along with a critique of the pre-eminent literature driving the methodologies used in this current study.

Creswell and Miller (2000) noted that qualitative research is characterised by a concern for meanings, patterns of behaviour and the way that people understand things, going on to suggest that the choice of validity procedures is governed by two perspectives: the lens researcher's choose to validate their studies and the researcher's paradigm assumptions. Creswell and Miller also asserted that axiological assumptions require an acknowledgment by the researcher that there are inherent biases in the research, which reflect the values of the researcher and the values of the research topic. Also noted is that qualitative research does have its limitations in that it may not be representative, thereby restricting its generalisability (Denscombe, 2003).

In locating and justifying this research, the researcher's ontological, meta-ontological, and epistemological standpoints (i.e. how the world is understood to work, and how it can be investigated) have been reflected upon. Foucault, a post-structuralist and post-modernist philosopher, has been incorporated as the philosophical *weltanschauung*, using Foucauldian critical discourse analysis, focusing on power relationships in accounting society as expressed through language and practices of the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) who ultimately decide on the qualitative characteristics (QCs), and the IASB's interaction with professional accountants preparing international banks' annual reports. A post-modern post-structuralist approach was adopted, while retaining awareness of Zeeman et al., 2002, p. 96:

'It does appear that there is a large amount of work out there that makes a loose claim to using Foucault simply because there is some discussion of power and a few quotes from Foucault thrown in.'

3.2 Foucauldian critical discourse analysis – a theoretical background

In this sub-chapter a brief picture of critical discourse analysis (CDA) and the various approaches from an epistemological perspective are provided, mentioning some criticism which CDA has been confronted with in past years. The aim is to historically and theoretically situate Foucauldian critical discourse analysis, reviewing its key principles, and to codify the discourse power of the dominant group in this research, the IASB. CDA is a repertoire of political, epistemic stances, for the critical analysis of the place and force of language, discourse, text in changing contemporary social, economic, and cultural conditions (Luke, 1997; van Dijk, 1997). The CDA approach to text analysis draws on the post-Marxist, post-structuralist, Frankfurt School of critical theory, more fully generated by the French philosophers' Foucault and Derrida, who looked at the nature of language and its meaning.

'CDA involves a principled and transparent shunting back and forth between the microanalysis of texts using varied tools of linguistic, semiotic, and literary analysis and the microanalysis of social formations, institutions, and power relations that these texts index and construct.' (Luke, 2002, p. 103).

'CDA sets out to capture the dynamic relationships between discourse and society, between the micropolitics of everyday texts and the macropolitical landscape of ideological forces and power relations.' (Luke, 2002, p. 100).

Foucault (1982a) argues that discourse, systemically recurrent statements, tends to take a life of its own, autonomous from its historical authors. 'For Derrida, the absent signifier, the 'unsaid' and the 'unwritten', can be as significant as what is said' (Luke, 2002, p. 104). The silent and the absent, represented in implied intertextual

references, can have powerful political effects, although Freire and Macedo (1987) raised the possibility of nonideological text that is counter-ideological, acting to articulate and configure collective interests in transformative ways. Fairclough (2005) identified that critical discourse analysis can address how particular discourses become hegemonic and internalised within particular organisations, and on how discourse figures within the strategies pursued by groups of social agents to change organisations in particular directions.

Critical discourse analysis as an approach to the examination of language and its use by individuals and groups to enact specific identities (Gee, 2005), can be applied to a variety of different scenarios, such as globalisation, which is reflected upon briefly in this research through the use of a few countries' annual reports and interviews with users from countries shown in Table 2.1, as well as the global reach of the IASB itself. Phillips and Hardy, 2002, explored how discourse could come to have a particular meaning today, when 40 or 50 years ago it might have had a different meaning. This social and historical context in which discourse is embedded is of relevance to this study as the United States' Financial Accounting Standards Board's 1980 Hierarchy of Accounting Qualities, Figure 2.1, originally used the term 'reliability' which encompassed at the time 'faithful representation', while today 40 years later, such hierarchy has been reversed, with 'reliability' subsumed or marginalised within the more privileged 'faithful representation'. Keenoy, Oswick and Grant (1997) referred to how discourses compete with one another for dominance in what is termed a 'dialogical struggle'. Phillips and Hardy (2002, p. 8) also warned about 'particular actors drawing on the discourse to legitimate their positions and actions', a bias that is hoped has been avoided in this research.

Wodak (2013, p. 33) states that 'CDA constantly sits on the fence between social research and political argumentation', while Foucauldian critical discourse analysis, its key principles, current dilemmas, and possible futures, aid practitioners to act as 'transformative intellectuals in the task of unveiling, countering and consciousness-raising around dominant ideologies, with the aim of mobilising opinion and action against them and their class of producers' (Luke, 2002, pp. 105-106).

Support for this study's choice of Foucauldian critical discourse analysis (CDA) from the literature comes from Bryman's, (2012, p. 547), description of the method being 'a form of discourse analysis that emphasises the role of language as a power resource that is related to ideology and socio-cultural change. It draws on the theories and approaches of Foucault.' Schrato, Danahar, and Webb, (2012), added that Foucault also looked at hermeneutics, the branch of knowledge dealing with the interpretation of texts in relation to their historical context or 'archaeology'.

Another argument for adopting a Foucauldian CDA is that Foucault sought to uncover the representational properties of discourse as a vehicle for the exercise of power. The epistemology of critical realism argues that discourses should be examined in relation to social structures, including the power relationships that are responsible for occasioning them (Reed, 2000).

As a result of this research engaging in a critical conversation over the use of power, governmentality, and subjectification, the epistemological framework lends itself to that of Foucauldian CDA. As it is difficult to find coherent descriptions of how one might go about CDA using Foucault, the adopted framework may possibly be called CDA using a Foucauldian lens. Claiming to use Foucauldian CDA is a paradox, in that Foucault was not clear with his methods. Consequently, if prescriptive models are to be used so that the research can be repeated or triangulated in order to be taken seriously and counted as quality research, this work might be considered by some to be unFoucauldian (or 'Foucauldianistic') (Graham, 2005).

The methodological plan was to perform a poststructural discourse analysis that is informed by and consistent with the work of Foucault. The use of Foucauldian CDA as an epistemological framework was informed by the work of Foucault, not particularly by how language works within power relations (Taylor, 2004). Indeed, Derrida argued that there will always be other perspectives from which to interpret the material under review (Graham, 2005, p. 3). To seek a definitive account is, thus, a misguided undertaking. Wetherall (2001, p. 384) as a poststructuralist argued that 'the process of analysis is always interpretive, always contingent, always a version or a reading from some theoretical, epistemological or ethical standpoint.'

In the current climate privileging scientific or evidence-based paradigms, the problem becomes how can one remain open to poststructural undecidability without being accused of unsystematised speculation? (Allan, 2004). This is the hegemony of theory, when most people think alike about certain matters, or even forget that there are alternatives to the status quo, the Gramscian concept of hegemony. For example, Foucault did not systematise how to perform genealogy in order for it to have been deemed authentic, rather, as in *The Archaeology of Knowledge* (Foucault, 1982a) or *The Order of Things* (Foucault 2002a), he was specifically explicit about what he was doing, using methodological judgement. The method in this thesis too was not prescriptive, rather subjective. The ambiguity arising from such subjectivity affected generalisation of the research, requiring triangulation and repetition to avoid.

The purview of Foucauldian CDA could have included the documentation of minority discourses, diasporic voices, texts and statements that were 'written out' and over by the dominant IASB or their subservient accountancy professional and national bodies, or in this research's context of local bank participants, it might have shown a countenance to the IASB's dominant pedagogic discourse aimed at the IASB's own conservation of identity, towards a more blended form of governmentality.

In the context of this research, Foucauldian CDA is an exercise in explicating statements that function to place a construction rhetorically. The research may find that there has been little self-regularity and self-government by professional Accountants, as the IASB may have codified certain practices such as the QCs to such an extent that accountants have subjectified themselves to what the accounting standards say must be disclosed when they have to make changes in their accounting policies and publicise same in their annual reports. Accountants may be shown through this research not only to come to occupy spaces in the social hierarchy beneath the IASB, but through continual subjectification, come to know and accept their place.

All the while, intellectual freedom has been sought by using a Foucauldian paradigm, whilst remaining within and respecting the expectations of a community of scholarship although the researcher is not outside the power of the IASB due to his profession as an accountant.

3.3 Foucauldian critical discourse analysis – the actual method deployed

The actual method of critical discourse deployed in this thesis, the connection between theory and the discourse, can be illustrated in terms of figure 3.1. It is a general social theory in which the theory, the conceptual framework's qualitative characteristics, are operationally conceptualised. The qualitative characteristics included by the IASB are defined within the text of the Conceptual Framework, allowing interpretation only selectively by users and preparers of banks' annual reports.

The extent to which the user or preparer of banks' annual reports can influence the qualitative characteristics is explored initially through interviewing both users and preparers, asking questions over both the possible subjugation of other plausible qualitative characteristics by the IASB, and the governmentality of the IASB by restricting the qualitative characteristics that can be used and their ranking as fundamental or enhancing in the Conceptual Framework.

The second step is to analyse the text from the changes in accounting policy notes of banks prepared both before and after the revision of the Conceptual Framework late March 2018, to establish further the governmentality and power of the IASB's discourse and the subjectification of users and preparers.

The third step involves data collected from the comment letters sent in to the IASB, and amongst other enquiries, analysing the comment questions and answers, using intellectual freedom to subjectively interpret the discourse arising from the comment letters from banks' and banking associations'.

The uniqueness of this study is that it innovatively applies a Foucauldian critical discourse analysis lens to the IASB's formulation and implementation of its Conceptual Framework's qualitative characteristics, within a paradigm of governmentality, power, and subjectification.

Figure 3. 1 Foucauldian CDA as a circular process

Reference: Adapted from Wodak, R and Meyer, M (2009) Critical Discourse Analysis: History, Agenda, Theory, and Methodology. Methods of critical discourse analysis, chapter 1, p. 24.

3.4 Content Analysis – a theoretical background

Complementing the Foucauldian critical discourse analysis methodology used in this research, in an attempt to satisfy the research objectives, is the technique of content analysis. Content analysis is a widely used qualitative research technique designed to interpret meaning from the content of data in the form of text, using various coding schemes.

‘The specific type of content analysis approach chosen by a researcher varies with the theoretical and substantive interests of the researcher and the problem being studied (Hseih and Shannon, 2005, p. 1277, citing Weber, 1990).’ Krippendorff (1989) described content analysis as, ‘... a research technique for making replicable and valid inferences from texts (or other meaningful matter) to the contexts of their use.’ Hseih and Shannon (2005) put forward three approaches to qualitative content analysis, being firstly ‘Conventional’ where coding categories are derived direct from the coding data, secondly, ‘Directed’ where the analysis starts with a theory or relevant research

findings as guidance for the initial codes used, and thirdly, 'Summative' which involves counting and comparisons, usually of keywords or content, followed by the interpretation of the underlying context. The approach in this thesis is that of 'Directed', as the Conceptual Framework labels the qualitative characteristics and provides more detailed definitions that can begin to be worked with to develop the initial codes. Finningham's (2010) framework for conducting content analysis was employed, given the similarity of the investigation undertaken.

'Researchers avoid using preconceived categories, instead allowing the categories and names for categories to flow from the data. Researchers immerse themselves in the data to allow new insights to emerge' (Kondracki and Wellman, 2002, pp. 224-225). The researcher approaches the text making notes of their first impressions and thoughts. Continuing, codes emerge that are reflective of key thoughts. These initial codes are sorted into categories, and thereafter into broad clusters (Patton 2002; Coffey and Atkinson, 1996; Morse and Field, 1995). The advantage of this approach to content analysis is that information can be obtained directly from study participants without imposing preconceived categories. Credibility can then be established through peer debriefing, triangulation and other activities (Krippendorff, 2004; Manning, 1997; Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

Content analysis can easily be confused with other qualitative methods such as grounded theory or phenomenology. However, the goal of content analysis in this thesis is to validate or extend conceptually the theoretical conceptual framework, and content analysis determines the initial coding scheme. A new code would then be given to any text not categorised within the initial coding scheme, as they may represent a new determinant of the QC of useful financial information. Ranking the frequency of the codes can be used (Curtis et. al., 2001). New determinants of QCs, if identified, shall either offer a contradictory view of the stated QCs in the revised CF, or might further refine, extend, or enrich the CF. The data gained for the content analysis was approached with an informed, unbiased view. The researcher had tried, as faithfully as he could, not to let the interview participants get clues from him to answer the questions in a certain way or to agree with him. The predetermined QCs, already defined in the CF, allowed the achievement of such unbiased or neutral results.

This summative approach to content analysis allowed the usage of certain words and content in text to be explored, with the purpose of understanding the contextual use of the words. The researcher tried to explore the word usage or discover the range of meanings of the QC in normal use, and discover patterns or themes derived by analysing the text, and relationships between them. This approach, outlining the coding process, the training required to perform the coding, and how the coding process was implemented, allowed the results of the coding process and study to be increasingly trustworthy and valid.

The validity of content analysis procedures is according to Creswell and Miller (2000, p. 124) 'governed by two perspectives: the lens researchers choose to validate their studies, and the researcher's paradigm assumptions'. The completeness of the qualitative characteristics is determinable from how accurately the QCs represent the study's participants' realities when determining or developing accounting policies as evidenced through their change in accounting policy notes, or on presenting financial information in general gleaned from the interviews undertaken and the replies given. Ultimately, the completeness of inclusion of a qualitative characteristic depends on the collective judgement of the scientific community that a characteristic and its measure are validly included (Bernard, 2012).

The researcher is able to determine how long to 'remain in the field', whether the data gathered enables, through saturation, good code or themes to be developed, evolving into a persuasive narrative (Creswell and Miller, 2000). As a qualitative analysis the data is returned to numerous times to ascertain whether any constructs, categories, and the explanations and interpretations from the data, make sense. All the research participants' were actively involved in assessing the completeness of the QCs as they were asked if the QCs were to them complete or not. Creswell and Miller, 2000, listed nine different types of validity procedures, not all of which have been used here to explore for completeness. Triangulation is used to search for convergence among multiple and different sources of information (interview transcripts, accounting policies, and comment letters) to help form themes or categories. A priori or deduced themes come from prior understanding of the qualitative characteristics, what Aristotle identified as essences. The researcher was aware that it was important to remain sceptical, to retain an etic, an outsider or general objective perspective, and not to 'go

native'. Disconfirming evidence, if any was found, would also be used, to search through the data for evidence that is consistent with or disconfirms the QCs themes. The researcher also acknowledged and described his beliefs and biases early in the process to allow participants to understand his position, and then to bracket or suspend those researcher biases as the study proceeded. Member checking was not carried out, outside of asking the research group in the individual interviews if the QCs made sense, whether they were accurate and realistic. The level of engagement with the data sources, through interviews, analysing accounting policies of the banks', and the comment letters from banks' and banking associations', were considered as saturating the findings available, barring an outlier or two, which would then not have any statistical significance.

As the inquiry audit trail carried out was documented through the keeping of a research log of all activities and data analyses procedures clearly recorded, the findings can be substantially replicated apart from the deviations caused by the effluxion of time, changes in accounting regulations, knowledge of the participants, particularly conscious and unconscious bias that the present participants' have, having gone through the study.

Content analysis has been widely used as a research method in several accounting and finance studies, although most often used in social studies, lending credence for its use in this thesis. Several studies have investigated the content of financial accounting narrative, such as that presented in corporate annual reports'. Dunne (2003) used the technique to examine the impact of a new derivatives accounting standard on UK corporate annual reports', and likewise, Finningham (2010), the impact of the introduction of IFRS on corporate annual reports' and accounts in the UK, while Steenkamp and Northcott (2007) reported on the practical challenges of using content analysis as a research method in examining companies annual reports'. Unstructured documents, such as banks annual reports', can be statistically analysed, numerical data summarised, and inferences drawn from the analysis (Dunne, 2003).

3.4.1 **Validity and reliability**

Of relevance to this thesis's validity (rigour) and reliability is what Lincoln and Guba (1985) argued. They stated that 'establishing the trustworthiness of a research report lies at the heart of issues conventionally discussed as validity and reliability', asking questions of research reports about their truth value (or trustworthiness), applicability, consistency, and neutrality', adding 'authenticity' in 1994. Criticism of these questions are that 'applicability' depends on generalising from a sample to a population, 'consistency' depends on realist assumptions, while 'neutrality' depends on separating one's values from the inquiry. Lincoln and Guba (1985) argue that trustworthiness is always negotiable and open-ended, that there are multiple constructed realities rather than a single tangible reality. Ontological authenticity can be shown, argue Lincoln and Guba (1985), if a range of different realities, fairness, are represented, and viewpoints of people other than their own have been appreciated. Indeed, Lincoln and Guba (1985) state 'the view that fairness, sophistication, mutual understanding, and empowerment are generally desirable is itself a value-laden, culture-bound position that a Foucauldian deconstructionist might very well enjoy taking apart'.

This research looks obiter dicta at 'theoretical' validity, of which Norris (1997) noted there are two aspects; the validity of the concepts and categories applied to the phenomena, and the validity of the postulated relations among the concepts. Both these aspects of validity are to be commented upon indirectly in this research, while exploring the completeness or otherwise of the qualitative characteristics. Validity refers to the truth, the correctness, and the strength of a statement made in this thesis, and the degree that a method investigates what it is intended to investigate. 'Validation is more than corroboration; it is a process for developing sounder interpretations of observations' (Cronbach, 1971). Reliability of findings from a thesis pertains to consistency and trustworthiness, whether the findings are reproducible at other times and by other researchers. It is proposed that as the epistemology in this thesis is qualitative, and the researcher is the research instrument, a singular truth shall emerge, triangulated by the various data sources.

3.5 How the research methodology and methods were used to answer the research questions

The research questions stated in s.1.2 '*Which qualitative characteristics do 'preparers' refer to when explaining their accounting decisions, and when do they refer to these qualitative characteristics?*

And are the qualitative characteristics complete?' were addressed by the methodology through:

- a. a critical examination of the research literature;
- b. using semi-structured interviews with preparers and users, and both a Foucauldian critical discourse analysis and a further content analysis of those interviews;
- c. an analysis of changes in accounting policy disclosures in annual reports of selected banks', both before and after the Conceptual Framework revision date of late March 2018, using content analysis;
- d. an analysis of content of comment letters from banks' and banking associations' sent to the IASB before late March 2018, with a further use of Foucauldian critical discourse analysis.

Given the aims of this research and its underlying philosophical assumptions, using qualitative research methods of both Foucauldian critical discourse analysis and content analysis were considered to be appropriate to align with the research questions, both ontologically and epistemologically. The research methods undertaken in chapter three attempt to determine whether the claims of the IASB about the usefulness of financial information is supported in practice by the QCs deemed fundamental or enhancing by the IASB, and to determine whether there are further valid QCs deemed appropriate by preparers of international, domestic and local banks' annual reports?

Chapter 4 Data Collection

4.1 Introduction

The first strand of the research, semi-structured interviews, investigates the magnitude and the nature of disclosures of qualitative characteristics (QCs) provided by interviewing preparers of banks' annual reports, as well as users of such reports represented by Investment Analyst Societies / Chartered Financial Analyst Societies.

A content analysis of selected banks' annual reports changes in accounting policies both before and after the revision date is the second strand, allowing for identification of the impact, if any, of the revised QCs.

The third strand, that of content analysing comment letters provided to the IASB before revision, for QCs that were proposed but did not find their way into the revised CF, could provide evidence of the governmentality and power of the IASB to subjectify other stakeholders input into the revision process, all Foucauldian concepts.

Figure 4.1 presents an overview of the research strands undertaken, revealing the part that looking at the revised Conceptual Framework through Foucauldian lens plays in this research framework, and poses the questions of whether the Conceptual Framework is decision-useful, complete as far as the qualitative characteristics used and described in context goes, along with whether there are any further constraints that should apply to situating the qualitative characteristics in the framework.

4.2 Data collection from semi-structured interviews held with preparers and users

A short theoretical background to undertaking interviews has been relegated to Appendix D in order that the practical interview steps conducted could be highlighted below.

Figure 4. 1 Overview diagram of research undertaken

4.2.1 Interviews with preparers and users - sample choice and size

The number of semi-structured in-depth interviews with preparers of banks' financial statements was originally envisaged to be around nine. In the event, the sample for the semi-structured in-depth interviews held with preparers', totalled five if the pilot interview was included, although saturation point was probably reached after about four interviews, Table 4.1, and Appendix J, Table J.1. All preparer interviews were with Head's of Financial Reporting of each of their separate bank's, and there was further homogeneity in the population interviewed, as all preparers were professionally qualified accountants.

It was initially intended to interview Head's of Financial Reporting of banks' listed on the London, South African and Australian stock exchanges. This was to be secured via 'snowball sampling' from the UK building society interview, to certain other large international and UK banks' preparers who might have been willing to participate in this study. This was because it is extremely hard for an outsider to identify who belongs to the population within those banks', and such banks' are not forthcoming with providing their time for research. The one UK bank interviewed said afterwards that they would not normally have granted the interview, except that the researcher was well known to them, and favourably so, and so they could expect a high level of trust and confidentiality. Interviewing elites, leaders or experts in the financial reporting community, usually in powerful positions, made obtaining access problematic. However, the interviewer / researcher, demonstrating a sound knowledge of the interview topic and technical language, gained respect and was able to achieve an extent of symmetry in the interview relationship. Elite interviewees tended to have a secure status, so it was feasible to challenge their statements, with the provocations possibly leading to new insights. Interviewing experts, where the interviewer confronted and also contributed with his conceptions of the interview theme, perhaps approximated the intense questioning of a Socratic dialogue, ideally leading to knowledge in the sense of episteme.

Replacement of these international banks' that were originally going to be included in the preparer sample was made by choosing Isle of Man banks'. Such banks' would provide rich research findings in an island context, nissology, which could be extrapolated out to other British Islands. The IOM banks' selected for preparer

interview, comprised all the banks' available that are registered on the IOM, which accounted in terms of IFRS and were not branches of overseas banks. The population was saturated except for a bank grouping holding three brands on the Isle of Man, which declined due to restructuring considerations and secrecy, Appendix J, Table J.1.

Three international representative user groupings were chosen for the study, representing the UK, South Africa, and Australia, to mirror geographically the envisaged preparer participants'. In the event, only two of the three user groupings agreed to participate, the UK Chartered Financial Analysts Society, and the South African Investment Analyst Society, while the Australian Chartered Financial Analysts did not (see Table 4.3 below). Three countries Investment Analyst Societies, or their equivalent, would have helped to explore triangulated evidence for the completeness of the QCs, or it may have indicated a country bias. Investment analyst societies were chosen as the user grouping, following recent pertinent research done by Cascino, Clatworthy, Osma, Gassen, Shahed, and Jeanjean (2016) for the Institute of Chartered Accountants' of Scotland and the European Financial Reporting Action Group. The users were director's of their respective country's Investment Analyst Society or Chartered Financial Analyst representative body (see Tables 4.2 and 4.3 below). There was no IOM equivalent of a representative Investment Analyst Society that could have been included in the user interviews at the time.

It is not considered relevant to further delineate out the demographics of the preparer and user participants', as age and sex are irrelevant as is the years in the organisation they represent, only their seniority and decision-making prowess within their respective organisations.

Reasons for not having interviewed a board member from the IASB include the fact that permission was not asked upfront in Ethics to do so, the Board's views are freely available from webinars and podcasts, and that the thesis maintains that the end product, the CF's QCs, are decided by the Board anyway. Most of the questions asked in Appendix I of participants would not be valid for responding to by a Board member, while the thrust of this research is to find out what preparers and users think of the (mainly) completeness of the QCs, which thoughts may be 'hidden' and not readily

available without this study. Also, selecting a singular IASB board member only introduces the challenge of a non-representative sample, and what can be derived from such sample's results.

Table 4. 1. Preparer participant numbers

	Total	UK	South Africa	Australia	IOM
Initial preparer sample	6	2	2	2	0
Preparers excluded as could not be 'snowball' sampled	(5)	(1)	(2)	(2)	0
Isle of Man registered banks' Head's of Financial Reporting full complement	3	0	0	0	3
Preparer sample interviewed	4	1	0	0	3

Note: This table outlines the sample of banks' included in the analysis of the interviews in chapters five and six.

Table 4. 2 User participant numbers

	Total	UK	South Africa	Australia	IOM
Initial user sample	3	1	1	1	0
Users excluded as could not be sampled	(1)	0	0	(1)	0
IOM User groupings to subvent sample (none of sufficient gravitas outside of Regulator, IOM FSA)	0	0	0	0	0
User sample interviewed	2	1	1	0	0

Note: This table outlines the sample of users included in the analysis of the interviews in chapters five and six.

Table 4. 3 Geographical spread of participants

	Total		UK		South Africa		Australia		Isle of Man	
Interviews	Proposed	Actual	Proposed	Actual	Proposed	Actual	Proposed	Actual	Proposed	Actual
Users	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Preparers (incl. pilot)	6	5	4	1	1	1	1	0	0	3

4.2.2 Informed consent

All preparers' and users' who agreed to the in-depth interviews received a Participant Information Sheet prepared by the researcher (Appendix E). Informed consent was then assumed if the preparers' and or users' agreed to the in-depth interview, and the Consent Form (Appendix F) had been received back by the researcher, explicitly signed by the participant. Informed consent was thus obtained from research participants who were informed of the purpose of the study, the main features of the design, as well as any possible risks and benefits of participation in the research project. Informed consent further involved obtaining the voluntary participation of the participants', informing them of their right to withdraw from the study at any time, information about confidentiality and who shall have access to the interview or other material, the researcher's right to publish the whole interview or parts of it, and the participants' possible access to the transcription and the analysis of the qualitative data. Written agreement was obtained to serve as protection for both the participants' and the researcher (Appendix F). Confidentiality too was agreed with participants',

data not being able to identify the participants' nor their organisations. The ethical principle of beneficence meant that the risk of harm to a participant was to be the least possible. From a utilitarian ethical perspective, the sum of potential benefits to the participants' and the importance of the knowledge gained outweighed the risk of harm to the participant and thus warranted the decision to carry out the study.

Participants' were reminded of their right to withdraw from the study at any time in the Consent Form (Appendix F, point 2, p. 225), and in the Participant Information Sheet (Appendix E, pp. 222-224) as stated. Taking part in the study was entirely voluntary and participants' were free to withdraw from the whole study at any time without giving any reason and without any penalty. If a participant had withdrawn, the participant's interview transcript, audio recording and audio recording transcript would all have been destroyed immediately.

Debriefing took place with individual user's and preparer's following each in-depth interview. The interviewer mentioned the main points learnt from the interview, asking the interviewee, the preparer or user, to comment on this feedback. This offered the opportunity to give further feedback on the process, to deal with issues raised from the interview, and to offer any further commentary that might have been helpful to the study going forward. The researcher did the debriefing immediately after the interview, allowing the participant a further chance to comment. The interviewing continually improved as the researcher learnt more about a topic, resulting in a more sophisticated form of interviewing receptive to the nuances and complexities of the topic being explored. The researcher performed the transcription of the interviews himself. At the end of the research, a written summary of the overall findings was given to each participant, near to the time of submission of this report to the University.

To ensure anonymity was preserved as far as possible, pseudonyms or code numbers were used during the research process, names and locations of the in-depth interviews were stored securely by the researcher; transcripts were anonymised, and all interviews were transcribed by the researcher himself; computer files have been password protected; printed anonymised data, if any, will continue to be kept under lock and key within a fireproof filing cabinet; anonymised data will be disposed of securely after six years (Appendix E, Participant Information Sheet, p. 223).

In-depth interview transcripts, audio recordings, and audio recording transcripts will continue to be kept in a fireproof locked filing cabinet by the researcher who is the only key holder. The cabinet will continue to be kept locked within the researcher's place of employment. All computer documents have been stored, encrypted, on a password protected computer in password protected files. Supervisors of the Professional Doctorate program have access to the anonymised confidential data. None of the data contains personal details, as it has been anonymised using pseudonyms or code numbers. Such supervisors have been entrusted by the University to keep such information accessed confidential and secret unless written appropriate permission is obtained from the participants'. Access and confidentiality were set out expressly in the Consent Form (Appendix F) and Participant Information Sheet (Appendix E). If a participant had wished to withdraw from the study, then the researcher would have been able to identify their anonymised data for destruction from the pseudonym or code number used.

4.2.3 Pilot interview sample

An initial upfront pilot in-depth interview with a local Isle of Man bank, a member of the preparer grouping, incorporating the updated QCs in the 2018 revised Conceptual Framework document, helped inform the direction of the semi-structured interviews held with the users' and the preparers', ensuring the participant's voice was heard, and that the researcher was not leading the interview, but asking open questions. None of the questions that were put to the pilot preparer needed to change at all for the remaining semi-structured interviews as they had been understandable and answerable by the pilot preparer, and the questions that were put to the preparers' and users' remained as per Appendix I, pp. 231-236.

There were a further four questions to those listed in Appendix I that the researcher had considered including to ask interviewees. After the rich interview held with the Pilot preparer it was decided to leave the questions below out of the semi-structured interview questions because they patently could be considered 'leading' questions asked by the researcher, and more moderate, non-leading questions were asked instead:

- 1) Does Prudence introduce intentional bias, and hence Neutrality is unachievable (i.e. understating assets, overstating liabilities)?
- 2) Should Reliability be included as an enhancing QC; should Reliability be treated as a tenant of Faithful Representation?
- 3) Should Verifiability be part of Faithful Representation; should Verifiability be treated as a fundamental QC?
- 4) Do Preparers ignore the QCs when developing accounting policies, because most transactions are covered by existing IFRS standards?

4.2.4 **Ethics**

At all times the Economic and Social Research Council's (ESRC's) six key principles of ethical research were borne in mind by the researcher, particularly as they match principles espoused in the Association of Chartered Certified Accountant's (ACCA's) Code of Ethics and Conduct (Appendix G, pp. 227-228). Care was taken by the researcher to overcome all ethical issues and challenges (Appendix H, pp. 229-230).

4.2.5 **Procedure for semi-structured interview sampling in this study**

Preparers' and users' were interviewed by the researcher using a questionnaire (Appendix I, pp. 231-236), and audio recorded using both an audio recording device attached to the researcher's laptop, and alongside the laptop. Explicit consent was obtained for both the interview and for the audio recording of the interview beforehand (Appendix F). Some interviews were undertaken remotely, that is, the researcher was sitting within his closed office, and the participant was similarly sitting within their closed office, cities apart, else the interviewer and interviewee were in the same room across a boardroom table.

As participants' were professionally qualified accountants in banks', mostly local to the Isle of Man (IOM), (preparers'), and / or investment analysts (users'), there was a possibility, however small, that may have existed that some may have felt a certain level of obligation to participate. This was addressed at the introductory communication for participation in the semi-structured in-depth interviews for the preparers' and users', which included the information sheet (Appendix E), where the

researcher reinforced the choice and responsibility element of taking part in the study. The participation by preparers' and users' did not present a conflict of interests as the preparers' and users' were not worked with on a daily basis and no undue influence had been applied to participate. Collaboration in the research by preparers' and users' as participants remained entirely voluntary, and all participants' were entitled to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason, as stated in the Consent Form and Participant Information Sheet (Appendices F and E). The researcher complied with all appropriate ethical standards with integrity, not allowing participants' to participate under duress. Each in-depth interview with the preparers' and users' lasted approximately half an hour to an hour maximum. The interviews were then fully transcribed and analysed manually.

The interviews took place during 2018, all after the revision of the CF in March 2018, and weighted towards the end of 2018 to give the participants' time to analyse the revised CF and its implications for them and the bodies they represent as the first set of post revised CF compliant annual reports were being prepared. All the interviews were conducted by the researcher himself, restricted to those who agreed to participate in the study.

Preparers' and users' involved in the semi-structured in-depth interviews were asked at least a month before the interview took place. This was to ensure that participants' had obtained all internal consent required, if any, from relevant senior executive committees at their place of employment, which committees normally meet no more frequently than monthly. The doctrine of constructive notice was assumed once the signed Consent Form (Appendix F) was received by the researcher.

4.2.5.1 Using Excel and Word to facilitate coding the transcribed interview text

For the semi-structured interview dataset, each repeated question was auto-coded such that all respondents' answers to each question were accessible independently (Krippendorff, 1989). To do this, interview text was transcribed, sorted and structured using a manual method following the steps suggested by Ose (2016), set out below, using word and excel. The ten steps were:

1. Audio files from the interviews
2. Transcription of the audio files into Word
3. Transference of the text from Word to Excel, separated into logical chapters and subchapters
4. Preparation of the Excel workbook for manual coding
5. Coding of all the content in Excel
6. Preparation of the coded interviews for sorting
7. Sorting the coded data in excel
8. Transference of the interview quotes back from Excel into Word
9. Sorting the interview text into a logical structure based on the coding
10. Analysis of the coded interview data

The coding unit used in the current study was the qualitative characteristic (QC) or its synonyms and phrases, and the number of times it was used. The volume of times the QC was referred to was deemed to signify the relative importance of a particular QC, or phrases or characteristics that should be a QC (Bernard, Wutich and Ryan, 2017, p. 181) and (Krippendorff, 1989). Finningham (2010) contended that the most suitable coding unit was the proportion of a page devoted to a particular issue. It was argued that the amount of space given to the topic indicated the relative importance of the topic to those who produced the document.

Coder reliability, mitigating researcher bias, was ensured by there being only the researcher as the coder, and having a suitable, reliable and accurate decision rules for coding, although Krippendorff, as reported by Steenkamp and Northcott (2007), claims that content analysis would be pointless if analysts were not permitted to read texts differently from other readers, and to make choices.

Inferences would be shaped 'by whether the researcher explores issues related to the sender of the message, the message itself, and / or the audience for the message' (Smith, 2003, cited by Steenkamp and Northcott, 2007, p. 13). The most important concern for the researcher was to ensure the consistency and transparency of the analysis processes used, to enhance the validity and rigour of the study.

NVivo 11, a computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software package or CAQDAS, was initially thought to be usable to compare themes, codes and word frequency across the various data sources, the transcribed interviews', the annual reports' of the banks' participating and the comment letters of banks' and banking associations' which had written in to the IASB. NVivo 11 could have provided 'mapping' tools enabling connections to be interrogated, along with diagrammatic visualisations to facilitate non-linear thinking. However, as the volume of data was low, and variable across the data sources, on piloting NVivo 11 it was decided to revert to word and excel to code the text from the semi-structured interviews', analysing the data manually once sorted into themes, which themes mainly coalesced around the existing QCs.

4.3 Data collection from changes in accounting policy notes from preparers' annual reports

The aim of this strand of the research was to explore the qualitative characteristics used within the sample banks' covering the IOM, UK, SA, and Australia, both before and after the revision of the Conceptual Framework in late March 2018. As with Dunne et al. (2008), this analysis focuses on the non-financial statement section of the annual report, specifically the Basis of Preparation note or / and the Changes in Accounting Policy note, or in the absence of either, the changes brought about by updated IFRS accounting standards'. The remainder of the accounting policy notes were not considered, as any change in them would have been as a result of a measurement change and not a policy change. Unlike Dunne et al. (2008), the primary statements (Income Statement, Balance Sheet, Cash Flow Statement etc.) have not been analysed for the impact of any differences in findings between the qualitative characteristics before and after the revised CF.

The IASB states in its feedback to the Conceptual Framework (IASB, 2018b) that developing an accounting policy by reference to the CF is rare, noting that most transactions and events are already covered by existing IFRS standards and therefore the use of the CF is not necessary when developing accounting policies for such transactions. This research sought to find out if this is true.

As banks' annual reports were content analysed both before the revised CF and afterwards, four UK banks', one South African, one Australian, and six Isle of Man banks', equating to twenty-four annual reports in total, were selected. All the banks' interviewed were included in the sample, to allow for triangulation between results. Those banks' on the Isle of Man that report under International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) were chosen, rejecting those that use FRS 102. This allowed the preparer sample to include 100% of the Isle of Man banks' that met this criterion, of reporting under IFRS (Appendix J, Table J.1, pp. 243-245).

An initial upfront pilot content analysis of an IOM bank's annual report helped inform the direction of the content analyses of all the banks' annual reports selected. The pilot study undertaken illustrated the difficulties of judging how to code written texts into mutually exclusive categories. Steenkamp and Northcott (2007, p. 12) focussed on three practical challenges normally encountered in applying content analysis to annual reports: 'determining the appropriate categories and recording units; counting repetitive messages; and dealing with the subjective interpretation and categorisation of ambiguous messages.' It is the latter, the inference from the text being investigated, that the researcher concentrated on in this study. The pilot study of the annual report also did not show the results expected from using NVivo 11, so the analysis of the changes in accounting policy notes or basis of preparation notes was done manually by the researcher, using a set of decision rules.

Further details of the decision rules for content analysing the changes in accounting policies of the banks, which were developed and pre-tested, are provided in Appendix K, p. 280, while the banks' actually sampled and the results from the content analysis therefrom are also shown in the appendices under Appendix J, Table J.1, pp. 237-239. The coding procedures, following in part Nobes and Stadler (2014), have been set out in Appendix L, pp. 275-278, so that later studies are able to draw informed comparisons. The individual qualitative characteristics were also discussed under this strand of content analysis of changes in accounting policy notes due to the ability to relate notes found such as that for IFRS 9 to each qualitative characteristic. Considering that subjectivity is inherent in the Content Analysis method, it is this richness of subject interpretation that offers the greatest potential for meaningful contribution to our understanding of accounting disclosures. To make the single coder

subjectivity more transparent, included in Appendices K and L are illustrative decision rules and a template for the content analysis, so that guidance is offered to future researchers' and those wishing to compare studies to have room for improvement.

Table 4. 4 Sample details

	Total		UK		South Africa		Australia		Isle of Man	
Bank annual reports	Proposed	Actual								
Accounting policies pre- revision of CF	6	12	4	5	1	1	1	1	0	5
Accounting policies post- revision of CF	6	12	4	5	1	1	1	1	0	5

4.4 Data collection from comment letters' sent to the IASB by banks' and banking associations'

The third strand of the research involved an extraction and analysis of all the comment letters written into the IASB at its Discussion Paper stage, which are all publicly available documents, that were from individual bank's and banking association's. It was considered necessary for assessment of the completeness of the qualitative characteristics to ascertain using content analysis whether there were any qualitative characteristics subjugated by the IASB that had been put forward by the banks' and banking associations' that did not make it to the final Conceptual Framework chapter, and were possibly not fully discussed along the way. No ethical issues arose as the

comment letters were all publicly available documents. Insights from the comment letters are commented upon in chapter 5.4.

The Exposure Draft May 2015 ED/2015/3 p. 10 (IASB, 2015) contains a summary of questions for respondents, the question and its sub-parts to do with the qualitative characteristics being listed immediately below:

‘Question 1—Proposed changes to Chapters 1 and 2

Do you support the proposals:

(a) to give more prominence, within the objective of financial reporting, to the importance of providing information needed to assess management’s stewardship of the entity’s resources;

(b) to reintroduce an explicit reference to the notion of prudence (described as caution when making judgements under conditions of uncertainty) and to state that prudence is important in achieving neutrality;

(c) to state explicitly that a faithful representation represents the substance of an economic phenomenon instead of merely representing its legal form;

(d) to clarify that measurement uncertainty is one factor that can make financial information less relevant, and that there is a trade-off between the level of measurement uncertainty and other factors that make information relevant; and

(e) to continue to identify relevance and faithful representation as the two fundamental qualitative characteristics of useful financial information?

Why or why not?’

Table 4. 5 Comment letters from banks' and banking groups' to the IASB (numerical count of the proposal questions answered)

Bank/ Banking Group/ ED/2015/3 Q1	(a) Stewardship	(b) Prudence	(c) Substance over legal form	(d) Measurement uncertainty	(e) Fundamental QCs	Further QC-related comment
Australia and New Zealand Banking Group, Buggle, S. (2015)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Banco Bradesco (Brazil), Galende, M. A. (2015)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, Ingves, S. (2015)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
BNP Paribas, Machenil, L. (2015)	✓	No comment	No comment	✓	✓	✓
Canadian Bankers Association (CBA), Hannah, D. (2015)	✓	✓	✓	No comment	No comment	None
Chartered Financial Analysts Society of the UK, Miemietz, M., Lee, P. and Goodhart, W. (2015)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Credit Agricole Group, Bouchard, P. (2015)	✓	✓	No comment	No comment	✓	✓
Deutsche Bank, Bomba, L. (2015)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	None
European Association of Co-operatives Banks (EACB), Guider, H. and Heegemann, V. (2015)	✓	✓	✓	No comment	No comment	None
European Banking Authority (EBA), Enria, A. (2015)	✓	✓	No comment	✓	✓	✓
European Banking Federation (EBF), Mijs, W. (2015)	✓	✓	✓	No comment	No comment	✓
French Banking Federation (FBF), Lussigny, B. (2015)	✓	✓	No comment	No comment	No comment	None
German Savings Banks Association, Goebel, R. and Rutenberg, G. (2015)	✓	✓	✓	No comment	✓	None
Japanese Bankers Association (JBA), Hiroyuki, O. (2015)	No comment	None				
The Hong Kong Association of Banks (HKAB), Chan, H. (2015)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	None

Total	15	15	15	15	15	15
No comment	1	2	5	7	5	8
Commented upon	14	13	10	8	10	7
Proposal supported	11	7	8	4	4	
Proposal not supported without qualification	3	6	2	4	6	
Percentage 'overruled' by IASB	21%	46%	20%	50%	60%	

Note: How ubiquitous the concept is can be reflected by how often it appears in the comment letters.

4.5 Summary

The data collected from the semi-structured interviews held with preparers' and users', from changes in accounting policy notes from the banks' annual reports, and from comment letters sent in to the International Accounting Standards Board from banks' and banking associations', all serve to allow a consideration of the understanding that the preparers' and users' may or may not have of the IASB's governmentality and power over them using a Foucauldian critical discourse analysis, and for further content analysis to scrutinise the application and completeness or otherwise of the qualitative characteristics stated in the Conceptual Framework, towards answering the research questions asked in s.1.2.

Chapter 5 Insights from Foucauldian Critical Discourse Analysis

5.1 Introduction

The primary objective of this thesis is an exploration around completeness of the International Accounting Standards Board's (IASB)'s qualitative characteristics. Facilitating this objective is a procedurally documented analysis of the IASB's policy development and consultation process (Appendix B) which includes both mandatory steps such as exposure drafts' and comment letters', and non-mandatory steps such as discussion papers' and public hearings. Behind that, the Foucauldian concepts of power, subjectification and governmentality are worth investigating, in that they have a part to play in the formulation of the Conceptual Framework's qualitative characteristics eventually decided upon by the IASB.

This chapter reports on the results of the Foucauldian critical discourse analysis of the interviews held with both preparers' and users' of banks' annual reports. The discussion of the results is divided into a summary of responses from the participants (s.5.2), specific analyses of responses from the Foucauldian concepts of power (s.5.2.1), governmentality (s.5.2.2), subjectivity and subjugated knowledge (s.5.2.3), and finally the overall implications for the IASB's consultation process (s.5.2.4).

The analysis has been performed looking at the banking industry, and the Isle of Man in particular, such that the findings can be said to be specific to the Isle of Man and to the banking sector, yet its implications can possibly be extrapolated further to other jurisdictions and industry sectors, proof of which can be derived from carrying out recommended further studies which would follow this research.

5.2 Interview discussion of Foucauldian concepts

Six interviews were held with preparers' or users'. The initial sample envisaged of six preparer's, each Head's of Financial Reporting from global banks' covering the UK, South Africa and Australia, to match the envisaged three users, each a director of Investment Analyst Societies or Chartered Financial Analyst societies in the three countries of the UK, South Africa and Australia, was reduced to four and two

respectively, as explained in chapter three on Methods. Those three countries were chosen because it was assumed that preparers' from the banks' and users' all within a similar national accounting environment and legal and cultural system, would report similarly under the IASB's Conceptual Framework. Nevertheless, the UK is formally represented in both categories, and the island of the Isle of Man, a self-governing territory, is depicted instead due to the researcher's direct interest, with ramifications from the research's implications that are still international.

An analysis of the comments provided by the UK and other international and Isle of Man banks' about Foucauldian concepts and their interaction with or knowledge of the IASB, are set out below. All relevant questions asked in the semi-structured interviews were answered by all participants.

5.2.1 **Power**

An observation that was expected to come out of the research relating to power of the IASB, arises directly from the power that the Conceptual Framework provides to the IASB, as the Conceptual Framework strengthens the IASB's position for establishing financial standards' in the private sector which the banks' would then have to follow. This thought was not elucidated by the research participants', more the concept that power which concerned them, came from the national Regulator such as the Financial Reporting Council (FRC) (replaced by a new regulator, the Audit, Reporting and Governance Authority from 1 April 2019) and Prudential Regulatory Authority (PRA), or, where applicable, the IOM's Financial Services Authority (FSA), not the IASB.

*Q11) To what extent do you think the **power** of the IASB contributes to **subordination**, control and regulation of professional accountants?*

Pilot preparer: 'Always felt that the IASB is more to do with the quality of financial reporting than the regulation / control of accountants as such. They do well in terms of defining and moulding the IFRSs and determining what is required in that sense. Whilst they drive the output of accountants work there is still significant judgement on the part of the accountant in preparing the financial statements.'

The pilot preparer's thoughts were mimicked by all the participants', some of whose thoughts are quoted below.

Preparer 12: 'In terms of 'Power', I think from my perspective I see that much more driven by other regulatory bodies. So, in the UK we have the FRC, which would collect samples of annual reports, and they will comment back to individual businesses and publish their findings on annual reports which they feel ... certainly the sort of criteria we are talking about today, so too the PRA. I see more instances of those regulatory bodies openly identifying reports that are maybe not meeting requirements, than say the IASB.'

Preparer 13: 'I am not sure they do. I am not inclined to agree.'

Preparer 14: 'I am not sure that they have (power over us) ... They do tend to listen to argument, um, it is a very collaborative approach to writing these standards, it doesn't tend to be some committee just pushing them out because there tends to be lot of complexity, and it perhaps brings uncertainty because it is very difficult. IFRS 9 is a big change for banks' and um you know, they are still not settled on what year end disclosures are going to look like and we are three weeks away from year end, because the thinking has developed over the course of the year. I'm not sure they have a particular power over us, there are so many inputs into it that if you felt strongly about it you can get representation through your professional body, through your business, uh, even through the accounting firms.'

Other participants' reiterated the thoughts above. In summary, the IASB has perceived power, but as one participant said, 'indirect not direct power', by guiding national accounting standard setters and Regulatory bodies. However, particularly in

the UK bank's case, the FRC⁸ and the PRA, and for the IOM registered banks', the IOM FSA, have greater perceived direct control or power over them. Indeed, bankers are more likely to follow the FRC's Code which proposes characteristics of financial information to be 'Fair, Balanced and Understandable', while professional accountants are expected to follow the IASB's qualitative characteristics when determining their company's accounting policies.

5.2.2 Governmentality

As the IASB is a private-sector standard-setter with no elected or other governmental authority, transparent standard setting with the participation of constituents is a crucial element of its legitimacy. The IASB does incorporate formal public consultations (public hearings, issuing discussion papers and exposure drafts for comment) in its due process (Appendix B, p. 208). The IASB also uses more informal methods such as informal meetings within the IASB amongst its staff, and webinars, live webcasts and online surveys too (Jorissen et al., 2012, and Huian, 2013).

*Q16) From your experience, has **governmentality** of the qualitative characteristics by the IASB restricted the characteristics you have used to explain accounting policy choices made and accounting standards adopted in your annual reports?*

Participant 12's annual report had a change in accounting policy for segmented information in their latest annual report, so it was a pertinent question. However, participant 12 reported that the technical team would have been aware of the Conceptual Framework's qualitative characteristics at the time the change was made, but he was not aware of the QCs per se in deriving the accounting policy note.

The local IOM bank participants' were collectively similar to the following in their reply:

⁸ (replaced by a new regulator, the Audit, Reporting and Governance Authority from 1 April 2019)

Participant 14: 'We would tend to use our internal wordings, we look to similar size banks' within the Group and use those. We would not try to rewrite them. We sometimes have to customise the wording for our circumstances because it covers things we don't have, or it doesn't cover things in sufficient detail, but it is not going to be wholesale change from Group wordings. There is an expectation we use Group accounting policies, and therefore the Group wording is fine.'

Participant 14 was particularly effusive and went on further to state:

'There is a whole raft of technical people in the Group so if you have a technical issue you tend to go and talk to them and they tend to be very good on the technical issues. We did think about the CF when we were talking about this, whether this asset and liability should be recognised, because it was the only way, there wasn't really a Standard that said this is what you should do, and we were pondering whether an asset and liability actually existed, but it depended on the (indistinct) pattern as to whether it existed. We might look at other banks' to see what they are doing. Our primary driver is what our Group issues as instructions about financial statements, and we are waiting for the IFRS stuff so that we follow, and in part that reduces the work locally because PWC would have already considered those disclosures and agreed them, and therefore we haven't got to go back through the loop, and get PWC our auditors to agree them again.'

This comment shows that the IOM banks' in particular are not aware of the governmentality of the IASB. Their group accountants' elsewhere in the world may be, but on the IOM, the heads' of financial reporting are looking to what the group decrees as changes in accounting policies and the wording to come therefrom, and locally to obtain their external auditors sign-off as to the adequacy of such wording in a local generally accepted accounting practice situation (local Companies Acts, Statement of Recommended Practice (SORP), legal precedents, Audit Act 2006, and

the Audit and Accounting Regulations 2018 Act⁹), subject to the local Regulator's specific additional requirements if any. Another participant mentioned the dilemma over cryptocurrency reporting, whether there is an asset that can be fairly valued, and noted that IFRS has not given any specific guidance, so the external auditors would be consulted. This raised a further difficulty for some participants in that as they are regulated banks', they are not supposed to obtain advice from their external auditors who in turn are responsible for the audit of the repercussions of the financial reporting advice given. One participant, a user, suggested that the preparers' should follow the governmentality of the IASB with its IFRSs' and IASs', and in need, provide an annexure for additional information that management feel is relevant to the users' of the financial statements.

5.2.3 Subjectivity and subjugated knowledge

*Q14) In your view, has the IASB encouraged critique (**scepticism**) and critical inquiry (challenge) of the qualitative characteristics sufficiently?*

Pilot preparer: 'Whilst they certainly do always request input from outside users and a committee was pulled together with wide range of experience, I think really the main interested parties / responders are generally from the top 10 accounting / auditing firms who are the ones that are checking ultimate compliance - I should imagine most accountants in their day to day lives weren't too concerned to feel the need to critique or critically inquire the subject and would expect guidance / support from their own auditors when preparing their financial statements (outside of main market listed / very large private companies).'

Preparer 15: 'No, not really, maybe, as users of IFRS you are supposed to get a bit more involved, but yeah, you just have to accept it as written.'

⁹ The researcher helped to update the Audit and Accounting Regulations 2018 Act.

Whilst the preparers' felt that they were having to just accept the qualitative characteristics, user participants', who are very influential being director's of user groupings, were more sanguine and felt they did have a say. User 22 felt that *'as there is an exposure draft which is publicly available before the Standard is adopted, gives anyone the opportunity to interrogate what is coming up or what they are planning to implement.'* Another user verbalised his feelings that *'the qualitative characteristics seem to be an adjunct to the CF, ranking secondary to the quantitative requirements'*.

Q15) In your view, could the epistemic knowledge of certain other plausible qualitative characteristics, put forward by the FASB or international accounting bodies before the IASB's pre-dominance, have been subjugated by the IASB ontologically?

Participant 12 summed up the majority of the interview responses by stating that they were inclined not to agree, as they believed the process to be transparent enough.

The topic of 'subjectivity and subjugated knowledge' is referenced again within this thesis by looking at the comment letters and the qualitative characteristics that were raised by those comment letters that never made it through to the final revision of the CF (Chapter 5).

5.2.4 Implications for consultation process

Q12) Do you think the compilation of the IASB's Conceptual Framework Project Committee has had any effect on the qualitative characteristics and their meanings decided upon?

The interviewees appeared to portray the opinion that the Conceptual Framework project had had some useful outcomes, with more clarity being given on certain terms, and also the reintroduction of some items ('prudence') that were removed from the 2010 framework. However, all participants were actually oblivious as to the compilation of the project team at the IASB for the Conceptual Framework project. They had no idea that a significant share of the members were in fact from the banking industry. Many said it showed a 'lack of interest' on their part, and that they had no

idea who comprised the project team, and how the project team was selected. Participant 14 went on to state that it is interesting, once I had mentioned the banking industry significant representation, as banks' he said 'were more balance sheet focused, while other firms were more income statement focused', which raises a certain dynamic if the Conceptual Framework was to have been more balance sheet driven. The lack of knowledge of the participants' around the IASB's project committee meant that most participants could only provide a 'no comment' answer.

Q13) What is your view on the IASB's problematisation process ('Requests for Information', Discussion Papers, Exposure Drafts, and ultimately Post Implementation Review) for revising the qualitative characteristics?

Participant 15: 'when you get it through the Institute (for example the Institute of Chartered Accountants of England and Wales) or the Big Four, it does work. For individuals, if you are not really following closely with your Institute not really, but for me, my Institute would usually ask for contributions from members. So, if you have anything to say you can do it through them.'

Other participants, particularly the users, believed that they could 'churn out the process quicker, ... and early adopt standards'.

The lack of widespread participation in the IFRS setting process can be criticised, particularly in the light of the financial crisis of 2008. Comment letters are assigned a pivotal role in the deliberations process, and it is just such input as comment letters that affords input legitimacy, where constituents that are affected by the Standard, have been seen to have contributed towards the standard-setting process (Dobler and Knospe, 2016). The lack of consultation by the banks' preparers' of financial reports as evidenced from this study, and indeed the lack of consultation by such preparers with their accounting bodies who could consult and have actually consulted on their behalf, confirms previous literature around low participation rates. This study contributes to the literature around low response rates. The research also shows that there is not widespread participation across interest groups, what with all offshore

banks' who participated in the study not realising that they too could communicate directly with the IASB, relying solely on their respective representative accounting bodies to do so on their behalf. This has implications when the geographical reach of IFRS is discussed, as extrapolating out this research's findings means that it is probable that many British accountants have had no direct say in the standard setting process of the IASB, as British Islands' most probably have not usurped their accounting bodies representativeness to have a say in the due process, even though the accountants in banks' within British Islands may be severely affected, particularly as far as new financial instrument standards are involved such as IFRS 9.

For legitimacy, all stakeholders affected by IFRS financial reporting should participate in the IASB's process of standard setting. Due to missing participation by offshore banks', the quality of the input to the IASB may suffer, and thus the derived standards might not be adequate or may even be biased. The incentives for offshore banks' to participate in the revision process is low. The importance of this research is illustrated by reaching out to this group, offshore banks', through semi-structured interviews, investigating how preparers' of banks' accounts feel about the IASB's due process.

5.3 Summary

The methodological tactic of using Foucauldian CDA in this research has included the analysis of texts such as the IASB's own pronouncements on the QCs, for example, Appendix M, pp. 279-286, Chapter Two of the Conceptual Framework for financial reporting, and the critical evidence from the discourses of the interviews held with participants in this chapter, after having sufficiently theorised power and the IASB as the institution under scrutiny. This aspect of the research has been less oriented towards lexicosyntactic features of the texts, and more focused on cultural and social resources and constructs affecting the IASB and its interactions with the accountancy profession. The methodological tactic deployed in this research has been to move back and forth from an analysis of the participants' interviews to the theorised power, political relations, and historical change of the IASB under scrutiny as evidenced by other academic writers and the researcher's own normative reading of the texts emanating from and about the IASB. This Foucauldian technique is an interactional and almost ethnomethodological analysis that grafts Foucauldian concepts of power into analyses made, remaining post-structuralist and post-Marxist. The role of this

analysis using a Foucauldian lens is to possibly aid in a transformation of the IASB by unveiling and mobilising opinion about their actions. Regardless of which philosophic linguistic and political analysis is made, there is a need to return to the issue of power when intellectually studying the IASB.

As anticipated, the apparent incongruity of bringing a Foucauldian lens to bear on the field of accounting has been justified by outlining from the insights in the chapter above exactly how Foucault's work shed's new light on the topic. On the one hand is the great challenge it mounts in terms of power, governmentality, subjectivity and subjugated knowledge; on the other hand, is the analytical reward such as that signposted above which can be reaped by applying his tools and concepts to issues within accounting discourses (adapted from Gillies, 2013).

Chapter 6 Insights from Content Analysis

6.1 Introduction

Chapter five outlined a Foucauldian Critical Discourse Analysis and the derivation of the Qualitative Characteristics of Decision-Useful Financial Information by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB). This chapter complements the previous chapter's analysis by exploring, using content analysis, the findings from data collected from interviews, and changes in accounting policy notes, while analysing comment letters.

6.2 A Content analysis of the interviews

From Table 6.1 it can be seen that the preparers did not all have the opportunity to answer all the questions as in the process of debate some of the latter questions on improvements proffered and early adoption of the Conceptual Framework were inadvertently not asked, while the users comprehensively responded to all questions.

Table 6. 1 Summary of responses from interviewees

	12	13	14	15	21	22
Question number	Preparers				Users	
1. Preparers key QCs?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2. Users key QCs?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
3. Preparers and Users QCs combined?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
4. Further QCs?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
5. Difference in QCs between voluntary and mandatory financial information?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
6. Use of Decision – Useful?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
7. Faithful representation represents substance?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
8. Prudence supporting Neutrality?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
9. Improvements to QCs?	✓	x	✓	✓	✓	✓

10. Comparability and early adoption of the CF?	✓	✓	×	×	✓	✓

× = Inadvertently not asked

6.2.1 Planning for the implementation: Preparers (head's of financial reporting, banks')

Many international banks' had started their preparation for the revised Conceptual Framework (CF) two years before the revision date, as many commented on the Exposure Draft issued in 2015 (IASB, 2015). The preparers from international banks' tended to develop strategy papers outlining details of what needed to be done and suggestions as to how this should happen, whether implementation would be before the mandatory 1 January 2020 date or before. This was directly confirmed from the interview with Nationwide Building Society, and from the South African and Australian international bank's annual reports.

The interview question relating to implementation of the revised Conceptual Framework:

Q10) Has your bank decided to be an early-adopter of the revised Conceptual Framework, or are you going to wait until 1 January 2020? And if an early adopter, what plans have you made already or do you envisage making?

Interestingly, the banks' preparers on the Isle of Man did not know at the time of interview whether they would be early-adopting, and hence had not begun planning for it. It could be that they were not willing to divulge the information, because it would be a surprise if contingency plans were not being put in place, particularly around the slight change in the definition of a liability in the CF, and its effect on implementing IFRS 9 on financial instruments whose mandatory effective application date was for annual periods beginning on or after 1 January 2018.

6.2.2 Planning for the implementation: Users (investment analysts)

There was a variation in the level of awareness about the revised CF issues among the users interviewed. It appeared very much to be each user for themselves. For example, many of the analysts were left to update themselves on the revised CF if they wanted to learn about it. The users' were particularly interested in how the banks' financial information was going to be presented in financial statements after mandatory implementation of the Conceptual Framework on 1 January 2020. One user stated:

Participant 21: We have had problems with adoption and early adoption before, it depends on what area they are early adopting, I would say I would not want banks' to early adopt, I would want banks' to adopt at the correct point in time, and for a lead-in period to be understood, to be acknowledged, however long that is deemed to be. In terms of early adoption, I would find that frustrating having to compare those who have early adopted to those that haven't.'

The QC of comparability was being called into question with early-adopting. No guidance to counteract this effect had been issued by the IASB. Another user stated that they wanted the IFRS 9 statement on Financial Instruments to be embedded before the CF differences were accounted for, so for there to be no early adoption of the Conceptual Framework.

6.2.3 Key QCs from the preparers' and the users' perspectives

Users have different interests in disclosures compared to preparers. Hence it was anticipated that the QCs used in the changes in accounting policies content analysis, as well as those QCs emphasised by preparers in the interviews, would be different to those preferred by users.

Q1) and Q2) What do you as a Preparer / User (as applicable) perceive to be the key qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information from your experience?

One preparer participant decided that their stance on the QCs was not to regurgitate the CF's QCs, but to state that the UK Corporate Governance Code (Code)¹⁰ (FRC, 2016) principles were more important to have in mind when preparing the annual report. There were similarities with the CF's 'relevance' and 'faithful representation', and the enhancing 'understandability', however the Code's principles of 'fair, balanced', and 'understandable'¹¹ prioritised characteristics differently to the CF, elevating 'understandable' from an enhancing level characteristic to that of fundamental.

All participants commented on the fact that key QCs depended on who the audience was. Preparer participant 13 went further and stated that 'the most useful audience is the Regulator, but they are not necessarily presented with information in the financial statements which I think is much use to them particularly'. Participant 13, an Isle of Man bank annual report preparer, explained that there are two audiences who were genuinely interested, being their overseas group holding company, and the Regulator, and that the Regulator was looking for completely different information than that presented in the annual report. This participant thought that there was an argument for reporting in different formats for different audiences, depending on the organisation

¹⁰ The UK Corporate Governance Code (from here on referred to as 'the Code') is a part of UK company law with a set of principles of good corporate governance aimed at companies listed on the London Stock Exchange. It is overseen by the Financial Reporting Council and its importance derives from the Financial Conduct Authority's Listing Rules. The Listing Rules themselves are given statutory authority under the Financial Services and Markets Act 2000 and require that public listed companies disclose how they have complied with the code, and explain where they have not applied the code – in what the code refers to as 'comply or explain'. Private companies are also encouraged to conform; however there is no requirement for disclosure of compliance in private company accounts. The Code adopts a principles-based approach in the sense that it provides general guidelines of best practice. This contrasts with a rules-based approach which rigidly defines exact provisions that must be adhered to.

¹¹ The UK Corporate Governance Code (2018) s.25 *'The main roles and responsibilities of the audit committee should include: ...providing advice (where requested by the board) on whether the annual report and accounts, taken as a whole, is fair, balanced and understandable, and provides the information necessary for shareholders to assess the company's position and performance, business model and strategy.'*

(in this case banks') and the size of the entity. Interestingly, participant 13 went on to explain that he thought the enhancing characteristic of 'comparability' was most important, comparability between periods, whereas he felt that currently disclosures are being dictated by the particular accounting standards as well as its Group accounting policies.

Participant 14 concurred, going further to criticise overdisclosure, stating that *'the standards require you to have a whole load of disclosure that doesn't really add anything to the information. It is so hard to understand that unless you know about the detail of our business, it does not mean anything, it just becomes pages of stuff that you have to put in'*. The participant explained that he had this viewpoint because there was a lack of complexity about the banking business that they were involved with, not doing anything sophisticated. They did not have the tools to do any bespoke IFRS 9 modelling, leaving that to the UK to do. Participant 14's key QCs were Relevance, and not the other fundamental QC 'faithful representation', but the enhancing 'timeliness'.

Participant 14 was vociferous about forward-looking elements to the financial statements, saying that to him forward-looking elements are subjective and always a guess.

Other preparer participants too supported the characteristic of 'comparability', particularly amongst banks', along with 'consistency' and 'timeliness'. So, it is clear from the researcher's exegesis that the offshore island banks' are more concerned with 'comparability' and 'timeliness', both only enhancing QCs, rather than with the CF's 'faithful representation'.

Table 6.2 below, provides summary results of the qualitative characteristics that were to be expected, as they accord with the Conceptual Framework's QCs in the main. Participants were aware of the two fundamental characteristics being relevance and faithful representation, and the enhancing characteristics of understandability, timeliness, and comparability were well recognised. Interestingly, verifiability was not as well recognised as a qualitative characteristic, with only one participant referring to it in the interview.

There was an emphasis on timeliness by both the preparers' and users' as a qualitative characteristic that they each felt needed to be responded about, while it was raised by a preparer that information for the Regulator should be accommodated as a qualitative characteristic. The researcher has translated this to mean that the preparer believed the information for the Regulator to be a constraint rather than a qualitative characteristic (see Figure 6.1).

Table 6.2 Summary of key QC responses from interviewees – preparers and users

Key Qualitative Characteristic (preparers and users)	12	13	14	15	21	22
Relevance (Fundamental QC)			✓	✓		✓
Faithful Representation (Fundamental QC)	✓				✓	✓
Understandability (Enhancing QC)	✓	✓			✓	
Accessibility (not a QC at present)		✓				
Comparability (Enhancing QC)		✓		✓		✓
Usefulness (Constraint)		✓				
Presentability (not a QC at present)		✓				
Timeliness (as in Currentness)			✓	✓		✓
Non-overdisclosure (not a QC at present)			✓			
Consistency (Enhancing QC, part of comparability)				✓		
Verifiability (Enhancing QC)					✓	
Fair and Balanced	✓					
Information for the Regulator (constraint)		✓				

Table 6.3 Summary of qualitative characteristics that the one participant grouping thought was important to the other

Key Qualitative Characteristic (as perceived by the other participant grouping i.e. users of preparers, and preparers of users)	12	13	14	15	21	22
Relevance (Fundamental QC)	✓				✓	
Faithful Representation (Fundamental QC)					✓	✓
Availability (as opposed to Accessibility) (neither are QCs at present)			✓			
Comparability (Enhancing QC)		✓				✓
Timeliness				✓	✓	✓
Consistency (Enhancing QC)		✓				
Verifiability (not a QC at present)						✓
Neutrality (non-bias) (under Faithful Representation)				✓		
Quantitative numbers as opposed to QCs					✓	
Materiality						✓

6.2.4 Duality of qualitative characteristics for both preparers and users

Q3) Do you think qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information for both preparers and users can be combined in the Conceptual Framework under the same sub-headings of 'Fundamental' and 'Enhancing'?

The findings were split evenly in the interviews between combining the QCs for preparers' and users' as 'their (preparers and users) composition is no different' (Participant 21), and implying that the QCs did not matter to users' as 'the users were possibly not going to ever look at the CF document'. In summary, the interpretation placed by the interviewees was that no change need be made to differentiate between the users' and the preparers' needs, as it shall be the preparers' who shall be using the CF, and the QCs remain the same. However, on analysis (see Table 6.3), there

is a difference, and the IASB should be prepared to explore the theory of possibly incorporating further QCs to accommodate both users' and preparers'.

6.2.5 **Supernumerary qualitative characteristics**

Q4) What further qualitative characteristics might you suggest should be included in the Conceptual Framework to improve the narrative of decision-useful financial information?

Participants 12, 13, 14 all believed the QCs to be fundamentally complete, and were encouraged to see that prudence had been reinstated on revision, and that 'substance over form' was discussed under 'faithful representation' (not noting that the discussion centred on the need to make disclosures in terms of the substance of the transaction instead of its legal form).

Participants 15 and 22 raised the issue that 'materiality' should have been dealt with in the chapter, but wasn't specifically, with participant 22 believing 'materiality' to be a key qualitative characteristic. This is possibly because of the separate materiality project begun by the time of the revision of the CF, also 'materiality' had previously been a constraint and has been dropped as a constraint on revision. The suggestion emanating from this research is to reinstate 'materiality' as a constraint (see Figure 6.1).

Participant 21, a user of banks' accounts, was indignant about the QC 'consistency', as 'different banks' refer to the same feature but under different terms'. 'Comparability' between periods was also highlighted by the participant for emphasis, however it was not clear if the suggestion was to make 'comparability' a fundamental QC from its present ranking of enhancing, or if the participant wanted more emphasis from the banking annual reports oversight bodies such as the Financial Reporting Council (FRC) (replaced by a new regulator, The Audit, Reporting and Governance Authority from 1 April 2019) and even the banks' auditors, ensuring comparability between periods and between banks' in the terminology they use.

6.2.6 Perceived differences between the voluntary and mandatory sections of annual reports

Q5) Do you think that there is in reality differences in the key qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information used between the 'voluntary narrative sections' and the 'mandatory statutory financial information sections' of banks' annual reports?

Participants views differed, because logically the differences in QCs should be apparent as different users are more interested in the mandatory sections of the annual reports than the voluntary sections and vice versa. One participant added the logical finding that 'users would also be more concerned with transparency, a sort of conservatism, which is what you generally see within the accounting standards and the application of them. I am inclined to think that you are encouraged to err on the side of caution, whereas I think if you were an investor you would not necessarily want to see that. You would want to see the true position, true results.' 'Transparency' has been put forward as being a possible 'constraint', rather than a further qualitative characteristic as argued later (see Figure 8.1). Further along the continuum of conservatism, the voluntary section, perhaps as it is at the time of this study, disclosing the possible anticipated effects of Brexit on the bank's financial strength, prospects, and governance say, are less cautious and hence the narratives are not entirely adhering to the QCs maxims of neutrality as it tries to add value to the user.

Another participant suggested that *'the numerical side is probably easier because it is more factual...whereas the broader points about governance and controls is quite subjective'*.

A single participant suggested that there was to them a correlation between the size of the voluntary sections of banks' annual reports and their financial strength, interesting using HSBC, a bank which survived the financial crash of 2008, with a few hundred pages of reporting, contrasted against HBOS with far less, which did not survive the financial crash intact.

The overall impression from the participants' was that each component of the annual reports, both the voluntary mainly narrative disclosures and the mandatory narrative and numerical disclosures, should 'be in sync, a mosaic', and interpreted this means that the QCs are expected by both the majority of users and preparers to apply across the voluntary and the mandatory sections of the banks' annual reports, with perhaps 'transparency' being a further determinant required by the user participants across the voluntary sections.

6.2.7 Usefulness of 'decision-useful'

Q6) What are your views on the IASB no longer using the adjective 'decision-useful' to describe qualitative characteristics of financial information? Should it have been reinstated in the Conceptual Framework, given that the information is for both corporate governance (management's stewardship of the entity's resources) and financial sustainability purposes?

The majority of the participants' in this study were of the opinion that the adjective 'decision-useful' instead of just 'useful' was not required, and hence supported the IASB's viewpoint not to reinstate the adjective to describe the financial information referred to in the revised CF from that of its 2010 version where 'decision-useful' was an integral part of the import of what the IASB were trying to get across.

The participants' felt that the QCs 'decision-usefulness' is relative, based upon the use for decisions that the users would have, many feeling that the historical annual reports of the banks' were not useful for decision-making vis-à-vis forward-looking statements, and hence the word is not critical, and in any case, they believed the word to be implied by the IASB. This acceptance of the dropping of 'decision-useful' reinstating 'useful' formed part of the academic debate that has taken place over many years, and reported upon in the Literature Review's s.2.7. With the seminal papers from Nobes and Stadler (2014), and Cascino et al. (2017) and (2016) referring explicitly to 'decision-useful' financial information, perhaps it is time to reinstate the adjective in the title to chapter two of the Conceptual Framework, see Figure 8.1. and Appendix M, p. 279.

6.2.8 **Substance over form**

Q7) What is your view on the IASB stating explicitly in the revised Conceptual Framework that 'Faithful Representation' must also represent the substance of an economic phenomenon, and that if the substance of an economic phenomenon and its legal form are not the same, providing information only about the legal form would not faithfully represent the economic phenomenon?

All participants were in favour of reinstating the old concept of 'substance over legal form', although many raised the perplexing concept of how to account for the new cryptocurrencies. The researcher believes the solution is simpler than what participants' thought, as accounting for cryptocurrencies depends on whether they are being held as a short-term or a long-term investment, in what currency, and whether increases or impairments are accounted for using the historical cost or fair value model, and if fair value, whether changes in value are recognised in the P&L or the OCI. The QCs would be able to direct the accounting policy wording and disclosures used.

Other participants still continued the argument that regardless of what the IASB and hence external auditors of their bank's are requiring, the substance of the transaction to drive the transaction's disclosure, the legal form of a transaction can be one thing such as an interest-paying loan to a subsidiary, while in substance, if it is likely to be non-repayable, then it is in effect a contribution towards equity in the subsidiary in substance.

Participant 21 did take a dissenting view on the use of the word 'economic', preferring instead the word 'financial' to explain the phenomenon represented.

6.2.9 **Prudence under neutrality**

Q8) What is your view on the IASB reintroducing an explicit reference to the notion of 'prudence' (described as caution when making judgements

under conditions of uncertainty) as supporting Neutrality, instead of in its own right?

Pilot preparer: 'I think it is a good thing because maybe you should err on the side of caution, because you could get carried away with your estimates and be overly positive. But on the other side of that it is a way for people to manipulate results by say being prudent in a good year and at a later time in a bad year not be as prudent. So I guess it does impact on Neutrality as it is another avenue for people who want to manipulate results by saying that they were being Prudent. People choose when they want to be Prudent or not.'

By the IASB including 'prudence' under 'neutrality', discussion followed about 'asymmetric prudence', and the application of 'prudence' intentionally conservatively in good results years, and more biased prudence in poor results years, in order to achieve 'smoothing'. The Pilot preparer thus has a problem with including 'prudence' under 'neutrality' as 'neutrality' may not in effect be achievable if a key determinant in 'prudence', which in practice may be deliberately or intentionally made asymmetrical over reporting periods, a concept the IASB may not have discussed as they were concentrating more on a single reporting period as well as comparisons between entities.

Participant 13: 'I think Prudence and Neutrality are not easy bedfellows. Prudence needs to be there in its own right, it needs to be prescriptive rather than subjective to the extent that you can seriously manipulate the results.'

Participant 14: 'It would be very hard to isolate it because it links into all these other things. It links into Materiality, it links into Faithful Representation, so if you tried to isolate it, it almost becomes detached from everything else that is going on.'

Participant 15 felt that an improvement to the QCs could be made by reinstating 'prudence' in its own right, and not having the definition of 'prudence' as 'the exercise of caution when making judgements'.

Participant 22 described the feelings of all participants in that 'bringing 'prudence' back in makes perfect sense'.

6.2.10 Further alternatives or improvements to QCs

Q9) What alternatives/ improvements might you suggest to the qualitative characteristics?

Participant 12 alluded to the viewpoint that 'relevance' was fundamental to them and in participant 12's opinion, 'faithful representation was less so.' This tied in with the same participant's further expression of the chapter on QCs having been technically well written, rather than being more insightful which would have further supported their 'relevance' priority.

Participant 13 had no improvements to suggest for the QCs, however believed that *'new standards such as IFRS 9 on financial instruments bring in a whole raft of additional disclosure, and the danger is that you keep adding more and more which then starts to detract from the overall because you just end up with pages and pages of stuff which is very difficult to get to the bottom of.'* This is a project which is being dealt with by the IASB called 'Principles of Disclosure', which has benefited from a crossover period of twelve months with the Conceptual Framework project with its summary being published late March 2019, although it probably has had no effect on the QCs chapter in the revised CF as characteristics are applicable regardless of the length of a bank's annual report.

'Transparency' was raised obiter dicta in the semi-structured interviews, however not as a determining characteristic of decision-useful financial information, rather as participant 14 said 'transparency is a sum of the other parts. 'Transparency' is a fairly poor stand-alone characteristic, because of how much information is (on applying transparency) needed to be shown'. As mentioned above, 'transparency' was raised

as a determinant of decision-useful financial information for users' who would be wanting to see conservatism in the disclosures, while 'transparency' was not found in the offshore banks' minimalist disclosures that were designed to meet the accounting standard disclosures and the banks' group accounting policies and to go no further, in part because it was the Regulator who used their accounts the most, and for whom the accounts were being prepared (in addition to shareholders). The Pilot preparer felt that 'transparency' could be included under 'faithful representation', as *'you can have 'completeness', 'neutrality', and 'free from error', and not be 'transparent', as information can be all over the place and not be very clear, even though it is all there.'*

'Transparency' is more than 'neutrality', and hence a case can be made for 'transparency' to be included as a constraint (see Figure 6.1). All participants were not supportive of 'transparency' being incorporated as a stand-alone QC.

6.2.11 Summary

6.3 A Content analysis of accounting policy changes, and discussion of individual qualitative characteristics

Data has been collected on the magnitude and nature of qualitative characteristics within accounting policy disclosures of the banks' both pre and post the revised Conceptual Framework of late March 2018. This required the researcher to obtain publicly available annual reports for the banks' accounting years of 2017/2018 and 2018/2019, hereafter referred to as 2017 (pre) and 2018 (post). The qualitative characteristics found to have been used directly or indirectly, allowed comparability between the banks' reporting under IFRS, and also to ascertain whether IFRS had resulted in international harmonisation of accounting policies wordings, or whether national Standard setters' standards had prevailed, or Regulatory disclosures had been followed instead of IFRS.

IFRS's IAS 8 (2018) on Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors allows the company to assess whether to apply an accounting policy change, based on its own assessment of the expected benefits to users', and the cost to the company. The IFRS Interpretations Committee may also conclude that the existing

standards provide enough information for a company to determine its accounting policy.

Any immediate opportunity to achieve the benefits of greater transparency, comparability and uniformity are surely thwarted by the number of accounting policy options contained in the standards.

IAS 8 (2018) s.13 also states, relating to consistency of accounting policies:

‘An entity shall select and apply its accounting policies consistently for similar transactions, other events and conditions, unless an IFRS specifically requires or permits categorisation of items for which different policies may be appropriate. If an IFRS requires or permits such categorisation an appropriate accounting policy shall be selected and applied consistently in each category.’

The UK banks’, Spanish banking group, and the South African banking group were found to have been early adopters of changes in accounting policy brought about by the fundamental changes in Standard, for example from IAS 39 to IFRS 9 on Financial Instruments. The IOM banks’ and surprisingly the Australian banking group were found to be followers and not early adopters. This is interesting as all the banks’ in the sample were audited by one of the big four auditing firms,¹² at least as Lead Auditor, specifically licenced and authorised for auditing such regulated entities as banks’. No differences in qualitative characteristics were found to be in evidence as a result of having a ‘different’ auditor to another bank within the pools of banks’ sampled such as within the IOM banks’, or within the UK banks’. None of the banks’ were loss-making, as that would affect level of disclosures (Saha, Morris and Kang, 2018).

¹² Deloitte, PriceWaterhouseCoopers, KPMG or Ernst & Young.

As stated above, content analysis was employed in order to find the reasons given for accounting policy changes. This section reports on the results of the content analysis of QC disclosures contained in the banks' annual reports that participated in this study both before and after the publication of the revised CF, as well as those on the Isle of Man who had declined to take part in the interviews (all the banks' annual reports are in the public domain), to see if any changes in accounting policies have been brought about by the Conceptual Framework arising which could have arisen due to changes in the definition of assets, liabilities and equity, changes in recognition criteria, changes in measurement bases, and presentation and disclosure classifications, and if so, which qualitative characteristics have been used.

Comparison between banks' against the accounting policy choices from the standards was anticipated to be capable of being made, however, the 'standard' wording provided in the relevant accounting Standard tended to be used, and differences between banks' adoption of the Standard's requirements for measurement and presentation found on transition. In general, these transition provisions required the bank entity to make an assessment or determination at the date of initial application of the change in accounting policy, and either:

- a. apply that determination retrospectively notwithstanding that a different assessment or determination might have been made in prior periods based on the facts and circumstances prevailing at that date, or
- b. recognise any change in net assets in opening retained earnings at the initial date of application, if used.

The Feedback statement on issuing the revised Conceptual Framework in IASB 2018b p.4, extended the purpose of the CF to be:

- a. *'To assist the Board to develop standards that are based on consistent concepts;*
- b. *To assist preparers to develop consistent accounting policies when no Standard specifically applies to a transaction or other event or when a Standard allows a choice of accounting policy; and*
- c. *to assist all parties to understand and interpret standards.'*

IAS 8.14 allows a change in accounting policy *'if the change is required by an IFRS, or results in the financial statements providing reliable and more relevant information about the effects of transactions, other events or conditions on the entity's financial position, financial performance or cash flows.'*

The discussion of the results is divided into three sections: Location of QC's disclosure; disclosure by accounting policy or Standard; and disclosure by characteristic.

Nobes and Stadler (2014, p. 2) was 'the first study to use publicly available data to provide direct evidence about the role of the qualitative characteristics (QCs) of financial information in managements' accounting decisions.' They based their study on '40,895 hand-collected IFRS policy choices on 16 topics made by 514 large firms of ten jurisdictions in the period 2005-2011'. They reported upon the frequencies of reasons given for IFRS policy changes, identifying four broad categories of reasons being the qualitative characteristics in the Conceptual Framework, 'other' qualitative characteristics they identified and proposed such as transparency, economic reasons such as mergers, and lastly changes in standards or requirements of a local Regulator.

6.3.1 **Location of disclosure**

The annual report's changes in accounting policy note, if stated, was used as the principal focus of the content analysis, primarily because accounting regulations and IFRS provide that any changes are stated therein. If the change in accounting policy note was absent, then the basis of preparation note was investigated to find any changes in accounting policies that could have been mistakenly included. In addition, the 'amendments to IFRS' note was analysed to find substantial changes such as from IAS 39 to IFRS 9 for Financial Instruments.

Unlike Dunne et al. (2008), the proportion of page devoted to the change in accounting policy was not deemed to be relevant, and hence not calculated. The proportion of a page associated with a change in accounting policy does not correlate to its importance and the number of qualitative characteristics used, rather it aligns to the intricacy and explanation detail for the user to understand what the bank has recorded in order to meet the Standard's requirements, no more so than with the explanations provided for the change to IFRS 9 which were very detailed, once implemented.

Table 6.4 Location of QCs in IOM banks' pre-revision of the CF

Location of Disclosure	Pre CF revision (Ref: DP & ED)	Basis of Preparation note	Amendments to IFRS note	Change in accounting policy note	Other
Fundamental					
Relevance (inferred)	2	-	1	1	
Faithful Representation (inferred)	2	-	1	1	
Complete (inferred)	2	-	1	1	
Neutral	0	-	-	-	
Prudence	0	-	-	-	
Free from Error	0	-	-	-	
Enhancing					
Comparability	3	1	1	1	
Consistency	5	1	2	2	
Verifiability	0	-			
Timeliness	3	1	1	1	
Understandability	3		2	1	
Constraint					
Cost	0	-			
Materiality	3		2	1	
Additional QC?					
Transparency	1	-	1		

Table 6. 5 Location of QCs in IOM banks' post-revision of the CF

Accounting Policy/ Standard	Post CF revision	Basis of Preparation	Amendments to IFRS note	Change in accounting policy note	Other – Adoption of IFRS 9 note
Fundamental					
Relevance (inferred)	3	1	2	-	-
Faithful Representation (inferred)	3	1	2	-	-
Complete (inferred)	2	-	1	-	1
Neutral	0	-	-	-	-
Prudence	0	-	-	-	-
Free from Error	0	-	-	-	-
Enhancing					
Comparability	2	-	1	1	-
Consistency	4	-	2	1	1
Verifiability	0	-	-	-	-
Timeliness	2	-	1	1	-
Understandability	2	-	1	-	1
Constraint					
Cost	0	-	-	-	-
Materiality	4	1	2	1	-
Additional QC?					
Transparency	0	-	-	-	-

6.3.2 Disclosure by accounting policy or Standard

Both IFRS 9 on Financial Instruments and IFRS 15 on Revenue became effective to be applied in the UK from 1 January 2018. Hence, the annual reports' post late March 2018 all addressed the issue of the two 'new' IFRS standards in their change in accounting policy notes, provided of course that they were applicable, which in the case of most banks' they would be. Having both these 'new' IFRSs effective dates when they were, resulted in a discernable increase in the change in accounting policy notes published with the banks' sampled annual reports, with IFRS 9 accounting for the majority of the page space for changes in accounting policies.

The local Isle of Man banks' and the UK banks' sampled all reported on the change arising from IFRS 9, while it is noted that the pilot bank did not. The reason why the pilot bank did not is unclear. It could possibly be because of a 'time-lag' concerning implementing IFRS 9, or it may have no financial instruments that apply which is very unlikely, or most probably the pilot bank had a lack of understanding about IFRS 9 and was hoping to follow at a later date others' disclosures and disclosure adjustments who had already implemented IFRS 9.

It was evident from the change in accounting policy notes of the banks' in the sample that the wording and adjustments tended not to be similar, i.e. they were not 'boiler-plated' disclosures, more bespoke. What was similar was the nature of the adjustments made, the note of the effect on the bank's financial position if any, and the decrease in income (due to the material loan impairment provisions), along with the similarity of whether or not the comparative figures had been restated, and in any event, disclosure of the effect on the comparative figures as they were or would be if indeed adjusted.

Confirming previous findings of bank-specific information (Finningham, 2010, p. 219) disclosed, reconciliations between the forerunner to IFRS 9, being IAS 39, and IFRS 9 figures, were evident in most cases. This would possibly enable users to determine how the changes introduced by the new Standard, IFRS 9, would specifically impact that bank's business and its future prospects.

While noting that in this study's sample different versions of IFRS were adopted ('IFRS', or 'IFRS as adopted by the EU'), the actual variance in standards across jurisdictions were found to be low. This finding is in marked contrast to when IFRS was initially introduced at the turn of the century, and Ball (2006, p. 15) commented that 'jurisdictional differences in standards have persisted' suggesting that national political and economic forces were strong. This pervasiveness of IFRS and dominance of IFRS over national standards is underpinned and predicted by the Foucauldian analysis of the IASB, its power, governmentality, and indeed subjectification of national accounting setters along with their professional accountant members. No longer do banks' accounting policies differ substantially across countries, and it is only the local Regulatory forces, along of course with the estimation and judgements that come with applying whatever Standard, that differentiates accounting policies. Nobes (2013, p. 99) found evidence that indicated that 'the choices made vary along national lines, testament to the thesis that economic and political forces remain local'.

From Figure 6.1 below, it can be seen that the QCs have increased substantially from pre to post the revised CF, which could be the result of increased awareness of the terms, or it could have resulted from the increased size of the annual reports themselves from one year to the next.

The annual reports analysed for qualitative characteristics were those of the Isle of Man banks' sampled, as well as Nationwide Building Society. Where the Isle of Man bank had a holding bank, the holding bank's group accounts were selected instead. This resulted in a selection of a Spanish bank's group accounts, and that of a South African bank, as well as further UK banks' group accounts.

Included in the analysis are direct terms not listed in the Conceptual Framework as qualitative characteristics, such as 'matching', 'regulatory' and 'transparency', in order to ascertain the extent of their and their synonyms' direct usage and possible inclusion in further qualitative characteristics or constraints.

Figure 6.1 QCs disclosure by the CF before and after revision

6.3.2.1 IFRS 9

On 1 January 2018, a new accounting standard for how banks' report on financial instruments, IFRS 9, came into force. IFRS 9 is no panacea to the financial crisis. It may lead to volatility, inconsistency, lack of comparability, and the exacerbation of financial instability. Impairment losses for example are the largest factor affecting bank profits, so changing how they are calculated shall have a real effect. An estimation of future losses is just that, an estimate, and a highly subjective one at that. Furthermore, comparisons between banks' have become more difficult, since their views on the future could be radically different. The practicalities of considering several possible scenarios, calculating the probability of each occurring, and modelling the impact is extremely challenging. The sheer size of banks' loan portfolios, variety

of credit products sold, and diversity of customers, geographies, and sectors, all have had to be factored in when assessing the expected losses for the entire business (Mongelard, 2017).

6.3.2.2 Cryptocurrencies

It became apparent that Cryptocurrencies, surely held by the international banks', not yet referred to by IFRS and nor by national standard setters, had not been disclosed, and hence were not comparable between banks' and accounting periods. This could be because the banks' had an immaterial amount of Cryptocurrency and hence had no obligation to disclose separately the asset, or they did not know how to disclose the Cryptocurrency, at the lower of cost or net realisable value, or fair value. If it was the latter, then the banks' should have applied the Conceptual Framework's qualitative characteristics and definitions to craft an accounting policy for cryptocurrencies held in the absence of guidance from the IASB, yet the banks' had not done so.

6.3.3 Disclosure by characteristic

Table 6. 6 QCs and constraints used within change in accounting policies of sample IOM banks'

QC/ Constraint	Pre CF revision (Ref: DP ¹³ & ED ¹⁴)	Post CF revision	Confirmed	Not confirmed
Fundamental				
Relevance (inferred)	2	3	✓	
Faithful Representation (inferred)	2	3	✓	
Complete (inferred)	2	2	✓	
Neutral	0	0		✓
Prudence	0	0		✓
Free from Error	0	0		✓

¹³ DP = Discussion Paper (Reference: IASB, 2013a)

¹⁴ ED = Exposure Draft (Reference: IASB, 2015)

Enhancing				
Comparability	3	4	✓	
Consistency	5	3	✓	
Verifiability	0	0		✓
Timeliness	2	3	✓	
Understandability	2	3		✓
Constraint				
Cost	0	0	✓	
Materiality	3	4	✓	
Additional QC?				
Transparency	1	0	✓	

The low numbers in Table 6.6 are indicative of the low number of changes in accounting policy notes in the IOM banks' sampled. It is also interesting to see that 'relevance' and 'faithful representation' tended to be disclosed together, not mutually exclusive.

6.3.4 Decision-usefulness

The Conceptual Frameworks of the UK ASB, the US FASB and the IASB are based on decision-usefulness, whereas those of other countries often adopt a stewardship perspective (ICAS, 2007).

Financial statements have become 'boiler-plate' reports with companies disclosing essentially the same sorts of information that technically comply with Regulators' requirements. Thus, it is possible that financial statements are no longer serving the stated purpose of decision-usefulness.

Decision-usefulness provides a logical approach for the current study since it allows the researcher to evaluate the accounting policies produced under IFRS against an objective that the standard setting body has itself proposed.

The notion that accounting systems should produce useful information for rational decision-makers is well-established within accounting research (Chamber, 1955). Sterling (1972, p. 198) also concentrated on the usefulness of information provided by financial statements. Sterling stressed the importance of usefulness over other criteria such as verifiability and objectivity, arguing that 'annual reports should supply

information for rational decision-making...allowing decision-makers to achieve their goals’.

Analysing the QCs in relation to the change in accounting policy notes of the banks’ sampled may help provide an answer to the question of whether or not the QCs, embedded within the change in accounting policy notes, are useful for user decision-making purposes.

6.3.4.1 Relevance

A survey of preparers and users of IFRS information of 225 respondents showed that 80% believed a problem exists with disclosure overload, and hence the IFRS disclosure requirements do not produce relevant information (IASB, 2013b).

The CF states that if financial information is to be useful, it must be relevant. In order for there to be ‘relevance’ found in the narrative and figures provided in the change in accounting policy notes, particularly involving IFRS 9 for example, a form of reconciliation would be expected to be seen, for each adopting bank, between previously accounting for financial instruments under IAS 39, and now under IFRS 9. To be decision-useful, and ‘relevant’, any significant changes to the balance sheet and or income statement of the adopting banks’ as a result of the changeover from IAS 39 to IFRS 9, must have had implications for the perceived riskiness of those banks’, and therefore impacted on users’ investment decisions.

Using Table 5.6 above, the increase of ‘relevance’ illustrates that the banks’ in the sample have attempted to provide ‘relevant’ information to users’ about the changes from IAS 39 to IFRS 9.

The CF p. 14 states that ‘financial information has predictive value if it can be used as an input to processes employed by users to predict future outcomes’, and that ‘the predictive value and confirmatory value of financial information are interrelated’. The full financial impact of implementing IFRS 9 may not arise solely in the first year of adoption, raising the question of how much predictive value is available to users for

their investment decisions. For example, an annual impairment review is required to be undertaken over financial assets, such as loans made, under IFRS 9. The change in accounting policy note for the Standard may therefore not be reflective of the full impact of the new IFRS standard, as the full impact may not yet be known. Also, the technical nature and apparent lack of business context to the explanations of the changes introduced by the Standard, may limit the predictive ability of the disclosure. Hence it may be difficult for users' to determine the long-term impact of the IFRS on a bank's prospects and future financial results based on the first year's data only.

6.3.4.1.1 **Materiality**

As a result of the disclosure overload problem mentioned under 'relevance' above, the IASB started a number of projects, amongst which is an active project on materiality (IASB, 2017) called 'Definition of Material', and another on 'Principles of Disclosure', now closed.

Entities are not required to disclose immaterial information in their financial statements. Just because a Standard contains a list of disclosures does not mean that an entity must always make each of those disclosures in its financial statements. Judgement is required to determine whether the relevant line item is material and also whether the specified disclosure is material.

IASB, 2018a, p. 15 states that 'materiality is an entity-specific aspect of relevance based on the nature or magnitude, or both'. 'Relevance' is affected by materiality, and materiality satisfies the 'relevance' criteria, as adoption of the new IFRSs' have introduced changes to the formats and presentation of the financial statements of the adopting banks', impacting their financial position and financial results. If a change in profit of say 10% or a balance sheet change of say 3% occurred on changing the accounting policy, then that would be material for the reasonable man, and by definition must have had implications for the decision-usefulness of the information supplied to investors'. However, the perceived financial effects of the new standards' probably had no influence on the decisions of the users' due to their immateriality.

Therefore, although relevant and material within the time period of analysis, the financial years ending pre and post late March 2018, the changes reported should be treated with a degree of caution as they may be misleading given the transitory nature of the adjustment, where the full impact may only reveal itself in years following the changeover. This was evidenced by the financial crisis of 2008 and the fair value controversy that arose subsequently (Whittington, 2016). The high compliance rate of the sample banks' reporting under IFRS 9 by 1 January 2018, the effective date, contrasts with the financial crisis period where many bank's used exemptions from reporting under IFRS either through a lack of preparedness or a hesitance on the part of the banks' to adopt IFRS and disclose what may be sensitive information before their peers that their competitors could use, putting them at a competitive disadvantage, or simply waiting on their competitors to disclose information before deciding on their own publication format as cited by Finningham, 2010, p. 225 of Dunne et al., 2008, an Institute of Chartered Accountants of Scotland funded project.

6.3.4.2 Faithful representation

The CF (IASB, 2018a, p. 15) states 'financial information must not only represent relevant phenomena, but it must also faithfully represent the substance of the phenomena that it purports to represent'.

There may be doubts about the 'faithful representation' of the disclosures in the changes in accounting policies of the sample banks', not least because of the considerable variation in the statements of financial position and statements of comprehensive income or even the income statements of the impact of the transition reported by the banks' sampled. Some of the banks' showed for example a significantly smaller percentage movement in profits as a result of adopting IFRS 9 than did some of the larger banks' in the sample. Also, the impact of IFRS 9 may be sizable for the vast majority of the banks' sampled in the period reported upon post the revised CF, the longer-term effects may be negligible beyond the time period of the current analysis.

6.3.4.2.1 *Substance over form*

The CF (IASB, 2018a, p. 15), states that *'in many circumstances, the substance of an economic phenomenon and its legal form are the same. If they are not the same, providing information only about the legal form would not faithfully represent the economic phenomenon'*.

Many of the banks sampled provided a Reconciliation Statement to illustrate the effects of reporting under IFRS 9, instead of under IAS 39 which was no longer current from 1 January 2018. Such Reconciliation Statements reconciled the profit and equity on first adopting IFRS 9. It sought to illustrate the effects on changeover on the financial statements of the implementing banks, although the impact shown is only on implementation and for the first year thereafter. An example would be where the effective interest rate for a debt instrument is only consistent for the current year calculation of the present value of the debt instrument, and can change in forthcoming years. Many aspects of the new standards may only become apparent in forthcoming years, following adoption, thus the Reconciliation Statement, a 'legal requirement' of the Standard, may only disclose the substance of the implementation results over a longer period. The preparer would not know at the time of preparing the Reconciliation Statement what the eventual outcome of the substance of the changes would be, so would be in breach of the CF 'substance and legal form' requirement, p.15, *'providing information only about the legal form would not faithfully represent the economic phenomenon'*.

The Board goes on in its CF to postulate that to maximise 'faithful representation', disclosures would have to be 'complete', 'neutral' and 'free from error'.

6.3.4.2.2 Complete

It is possible that doubts may be raised in the minds of users as to the completeness of the IFRS 9 disclosures on changeover, due to the perceived difficulty of analysing the described reporting changes mainly due to the succinctness of the disclosures, which may not have fully described the 'process used to determine the numerical depiction', and 'factors and circumstances that might affect their quality and nature'. This was mainly the case in the local bank pool sampled, while the international, UK

registered banks' in the sample, as a pool, were more effusive in their descriptions of the nature of the information and numerical depictions provided.

6.3.4.2.3 Neutral

The IASB 2018a, p. 16, postulates that:

'A neutral depiction is without bias in the selection or presentation of financial information...relevant financial information is, by definition, capable of making a difference in users' decisions.'

'Neutrality' was not considered as a question to ask in the interviews for content analysing, as much of the sample banks' changeover disclosures were anticipated to be of a technical nature, without any statement of favourable or unfavourable opinions added.

In the event, no attempt was made to influence users' perceptions about whether to invest or withdraw their investments with the bank by any of the banks' changes in accounting policies, from content analysis by the researcher.

Reconciliation Statements were presented in a variety of formats by the banks' sampled who provided one, as the IASB did not provide an illustration of what the Reconciliation Statement would or should look like, which introduced an opportunity for information to be uniquely disclosed by the banks' preparers.

6.3.4.2.3.1 Prudence

The Board re-introduced 'prudence' to the CF, as part of 'neutrality', by stating that:

'Neutrality is supported by the exercise of prudence. Prudence is the exercise of caution when making judgements under conditions of uncertainty. The exercise of prudence means that assets and income are

not overstated, and liabilities and expenses are not understated.' (IASB, 2018a, p. 16).

The absence of forward-looking information in the changes in accounting policy notes evidences the 'prudence' deployed by the banks' as they are not aware, or at the very least not stated, how the adoption of the new IFRSs' shall affect their results.

What is interesting is the CF's recognition on p. 16 that:

'Standards may contain asymmetric requirements if this is a consequence of decisions intended to select the most relevant information that faithfully represents what it purports to represent.'

All of the sample banks' reporting under IFRS 9 for example showed a decrease in profit, mainly due to the impairment provision required against the loans made by the bank and the requirements of calculating such impairment in terms of the standard. This could be interpreted as being more prudent on adoption of IFRS 9, which is at odds with the asymmetrical requirement of 'prudence'. The impact of the new standards over a period of time may be more conservative, nevertheless, at the present point in time, IFRS 9's effects can be deemed to be more prudent than accounting for the same assets and liabilities under the previous IAS 39. The comparison would have been even more stark had IAS 39 not emphasised fair value accounting after the financial crisis of 2008. Current indications from the sample banks' analysed are that under IAS 39 for example, the banks' assets and liabilities were both slightly overstated.

6.3.4.2.4 Free from error

Supporting 'faithful representation' is another qualitative characteristic, 'free from error'. The Board states that this does not mean 'accurate in all respects' (IASB, 2018a, p. 16). The Board further states that 'free from error' means:

'there are no errors or omissions in the description of the phenomenon, and the process used to produce the reported information has been selected and applied with no errors in the process... measurement uncertainty arises. The use of reasonable estimates is an essential part of the preparation of financial information...'

From Table 6.6 above, it can be seen that there was considerable variation in the impact of transition from IAS 39 to IFRS 9 amongst the banks' sampled. This raises the question of whether the adjustments required have been fully implemented in the first year, and implemented consistently across the banks'. Of course, outliers arise due to the nature and extent of the financial instruments actually held by each bank.

6.3.4.3 Enhancing qualitative characteristics

The rationale for the enhancing qualitative characteristics are, as stated by the Board:

'The enhancing qualitative characteristics may also help determine which of the two ways should be used to depict a phenomenon if both are considered to provide equally relevant information and an equally faithful representation of the phenomenon.' (IASB, 2018a, p. 17).

The enhancing qualitative characteristics are as below, 'comparability' (supported by 'consistency'), 'verifiability', 'timeliness' and 'understandability'.

6.3.4.3.1 Comparability and Consistency

The Board states about 'comparability' that:

'information about a reporting entity is more useful if it can be compared with similar information about other entities and with similar information about the same entity for another period or another date.' (IASB, 2018a, p. 17).

'Consistency', although not the same as 'comparability', is related. The Board states that:

'Consistency refers to the use of the same methods for the same items, either from period to period within a reporting entity or in a single period across entities.' (IASB, 2018a, p. 18).

This study explores the annual reports' changes in accounting policy notes in the year prior to and following the implementation of the revised Conceptual Framework late March 2018, coincidentally similar timing to the effective implementation date of IFRS 9 on Financial Instruments from 1 January 2018. Thus, it is not possible to adequately compare the sample banks' accounting policy changes over time as they are discrete to the year disclosed.

However, comparing the reconciliation statement of the changes from IAS 39 to IFRS 9 across the various banks' should be possible, except that it was found that such statements were presented in a range of formats by the sample banks', constraining the 'comparability'. Also, the extent of the effects on the sample banks' income statements and balance sheets also varied widely, with some reporting large adjustments, while others reported minor changes, with the remainder reporting no adjustments to their financial statements.

6.3.4.3.2 Verifiability

Even the Board itself admits that 'it may not be possible to verify some explanations and forward-looking financial information until a future period, if at all' (CF, p. 18). In order for the information to be decision-useful, it is 'necessary to disclose underlying assumptions, methods of compiling the information, and other factors and circumstances that support the information'.

From the banks' sampled that provided IFRS 9 notes, it cannot easily be adjudicated that such information is verifiable, not least because the methods of compiling the

information are not disclosed. 'Verifiability' therefore is more of a wish than a possibility.

6.3.4.3.3 Timeliness

Previously a constraint, then brought back as an enhancing qualitative characteristic on issuance of the exposure draft (IASB, 2015), 'timeliness' can be illustrated to a point by the fact that the banks' sampled have adopted IFRS 9 for example from its effective date 1 January 2018. However, financial information is often most useful when trends are identified and assessed, and having one year's discrete information is not sufficient, hence 'timeliness' in this example cannot be said to influence decisions of users'.

6.3.4.3.4 Understandability

Pre the 'divorce' of the IASB from FASB in 2010, 'understandability' had a place amongst the fundamental QCs alongside 'relevance', 'reliability' (now 'faithful representation'), and 'comparability'.

As stated in chapter two of the Conceptual Framework (Appendix M, p. 280), '*Financial reports are prepared for users who have a reasonable knowledge of business and economic activities and who review and analyse the information diligently.*' '*Classifying, characterising and presenting information clearly and concisely makes it understandable.*' (IASB, 2018a, p. 19).

The content analysis of changes in accounting policies revealed a significant increase in information disclosed in the annual reports of the sample banks', particularly the UK banking group as opposed to the local Isle of Man bank grouping. Also, using NVivo 11, it has been shown that the qualitative characteristics used post late March 2018 in the banks' annual reports increased significantly from that of pre late March 2018 (Figure 6.1).

The ‘understandability’ of the banks’ annual reports have improved hugely since Finningham, 2010, p. 216, reported on adoption of IFRS that *‘companies often presented the financial impact of, for example, IAS 32/39... as a single line item within the Reconciliation Statement thus making it difficult to determine either the individual impact of each Standard or the aspects of each Standard that the adjustment related to.’*

From the banks’ sampled, the allocation of adjustments derived from implementing different IFRSs’ were clear. ‘Understandability’ however was affected due to the overly technical nature of the adjustments, affecting the decision-usefulness of the disclosures for users’.

6.3.5 **Summary**

This sub-chapter has explored the qualitative characteristics used by ten banking groups across the UK and Isle of Man, South Africa and Australia, before and after the revision of the Conceptual Framework in March 2018. The results indicate that the revision of the CF was associated with a nominal increase in accounting policy disclosures in each of the jurisdictions. The nature of variation by accounting policy is also minimal. It is recognised that the majority of the larger banks’ were all early adopters of the revised Conceptual Framework’s qualitative characteristics, prior to the Framework’s mandatory implementation from 1 January 2020.

6.4 **An analysis of content of the comment letters**

In order to ensure no bank’s comment about the Exposure Draft ED/2015/3 (IASB, 2015) and its questions to do with the Conceptual Framework’s QCs were overlooked by the IASB for whatever reason, a fully comprehensive listing of the comment letters received by the IASB was obtained, and all banks’ or banking groups’ comment letters sent in analysed (see summary Table 4.5 above).

Analysing all the comment letters from banks’, exposed this research study’s findings to different cultural influences that may be found. It is interesting to note that the South African influence, corresponding to the South African influence from the interviews in

s.5.2 with the user grouping South African Investment Analysts Society, is mirrored by the Basel Committee’s Accounting Experts Group responses which was chaired by Rene van Wyk, Register of Banks, South African Reserve Bank. Also, the interview under s.5.2 held with the Director of the United Kingdom’s CFA Society, is partially mirrored by the written comment letter from the CFA Society of the UK, included below, as analysed.

6.4.1 Stewardship

Question 1(a) to give more prominence, within the objective of financial reporting, to the importance of providing information needed to assess management’s stewardship of the entity’s resources? (Exposure Draft ED/2015/3 p. 10, IASB, 2015).

Table 6. 7 Stewardship

Bank/ Group/ ED/2015/3 Q1	Banking	(a) Stewardship
Australia and New Zealand Group	Banking	Agreed.
Banco (Brazil)	Bradesco	Agreed.
Basel Committee on Banking Supervision		Agreed.
BNP Paribas		Agreed.
Canadian Bankers Association (CBA)		Qualified agreement. The definition of stewardship is unclear and the expected (useful information to be included) impact is also uncertain, particularly as it may be dependent on the entity’s industry, geography, product / service mix, or the economic cycle, affecting comparability. Concerned that the introduction of stewardship may lead to further disclosure requirements.
Chartered Financial Analysts Society of the UK		Agreed, adding that there needs to be some further recognition that the word ‘stewardship’ does not translate easily into other languages.

Credit Agricole Group	Agreed, adding that stewardship is of interest not only to external users, but to internal users also.
Deutsche Bank	Qualified agreement, adding that the wider meaning of stewardship needs to be clarified, and noting that <i>‘the perspective of a prudential regulator is likely to be different to that of an investor, who may be primarily concerned with an entity’s prospects for future cash flows’</i> .
European Association of Co-operatives Banks (EACB)	Do not agree, citing the difficulty to provide relevant information to support all users’ stewardship’s interests.
European Banking Authority (EBA)	Agreed.
European Banking Federation (EBF)	Agreed.
French Banking Federation (FBF)	Agreed. However, they went on to state that ‘Investors and management need to share the same indicators of financial information when assessing the performance of the entity.’ This would be taking the concept of transparency too far, sharing possibly strategic information which competitors could use to their benefit.
German Savings Banks Association	Agreed. However, they requested that the IASB discuss in detail in the revised CF how the goals of ‘stewardship’ and decision-usefulness could ultimately diverge, as ‘they may compete with each other’.
The Hong Kong Association of Banks (HKAB)	Agreed.

Most respondents agreed with the re-emphasis on stewardship, although there were many qualified agreements, wishing the IASB’s CF to acknowledge that information that is relevant to support the assessment of stewardship may include additional, or different, information to that needed to support decisions such as to buy, hold and sell banking investments.

What is not clear from the comment letters is the banks' and banking associations' views on 'decision-usefulness', as their views were not elicited. Indeed, the question on 'stewardship' is asked in such a way that the IASB could thereafter quote responses in order to support the view expressed anonymously which has subsequently come to light of their Chairman, David Tweedie, to give 'stewardship' a more prominent role, and 'drop' the term 'decision' in front of the conceptual term 'useful'. The German Savings Bank Association's comment letter has been completely ignored on this point, further evidence of the IASB's power, governmentality and subjectification of its members and users.

6.4.2 Prudence

Question 1(b) to reintroduce an explicit reference to the notion of prudence (described as caution when making judgements under conditions of uncertainty) and to state that prudence is important in achieving neutrality? (Exposure Draft ED/2015/3 p. 10, IASB, 2015).

Table 6. 8 Prudence

Bank/ Group/ ED/2015/3 Q1	(b) Prudence
Australia and New Zealand Banking Group	Do not agree. Existing concept of 'neutrality' is sufficient and appropriate. The difference from 'prudence's' common usage and historical interpretation will create rather than alleviate uncertainty in applying the concept of 'neutrality'. Researcher: This was ignored by IASB, and 'prudence' brought in as supporting 'neutrality'.
Banco Bradesco (Brazil)	Qualified agreement. 'Prudence' is inconsistent with the word 'neutrality'. Researcher: This was ignored by IASB, and 'prudence' brought in as supporting 'neutrality'.
Basel Committee on Banking Supervision	Agreed.

BNP Paribas	Qualified agreement. While agreeing that the exercise of prudence should not lead to a deliberately biased measurement, the CF should enable asymmetric prudence to be used by standard setters when building a Standard.
Canadian Bankers Association (CBA)	Agreed. Further noted that the application of 'prudence' does not equate to over-conservatism.
Chartered Financial Analysts Society of the UK	Qualified agreement. <i>'We are supporters of neutrality, meaning free from bias, in the application of accounting policies. Since some interpret "prudence" as having a conservative bias, we have some reservations about its reintroduction. However, in the spirit of compromise with constituents who feel strongly about this, we support the reintroduction of prudence in the way the ED defines it, namely, the exercise of caution when making judgements under conditions of uncertainty. But it must remain clear that applying prudence in financial reporting does not mean applying any type of bias.'</i>
Credit Agricole Group	Disagreed. Credit Agricole believe 'asymmetric' prudence should be introduced to the CF, such that when charges are probable for example, they are recognised, rather than the more regulatory 'cautious' prudence approach to recognition. Credit Agricole point out that 'asymmetric' prudence is already applied, such as in IAS 37, <i>'where contingent assets are recognised when they become virtually certain, and where provisions are recognised as soon as the outflows are probable.'</i> <i>'The prudential concept goes beyond the financial concept of prudence since it encompasses capital adequacy and Sustainability under stress test scenarios'</i>
Deutsche Bank	Disagreed. 'Prudence' should be assigned to specific standards where relevant, for example IAS 37 (Provisions, Contingent Liabilities and Contingent Assets). Researcher: Interestingly, Deutsche Bank remarked that <i>'whatever the Board decides, prudence should clearly be defined as...'</i> . It is this subjugation of thought and conclusion to the IASB that is relevant, believing that after this consultation, the IASB has and perhaps should have the final say without there being a consultative committee made up of representative responders and the IASB members chosen to deliberate and control this project.
European Association of Co-operatives Banks (EACB)	Agreed.

European Banking Authority (EBA)	Agreed, also stating and explaining that not all asymmetry is inconsistent with 'neutrality', which needs to be recognised in the text.
European Banking Federation (EBF)	Agreed, also stating, in contrast to the EBA above, that they would strongly object to asymmetry being included as a descriptive of 'prudence' in the QCs, as it would introduce bias into standard setting, while agreeing that asymmetry would be appropriate in particular situations, best determined at the standards level.
French Banking Federation (FBF)	Qualified agreement. <i>'A standard setter should not be prohibited in some circumstances to introduce asymmetric prudence in a Standard in order to provide useful financial information.'</i>
German Savings Banks Association	Agreed, also stating that 'the notion of asymmetric 'prudence'...must be rejected. This would be in contradiction with the principle of 'neutrality'.'
The Hong Kong Association of Banks (HKAB)	Agreed.

The number of qualified agreements and indeed number disagreeing raises the spectre of what mandate the IASB had to pass their CF chapter two by including 'prudence' under 'neutrality' and ruling out asymmetrical 'prudence'. Many of the comment letters stated that in their view 'prudence' was not an element of 'neutrality', and that the CF should acknowledge the possibility of asymmetric outcomes.

6.4.3 Substance over legal form

Question 1(c) to state explicitly that a faithful representation represents the substance of an economic phenomenon instead of merely representing its legal form? (Exposure Draft ED/2015/3 p. 10, IASB, 2015).

Table 6. 9 Substance over legal form

Bank/ Group/ ED/2015/3 Q1	(c) Substance over legal form
Australia and New Zealand Banking Group	Agreed. However, recommendation made that paragraph 2.14 is redrafted to avoid characterising substance and legal form as mutually exclusive concepts. Researcher: This was done by the IASB on revision.
Banco Bradesco (Brazil)	Agreed.
Basel Committee on Banking Supervision	Agreed.
Canadian Bankers Association (CBA)	Agreed.
Chartered Financial Analysts Society of the UK	Agreed.
Deutsche Bank	Agreed, wishing clarification through examples given be made as to when legal form is important.
European Association of Co-operatives Banks (EACB)	Do not agree. Although not answering question 1(c) specifically asked, the EACB were vociferous in their condemnation of the widening of the definition of a present obligation in the rest of the CF, which, if thereafter the substance of a transaction is followed over its legal form, they believe could trigger important capital base effects (and hence restrictive lending).
European Banking Federation (EBF)	Agreed, suggesting that <i>'further consideration needs to be given as to how 'substance over form' interacts with accounting based on financial instrument contracts'</i> .

German Savings Banks Association	Do not agree as the wording can be misinterpreted to mean that the legal form may be omitted, <i>‘strongly believing that the economic substance cannot be considered independently of the legal aspects of an item in the financial statement.’</i>
The Hong Kong Association of Banks (HKAB)	Agreed.

The bank respondents’ generally agreed to the reintroduction of ‘substance over legal form’ as a necessary component of faithful representation. The revision is still clumsy in that there is the possibility of misinterpretation that legal arrangements should be disregarded, and the economic substance of transactions be considered independently. Also, as legal frameworks vary from jurisdiction to jurisdiction, different outcomes for different countries, even for entities in the same economic sector, for the same type of transaction may occur.

6.4.4 Measurement uncertainty

Question 1(d) to clarify that measurement uncertainty is one factor that can make financial information less relevant, and that there is a trade-off between the level of measurement uncertainty and other factors that make information relevant? (Exposure Draft ED/2015/3 p. 10, IASB, 2015).

Table 6. 10 Measurement uncertainty

Bank/ Group/ ED/2015/3 Q1	(d) Measurement uncertainty
Australia and New Zealand Banking Group	<p>Qualified agreement. <i>Measurement uncertainty can make financial information less relevant, however this will not necessarily always be the case. Furthermore, measurement uncertainty is equally important to the characteristic of faithful representation, as a high level of uncertainty can (but will not always) make information less faithfully representative.</i></p> <p>This was not accepted by the IASB, as the only references to Predictive Value and Confirmatory Value applying is contained in the revised CF at s.2.7-s.2.10, all under 'relevance', and not at all mentioned or alluded to under 'faithful representation'.</p>
Banco Bradesco (Brazil)	Agreed.
Basel Committee on Banking Supervision	Agreed.
BNP Paribas	Agreed, indirectly. Comment was made that <i>'in exercising prudence under circumstances of measurement uncertainty, a balance should be reached with neutrality and reliability.'</i>
Chartered Financial Analysts Society of the UK	Agreed, adding <i>'If assets/liabilities do not meet the recognition criteria due to their uncertainty, but are important to users of accounts, they should be disclosed in the notes, perhaps with a range of potential values and probabilities. Disclosure of a range of values is more useful to investors than false precision or omission.'</i>
Deutsche Bank	Disagreed, stating that <i>'ascribing values to products, particularly in illiquid markets, is challenging'</i> .

European Banking Authority (EBA)	<p>Agreed.</p> <p>However, the EBA also requested the IASB to <i>‘investigate further whether measurement uncertainty may also have a role to play in faithful representation’</i>, which the IASB has not commented on upon revision, further evidence of governmentality and subjectivity.</p>
The Hong Kong Association of Banks (HKAB)	<p>Disagreed. ‘Measurement uncertainty’ is a factor in both ‘relevance’ and ‘faithful representation’. <i>‘If measurement of an asset or liability is very uncertain, then this could have an impact on the assessment as to whether the financial statements are free from error, and whether the item in question is verifiable.’</i></p>

On balance, the consideration of ‘measurement uncertainty’ as part of ‘relevance’ in the revised CF s.2.7-s.2.10 cannot be supported. The CF should have acknowledged the trade-off between ‘relevance’ and ‘faithful representation’, with ‘measurement uncertainty’ potentially affecting ‘faithful representation’, as ‘measurement uncertainty’ may result in information not being ‘faithfully representative’. It can be argued that ‘measurement uncertainty’ should have been discussed only under ‘faithful representation’, and not ‘relevance’. An alternative view is that ‘measurement uncertainty’ should have been discussed under both ‘relevance’ and ‘faithful representation’. The question to critically consider thereafter would be is there a fundamental or even just a significant difference between ‘relevance’ and ‘faithful representation’, and if not, why are these two characteristics considered separately? Established practice has been to optimise the usefulness of financial information by considering both ‘relevance’ and ‘faithful representation’, and ‘measurement uncertainty’ under both. The probability thresholds defining recognition should remain a standards level decision due to significant diversity across standards, and not form part of ‘relevance’ and ‘faithful representation’ where ‘measurement uncertainty’ is considered.

6.4.5 Relevance and faithful representation

Question 1(e) to continue to identify relevance and faithful representation as the two fundamental qualitative characteristics of useful financial information? (Exposure Draft ED/2015/3 p. 10, IASB, 2015).

Table 6. 11 Relevance and faithful representation

Bank/ Group/ ED/2015/3 Q1	(e) Relevance and Faithful Representation
Australia and New Zealand Banking Group	<p>Qualified agreement. In terms of usefulness, the terms 'relevance' and 'faithful representation' are subordinate to the concept of 'fair presentation', already acknowledged by the IASB in IAS 1.15, and that International Auditing Standards require auditors to form a view as to whether general purpose financial statements are presented fairly.</p> <p>Fair Presentation is not referred to in the revised CF by the IASB.</p>
Banco Bradesco (Brazil)	Agreed.
Basel Committee on Banking Supervision	Qualified agreement. Reliance on the Fundamental QCs does not necessarily result in consistent standards or in consistent accounting policies being chosen when no standard applies.
BNP Paribas	<p>Disagreed. The term 'reliability' is more appropriate to meet the QCs of useful financial information instead of 'faithful representation'.</p> <p>Overruled by the IASB, and 'faithful representation' remains in the revised CF instead, with no mention of 'reliability' in the QC chapter two.</p>
Chartered Financial Analysts Society of the UK	<p>Qualified agreement. 'Faithful representation' has virtually the same meaning as 'reliability', and 'reliability' should be included in the CF.</p> <p>'Reliability' discussion is not made by the IASB in the CF's QCs.</p>
Credit Agricole Group	Qualified agreement. 'Reliability' should be included in the CF.

Deutsche Bank	Agreed.
European Banking Authority (EBA)	No comment. Although the EBA asked the IASB in its comment letter to address the implied differences between the concept of 'reliability' (as in the pre-2010 CF) and the concept of 'faithful representation' as proposed in the ED, the IASB did not, further evidence of governmentality and subjectivity.
German Savings Banks Association	Agreed.
The Hong Kong Association of Banks (HKAB)	Agreed.

Most commentators who wrote in, with the banks' letters summarised above in Table 3.5, agreed with the notion of continuing to identify 'relevance' and 'faithful representation' as the two fundamental QCs of useful financial information.

Curiously, some commentators referred to the QC 'reliability', the forerunner of 'faithful representation', as being applicable still, and not exactly the same as 'faithful representation', such that a place should be found in the QC chapter to explain 'reliability' and its relationship to 'faithful representation'. This was not done in the revised CF, however was discussed at a meeting of the project team for the Conceptual Framework revision, and no longer referred to in the document itself.

6.4.6 Further QC related comments

Table 6. 12 Further QC related comments

Bank/ Group/ ED/2015/3 Q1	(f) Further QC-related comments
Australia and New Zealand Banking Group	<p><i>'We continue to believe full convergence with the United States is essential if IFRSs are to truly bring efficiency to global markets by facilitating comparability amongst competitors. Accordingly, we strongly recommend that the IASB re-engage with the FASB with the objective of achieving a converged Conceptual Framework prior to the finalisation of the proposals.'</i></p> <p>Requested guidance from the IASB in situations where preparers need to develop an accounting policy in advance of an IFRIC and have to interpret an IFRS, as they are not sure if an earlier version of the Conceptual Framework would apply or the current ED.</p>
Banco Bradesco (Brazil)	<p>Noted that the IASB was not requesting comments on all parts of chapters 1 and 2.</p> <p>This 'deliberate omission' has a Foucauldian effect on what the comments deal with, sifting out further commentary for expected discussion in public by the IASB.</p>
Basel Committee on Banking Supervision	<p><i>'We would encourage the IASB and IAASB to co-operate on conceptual issues that are relevant to both parties.'</i></p> <p><i>The QCs are relatively lightly described, and therefore relatively subjective. The QCs will:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• contribute to the development of well-designed, consistent accounting standards only if the standard-setter interprets and applies those characteristics consistently; and</i> <i>• will not achieve the other objectives the IASB has for the framework unless there is widespread agreement outside the IASB as to how those QCs are to be interpreted and applied.'</i>
BNP Paribas	<p>An explicit discussion on 'reliability' (no comment made as to its similarity to 'relevance' or 'faithful representation') should be made in the CF in the QC chapter, as 'reliability' is fundamental in achieving usefulness of financial information.</p> <p>'Reliability' discussion is not made by the IASB in the CF's QCs.</p>

Chartered Financial Analysts Society of the UK	CFA(UK) commented that the exposure draft document was too lengthy for its investor members, being 92 pages long and the supporting basis for conclusions runs to 134 pages. 'A shorter consultation document would be easier for investors to digest and would probably generate a greater degree of engagement from the investor community.' The CFA(UK) also stated that it looked forward to providing input to the IASB on future projects such as financial statement presentation, which would be of great benefit to investors, its members.
Credit Agricole Group	In favour of reintroducing the characteristic of 'reliability' (no comment made as to its similarity to 'relevance' or 'faithful representation') as a key component of useful information, as in the pre-2010 framework.
European Banking Authority (EBA)	<p><i>'The EBA has a strong interest in promoting sound and high quality accounting and disclosure standards for the banking and financial industry, as well as transparent and comparable financial statements that would strengthen market discipline.'</i></p> <p>Many of the banks' stressed 'transparency' along with 'comparability', supporting the idea that 'transparency' could and perhaps should be a further QC. Users of financial statements, as they interpret the financial information, are entitled to know that a mindset of openness or 'transparency' has been applied.</p> <p>The EBA believes that the IASB should recognise Regulators more strongly as users, as banking regulators rely on financial information for their prudential assessments.</p>
European Banking Federation (EBF)	<i>'IFRS could now be inconsistent with the CF...not being amended by the IASB, it seems unreasonable to expect the entity to develop a revised accounting policy at a lower level in the hierarchy.'</i>

Many bank commentators were of the written opinion that the revised CF's QCs would be, in some particular instances, different or provide inconsistent guidance to that prescribed in the relevant accounting Standard, and that it is up to the IASB to synchronise and eliminate these perceived differences.

6.4.7 Summary

The revision of the Conceptual Framework, particularly chapter two under review at exposure draft level by the named banks' above, came after close scrutiny by many banking organisations with stakes in IFRS policy. In the past decade of development of the IASB's CF, due process has repeatedly led to debate on some fundamental issues, even questioning the naming and completeness of the fundamental characteristics of useful financial information. If the IASB had been able to resolve these issues, then the efficiency of the IASB's standard-setting process and the confidence that those countries following IFRS would have had, would have been significantly enhanced.

On balance, many bank commentators would probably consider that the IASB's approach has been the right approach.

6.5 Insights from other professional financial bodies literature on the updated QCs

As noted above, the UK Corporate Governance Code states that the board should present a 'Fair, Balanced and Understandable' assessment of the company's position and prospects. Fair is similar to the fundamental QC 'faithful representation', Balanced is similar to 'neutrality', while Understandable is exactly the same as one of the enhancing QCs.

The International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB), an independent standards body which issues standards such as International Standards on Auditing, has as its overarching audit opinion the pronouncement of whether the banks' accounts are true and fair, fair presentation (ISA, 2016). This differs from the IASB's faithful representation as mentioned in the comment letters analysed above.

6.6 Summary comparison findings of QCs before and after revision

The revised CF, issued by the IASB in March 2018, includes a new chapter on measurement, guidance on reporting financial performance, improved definitions of an asset and a liability, and guidance supporting these definitions, as well as clarification

on the roles of stewardship, 'prudence' and 'measurement uncertainty' in financial reporting.

The Board also updated references to the Conceptual Framework in IFRS standards by issuing '*Amendments to References to the Conceptual Framework in IFRS Standards*'. This was done to support transition to the revised CF for companies that develop accounting policies using the CF when no IFRS standard applies to a particular transaction.

'In the absence of an IFRS standard that specifically applies to a transaction, other event or condition, management uses its judgement in developing and applying an accounting policy that results in information that is relevant and reliable. In making that judgement management refers to the following sources in descending order:

- *The requirements and guidance in IFRS standards dealing with similar and related issues; and*
- *The definitions, recognition criteria and measurement concepts for assets, liabilities, income and expenses in the Conceptual Framework.'* (IAS 8 Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors, 2018).

6.7 Cross country comparison, and Brexit influence

Brexit was originally meant to happen on 29 March 2019. However, there remains nervousness in the UK banking industry over what financial reporting standards shall apply post-Brexit, noting that at present UK listed banks' follow 'IFRS as adopted by the EU'. Many users' of banks' financial reports are well served by IFRS standards, which facilitate cross country comparisons of banks'. The ideal situation would be for the UK and the IOM to adopt IFRS unadulterated, if those IFRS standards are adopted by the Audit, Reporting and Governance Authority, which replaced the previous regulator, the Financial Reporting Council (FRC), from 1 April 2019, which has powers delegated to it under the Companies Act 2006. A risk of this approach is that the resurrection of national power over standard-setting shall invite banks' to lobby for deviations from IFRS (Fuller, 2018). It is useful to note that the UK already has a (minor) influence

within the IASB, as part of a wider European (not EU) cohort, allowing collaboration in research and technical developments. Could FRS 102 have more influence in the UK and locally in the IOM under the new Regulator, The Audit, Reporting and Governance Authority, or shall the standards become instead of 'IFRS as adopted by the EU', 'IFRS as adopted by the UK's Audit, Reporting and Governance Authority'? It is also likely that the IASB shall move its offices away from London after the Brexit date. Interestingly, it is also possible that there may be a decline in influence of the IASB after Brexit, due to UK and British Islands (incl. IOM) and possibly some Commonwealth countries, for example South Africa, moving away from the IASB to their national standards instead. This would be a boon to British banking business, as the regulatory environment would diminish from that of the EU and Prudential Regulatory Authority (PRA) of the Bank of England to only that of the BoE's PRA, along of course with its Financial Conduct Authority.

6.7.1 Differences across jurisdictions

Views of regulators and even auditors in the jurisdictions of this study, the IOM, UK and South Africa, are decision-critical as to the prioritisation of banks' annual reports as communication tools, or as compliance documents.

In contrast, banks' in some other jurisdictions may be in the early stages of implementing IFRS standards, focussing more on fulfilling the disclosure requirements of IFRS rather than the obvious communication tool that their annual reports serve to their stakeholders, or even the compliance requirements that their regulators may be insisting upon for their annual reports' disclosures (IFRS Foundation, 2019).

Substantial non-compliance with IFRS has been found to exist in Australia consistent with recent studies (Cascino and Gassen, 2015, abstract). For their sample of German and Italian firms selected, they found that compliance incentives, voluntary incentives or managerial incentives, at the level of the firm, the region, and the country 'systematically shaped IFRS compliance', being positively correlated. They further noted that 'firms from countries with tighter reporting enforcement experience larger IFRS comparability effects, and that public firms adopting IFRS become less comparable to local GAAP private firms from the same country.' They also found that

'public firms and firms from the same country report more comparable earnings'. While the former result is consistent with public firms having greater incentives to comply because they are subject to stronger enforcement (Ball and Shivakumar, 2005, p. 83), the latter result is consistent with the idea that firms sharing the same institutional infrastructure tend to have more comparable reporting practices.'

This study's emphasis on the small self-governing British island of the Isle of Man, illustrates its banks' dependence on their holding group companies for accounting policy notes, and interaction with the UK regulators and national accounting bodies. Although small island economies work differently to larger, mainland jurisdictions, due mainly to small population size, lack of economies of scale, dependence on external markets, and sometimes with potentially problematic governance forms and practices, nevertheless, many island jurisdictions' have achieved economic success and / or stability. The use of IFRS for reporting by many of the Isle of Man banks' runs counter to the generally held belief that IFRS have typically been designed from a large-state perspective. It is curious to realise that due to the banks' international affiliations through their holding companies, that IFRS for large corporations is used rather than IFRS for SMEs (small and medium enterprises).

6.8 Summary

The further method employed in this study has been content analysis. This technique was used to directly analyse the interviews held with preparers and users. Content analysis was also used to investigate the nature and extent of the changes in QCs of decision-useful financial information found in the international and local banks' annual report 2017/18 disclosures, compared to those found post publication of the Conceptual Framework revised late March 2018 by the IASB, with its updated QCs, in 2018/19. The content of comment letters written in to the IASB before revision of the Conceptual Framework, were also analysed.

Chapter 7 Discussion of Summary Findings

7.1 Discussion of signpostings from the literature review

'The primary purpose of an effective conceptual framework should be to assist the IASB to develop standards', (Barker and Teixeira, 2018, p. 153). Yet there are demonstrable gaps in the IASB's framework, implying a conceptual vagueness. The literature review did not set out to explore how the revised Conceptual Framework dealt with the purpose of transactions entered into by banks', rather whether the term decision-useful should be reinstated or whether the stewardship model prevailed. In the event, the literature clarified that the concept 'decision-useful' to describe the financial information, came from the original FASB diagram of the qualitative characteristics, its hierarchy of accounting qualities, which the IASB initially adopted. Then on their divorce in 2010, the IASB reverted to its preferred rationale for financial information, to provide users' with financial reports that allowed decisions over stewardship of the entity's economic resources to be made, rather than decisions of the financial strength of the entity.

Chapter two's literature review also illustrated that the concept of 'transparency' was found to be missing from the qualitative characteristics, specifically by Cascino et al. 2017, 2016, and Nobes and Stadler, 2014.

Chapter two's timeline of conceptual frameworks' illustrated that 'materiality' was included as a pervasive constraint in the earlier combined Conceptual Framework of the IASB and FASB in 2010 (Figure 2.2), yet for no communicated reason was later shown by both the IASB (Figure 2.4) and FASB (Figure 2.3) to be an entity-specific element of 'relevance' only, and no longer a constraint. The IASB did this by changing the Conceptual Framework's statement on materiality to be:

'Information is material if omitting it or misstating it could influence decisions that the primary users of general purpose financial reports (see paragraph 1.5) make on the basis of those reports, which provide financial information about a specific reporting entity. In other words, materiality is an entity-specific aspect of relevance based on the nature or magnitude, or both, of the items to which the information relates in the context of an individual entity's financial report. Consequently, the Board cannot specify a uniform

quantitative threshold for materiality or predetermine what could be material in a particular situation.’ (IASB, 2018a, s.2.11)

This statement on materiality, a significantly important accounting concept in IFRS standards, helps companies decide whether information should be included in their financial statements. The fact that there is a practice statement issued in 2017 called ‘IFRS Practice Statement 2: Making Materiality Judgements’ is no reason to omit materiality as a constraint, rather it is supportive that ‘materiality’ is indeed a practical consideration, a constraint. This thesis strongly suggests reinstating ‘materiality’ as a constraint, while leaving materiality, if the Board feels necessary, as an aspect of ‘relevance’ in addition, for emphasis and classification.

There is little in the literature review that pertains to how the Conceptual Framework takes small island economies into account. Performing the data gathering for this research from all applicable Isle of Man banks’, showed a constraint that could be perceived to be missing from the Conceptual Framework, namely ‘Regulatory / Supervisory’. The Conceptual Framework does allude to the usefulness of information to ‘hold management to account’ (IASB, 2018a, SP s.1.5(b), stating further that ‘As a source of globally comparable information, those standards are also of vital importance to regulators around the world’. This does not go far enough, however the IASB explains itself by stating:

‘Other parties, such as regulators and members of the public other than investors, lenders and other creditors, may also find general purpose financial reports useful. However, those reports are not primarily directed to these other groups’ (IASB, 2018a, s.1.10).

‘...management has responsibilities...ensuring that the entity complies with applicable laws, regulations and contractual provisions’ (IASB, 2018a, s.1.23).

The IASB itself admits that *‘the legal and regulatory frameworks for such entities (sole proprietorships, partnerships, trusts or various types of government business undertakings) are often different from frameworks that apply to corporate entities’ (IASB, 2018a, s.4.67), further confirming in IASB, 2018a, s.7.13 that to provide useful*

information, component elements such as equity may be 'subject to particular legal, regulatory or other requirements.' This practical consideration signposts the rationale for having 'Regulatory / Supervisory' as a constraint, as such regulations or laws need to be taken into account on disclosure of financial information. Finningham (2010) p. 21 concluded that 'global comparability will be dependent on factors other than accounting standards such as regulatory oversight.' Finningham's conclusion arose even though the European Union (EU) had regulated that International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) be adopted from 2005.

The literature is silent on professional regulations such as those of the British Bankers Association (BBA), subsumed into UK Finance from 2017, which states that not only accounting standards be used as a source of disclosure for banks', but company law too, and if listed, the stock exchange or listing requirements too, confirmed by Finningham (2010) p. 58. The literature does confirm that national regulations are a reason for deviations from comparability within the EU itself for example, and definitely, as in this study, between South Africa and Australia and UK banking accounting policy disclosures, although it is acknowledged that convergence between national accounting standards towards international accounting standards is taking place. Ball (2016) on the other hand suggests that public sector entities accounts are driven by their own countries regulations, outside of the accounting standards.

Barker and Teixeira (2018) noted that Standard-setters are continuing to have to 'work with a (Conceptual Framework) model created to resolve a problem of the 1970s', the framework being over 40 years' old. 'The Trueblood Committee proposed a Conceptual Framework to underpin consistency in standard-setting'. Barker and Teixeira (2018) propose that 'the professionalism of standard-setting has removed the problem the framework was meant to address'. This is contradicted by Walton (2018) who suggests that 'Standard-setters prefer incremental change' and that 'it should be no surprise that the IASB has not considered ...fundamentally redesigning its Conceptual Framework...'.

7.2 Discussion of summary findings from the interviews

This study found that the power of the IASB was felt to be more indirect than direct, with the Regulator (the FRC and PRA for UK banks' and the IOM FSA for the IOM banks')

having a more direct prominent role than that of the IASB. Likewise, the governmentality of the IASB was not felt as strongly by the banking participants as anticipated, seeing instead their external auditors as more directly influential, particularly when accounting policies wording needed to be decided upon. Indeed, the IOM bank participants relied more upon their Group determining the accounting policy wording and disclosure, and doubt was cast over whether the IASB's qualitative characteristics were referred to at all by this grouping. The acceptance of the IASB's Conceptual Framework by the bank preparers and users showed not their subjectification, but their apparent almost indifference. Indeed, the participants thought the IASB's processes transparent enough, yet incongruously could not proffer any thoughts about the members comprising the IASB's Conceptual Framework Project Committee probably because they did not know who the members were, even though there was a significant proportion of banking industry representation. The low interaction with the IASB by the banks' from the IOM, UK, South Africa and Australia, along with users' interviewed from all the geographical areas above except for Australia, is because there is a reliance by such professional accountants on both their professional accounting bodies, and the applicable Regulators, Figure 7.1 Foucault's 'Panopticon of Power' depicts these relationships. This lack of direct knowledge and involvement is surprising given the recent financial crisis, and the need to have a level playing field for all banks' disclosures that fairly represent and is relevant.

This research has contributed to the body of literature on power of and governmentality by the IASB, as it adds to findings from previous studies (Carter and Warren, 2018) with the use of more recent data from the semi-structured interviews held, through a different angle of inquiry, suggesting that the IASB is suffering a legitimacy crisis. In addition, and unlike Nobes and Stadler, 2014, the first empirical study using publicly available data to provide direct evidence about the role of QCs of financial information in accounting decisions, this research found the role of the qualitative characteristics to be minimal from a practical point of view, and largely theoretical.

Figure 7.1 Foucault's 'Panopticon of Power'

1. Basel Committee on Banking Supervision participates in the Monitoring Board as an observer; includes Capital market and other public authorities
2. The 14 trustees of the IFRS Foundation are responsible for the governance and oversight of the IASB, including the Constitution and due process for the development of accounting standards, Due Process Oversight Committee and Interpretations Committee (see also Table A.1)
3. Hans Hoogervorst (who succeeded Sir David Tweedie as Chairman of the IASB on retirement in 2011), and Professor Geoffrey Whittington, Cambridge (Foucault's 'London Governmentalists')

As can be seen in chapters five and six, the revised CF has had little effect on the QCs used in financial reporting of banks' in the countries studied. Further analysis focused on identifying the QCs that precipitated the most disclosure. It was concluded that the implementation of the revised CF and their QCs has had little impact on the accounting policy changes of banks' financial reports. Chapters five and six also report on findings from interviews conducted with both preparers' and users' of banks' financial reports who were affected by the revised CF. What can be concluded from the data is that preparers' and users' do not feel that the financial statements are decision-useful as they are too long and too complex, often running to hundreds of pages, in the case of UK listed banks', while the local Isle of Man banks' believe that the financial reports usefulness is more for Regulators rather than the investor, or depositor. All participants in the study alluded to the probability that the costs of producing the accounts in their current format have been outweighed by the benefits.

As reported under 6.7 above, interviewees recognised that after Brexit, the UK and its British Islands, may no longer have accounting policies that are fully compatible with the EU. Presently, the UK and its British Islands, such as the Isle of Man, are using IFRS as adopted by the EU. Brexit thus has the consequence of the UK and the Isle of Man banks' most likely using both IFRS and their own national accounting standards to report under, as is the case presently with banks' in South Africa and Australia forming part of this study.

Dunne, 2003, pronounced on the consultation process, supporting the decision-usefulness of financial information:

'From the interviews, users need to engage more with the financial reporting process in order to understand and thus enhance the usability of financial reports and to ensure that published reports are useful for decision-making purposes. Perhaps more extensive communication and encouragement to engage in the IASB's consultation process would help in this regard' (Dunne, 2003 p. 155).

From the interviews held with users, 'transparency' was raised, suggesting that 'transparency' be a further determinant of decision-useful financial information, particularly across the voluntary sections of the banks' annual reports. The participants' interviewed thought differently, believing 'transparency' to be a fairly poor standalone characteristic, because of its implication for the amount of information that is implied needs to be shown. Conversely, the pilot participant believed that 'transparency' could indeed be a separate QC, included as an enhancing QC under 'faithful representation', as 'you can have 'completeness', 'neutrality', and 'free from error', and not be 'transparent'".

Key participant user interviews, believed 'materiality' to be a key qualitative characteristic. This is not in accordance with the literature, which up to and including 2010, the year of IASB and FASB's 'divorce', showed 'materiality' as a constraint, and only afterwards did both the IASB and FASB suggest 'materiality' form part of 'relevance', and be entity-specific. This researcher finds that 'materiality' does definitely play a part subordinate to 'relevance' as a characteristic, yet presupposes, in addition, that 'materiality' also be reinstated to the situation up to 2010 where it was viewed as a 'constraint'. Interview participants' felt that 'materiality' should have been specifically dealt with in the chapter on qualitative characteristics, 'to improve the narrative of decision-useful financial information', while the IASB itself recognised the uncertainty surrounding 'materiality' and began in 2017 a project to define what is material in the context of financial reporting.

The Isle of Man bank participants' confirmed the signposting from the literature review to do with information for the Regulator being a constraint. The participants' from the Isle of Man believed that in their case there were two main users of their banks' annual reports being their group holding company, and the Regulator, in this case, the IOM Financial Services Authority, rather than other user's such as investors or even surprisingly depositors. They believed also that here was an argument for reporting in different formats for different audiences, which does happen already within banks' reporting. Liquidity and mismatch of assets and liabilities reports along with monthly management accounts are reported by regulated banks' to the IOM FSA on a quarterly and monthly basis respectively.

7.3 Discussion of summary findings from changes in accounting policy notes

Unlike Nobes and Stadler (2014) who only looked at accounting policy changes, this research included initial accounting policy choices as well as any possible accounting policy changes of going concern banks'. Nobes and Stadler looked at 434 policy changes, finding 147 explained using one or more qualitative characteristics, in particular, 'relevance', 'faithful representation', 'comparability', 'understandability', and transparency or clarity which had also been found earlier by Dichev et al. (2013). Using the same criteria for scoring as Nobes and Stadler (2014), the same definitions of qualitative characteristics, the research did not find any further qualitative characteristics to that offered by the Board's Conceptual Framework. There was however a high NVivo 11 matching found for the word 'Regulatory', Figure 6.1, illustrating the constraint or practical consideration that should be illustrated within the Conceptual Framework's qualitative characteristics diagram.

7.4 Discussion of summary findings from comment letters

None of the five questions asked by the IASB, at the time of the issuance of the 2015 exposure draft, of its stakeholders, mentioned 'decision-useful' or even useful financial information. The interviewees', when asked specifically about whether the concept of 'decision-useful' should be reinstated or not, overwhelmingly suggested that it need not. Indeed, the comment letters supported this viewpoint all be it from a more 'loaded' question as framed and put to users of the Conceptual Framework for the 2015 exposure draft. The German Savings Banks Association's letter most eloquently stated its outlier view, that decision-usefulness and stewardship are intertwined and not easily separable. FASB sees 'stewardship' as a sub-set of 'decision-usefulness', while incongruously, and with its power and governmentality, the IASB has foisted the term 'stewardship' to locate a more prominent position in its Conceptual Framework, subordinating the term 'decision' instead to each and nearly every paragraph describing the individual qualitative characteristics and constraints therein. It is therefore proposed by this researcher that 'decision-useful' be reinstated in the title, see Figure 8.1 below and recommendations.

Two of the comment letters, those from the French Banking Federation and the European Banking Authority, considered 'transparency' in their replies about stewardship, with diametrically opposed views. The French Banking Federation believed that if strategic information is shared in the banks' annual reports, then competitors could use this to their benefit (the approach for exclusion of 'transparency' as a QC adopted by FASB), while the European Banking Authority believed 'transparency' should be a further QC as comparability and openness are favourable characteristics for stakeholders of their banks' annual reports. The European Banking Authority appeared clearly influenced by the research of EFRAG (European Financial Reporting Action Group) written up by Cascino et al. (2017), Cascino et al. (2016), and Nobes and Stadler (2014). Such thought outliers, raised in the banks' comment letters to the IASB, were found to have been omitted by the IASB's technocrats when reporting back to the profession, confirming Stewart (2005) who stated that non-governmental organisations (like the IASB), lack numerous procedural safeguards, such as accountability, oversight, participation in the standards-setting process, and transparency of the decision-making process. There is a particular irony emanating herein from the literature review, the comment letters, and Appendix B, the IASB's Policy Development Process, in that there has been found to be a lack of transparency within the IASB's own decision-making process, yet 'transparency' has been mooted by many writers and researchers to be a further qualitative characteristic, or by this researcher, constraint, to be included in the Conceptual Framework.

Curiously, as it is known that banks' have a majority participation on the Board of the IASB, ignoring banks' comment letters suggests that the inner circle of the IASB excludes bank representatives, thereby enabling their own opinions to be foisted as conclusive, a reflection of the Foucauldian power and governmentality argued in this thesis as applying.

7.5 Summary

Discussion in this chapter of the summary findings from literature review signpostings, interviews, banks' changes in accounting policy notes, and comment letters, analysed by way of Foucauldian critical discourse analysis and content analysis, leads into next chapter's metasummary and conclusion.

Chapter 8 Conclusions, Limitations and Further Research

8.1 Introduction

Finally, chapter eight concludes the thesis, allowing for epistemological reflection, interactively moving between pragmatic practices and academic theory. Policy implications and recommendations are highlighted, both in order that they may assist future completeness of the qualitative characteristics, and to suggest improvements to the IASB's consultation process. Certain limitations of the current thesis are highlighted, along with potential future research avenues to be explored.

This thesis explored the International Accounting Standards Board's qualitative characteristics. A literature review in chapter two, discussed the International IASB's Conceptual Framework history and policy development process, thereafter discussing the pre-eminent literature on the qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information, finishing with an introduction to Foucault and what his themes may have to say about the IASB and the Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting in particular, before asking the research questions. Chapter three reported on the research methodologies of Foucauldian critical discourse analysis and content analysis, theoretically, and how they could be used to answer the research questions posed. In chapter four, research methods employed in this study were reported upon, the collection of data from the semi-structured interviews, the analysis of banks' changes in accounting policy notes, and the comment letters written in to the IASB from banks' and banking associations'. Chapter five discussed the findings using Foucauldian critical discourse analysis, while chapter six discussed the findings using content analysis. Chapter seven then discussed these summary findings. New constraints that might be applicable to the qualitative characteristics of useful financial information were suggested, and the suggested reinstatement of the adjective 'decision-useful' describing the qualitative characteristics, supported. The applicability of the supranational Conceptual Framework's qualitative characteristics to small economies, particularly British Islands', dependant for accounting regulations on their National regulatory body and, in many cases, UK law, was found to be mostly low and not considered, particularly when considering accounting policies where the International Financial Reporting Standards have not yet offered suggestions or alternatives, such as for cryptocurrencies. This final

chapter aims to succinctly restate the thesis main findings, diagrammatically illustrating the IASB's perceived governmentality and power, which may lead to improvements by suggesting that there could be further constraints in an attempt for there to be completeness of the qualitative characteristics.

A direct descendant of the Trueblood Report is the overall objective and purpose of banks' reported financial information being to be useful for making business and economic decisions. Indeed, the Conceptual Framework s.1.2 now states that:

'The objective of general purpose financial reporting is to provide financial information about the reporting entity that is useful to existing and potential investors, lenders and other creditors in making decisions relating to providing resources to the entity.'

Without the IASB providing a definition of 'stewardship', it is difficult to understand, given the objective above containing the words decision and useful, why the IASB has omitted the adjective decision from its chapter two title on qualitative characteristics, particularly as the definition 'decision-useful' perhaps may subsume the normal definition of 'stewardship'.

The researcher, for reasons given throughout this thesis, believes that 'transparency' may be an additional criteria of decision-useful financial reporting, not as some authors have proposed a qualitative characteristic in its own right (Cascino et al., 2016 and 2017, and Nobes and Stadler, 2014), and that if the Chairmen of major UK banks' and professors of accounting were to be shown this research's suggested diagram of the qualitative characteristics incorporating 'transparency', Figure 8.1, that it may be accepted. 'Transparency' appears to the researcher to be more in the nature of a practical consideration or 'criterion', rather than an enhancing qualitative characteristic, and as one of the criteria, may be more readily accepted by stakeholders, in this case banks', as users of the Conceptual Framework, and may possibly be included by the IASB on revision.

8.2 Metasummary

Figure 8.1 Suggested qualitative characteristics figure

Reference: Adapted from original FASB hierarchy of accounting qualities 1980, to 2019 from this research

Figure 8.2 Qualitative characteristics gap model

Adapted from: Parasuraman et al. (1988), Communication and Control Processes in the delivery of Service Quality. *Journal of Marketing*, 52(4), p. 38.

From the interviews particularly with the Isle of Man banks', and comment letters from banks' and banking associations' such as Deutsche Bank and the European Banking Association, it became apparent that banks' may need to recognise their Regulator(s) more as further users, as banking regulations may indicate reliance on financial information for their prudential assessments inclusive of the bank's annual report. Hence to perhaps include 'Regulatory / Supervisory' as a potential constraint or a practical consideration, a limitation or a restriction, may have credence particularly as the Regulations, which could be National accounting standards in addition to the Banking Regulators requirements, could have a likely direct effect on the qualitative characteristics of 'comparability' and 'timeliness'. Even if one extrapolates this thinking to IFRS standards, IFRS as adopted by the EU, or IFRS as adopted by the particular Nation state, these accounting regulations apply, so consideration could be given to perhaps including 'Regulatory / Supervisory' conditions as a new constraint.

It is conceded that materiality is entity specific and can remain under 'relevance', however, it may potentially also remain as a constraint, a practical consideration (see Figure 2.1, where FASB showed materiality as a constraint from 1980 onwards). An entity can choose to report immaterial information, and in so doing has considered, practically, what information is disclosed amountwise. FASB Concept Statement 8, paragraph BC 3.18, reports that 'A standard setter does not consider materiality when it is developing standards because it is an entity-specific consideration.' Standard setters are not the only users of the Conceptual Framework, acknowledged by the IASB within SP1.1 (b), which also says 'assist preparers to develop consistent accounting policies when no Standard applies...'. Preparers may have a practical consideration to make as to materiality of the transaction or event when choosing between accounting policies, and hence materiality should be seriously reconsidered as being potentially reinstated as a 'constraint', while also being defined under 'relevance' as it is at present.

One of the reasons that further discussion may need to take place over the above potential reinstatement of 'decision' into the title of the Conceptual Framework, and the three possible further constraints of 'transparency', 'Regulatory / Supervisory', and 'materiality' which may be added (Figure 8.1), is that, from studying what Foucault can teach us about power, governmentality, and possibly subjectification, is the 'fault' in

the CF acceptance procedure. The comment letters from the exposure draft stage for example are published, however the IASB working group is determined by the IASB itself, and the working group's technical writers can 'cherry pick' what goes through to the final edition of the Conceptual Framework, and what does not. Minority discourses could have been written out and over by the dominant IASB.

These suggested five golden threads (decision-useful, transparency, Regulatory / Supervisory, materiality, and power of selection of the qualitative characteristics and their constraints), are further able to be depicted adapting the Parasuraman et al. 1985, 1988 model of service quality (Figure 8.2), where preparers and users perceived qualitative characteristics (and constraints) may not be what the IASB has delivered.

8.3 Policy implications and recommendations

It is possible that a 'high speed' outcome may have been considered more important by the IASB than a 'high quality' outcome when publishing the revised Conceptual Framework late March 2018. From the findings of this study, from one or more of the literature review papers, content analysis of the interviews, content analysis of the changes in accounting policies, and an analysis of the comment letters, looked at through a Foucauldian lens, a number of policy implications are suggested as follows:

- a. For global comparability, the number of choices provided in the IFRSs may need to be limited, (Kvaal and Nobes, 2010).
- b. The interviews (s.7.2) perhaps highlighted that users' may need to engage more with the financial reporting process in order to possibly enhance the usability of financial reports and to ensure that published reports are useful for decision-making purposes. Perhaps more extensive communication and encouragement to engage in the IASB's consultation process would assist, along with communication from the IASB's various projects committee members, more transparency of the composition of its projects committee members upfront, rather than historical disclosure (s.7.2) where it was stated that all participants did not have a clue who were in the IASB's projects' committees).

Table 8.1 Timeline of concepts proposed

Timeline of concepts proposed

Direction of travel →

Concept	1989: IASB's Initial Conceptual Framework	2010: 'Joint' IASB & FASB Conceptual Framework	Late March 2018: Revised Conceptual Framework	Literature Review	Late 2018: Semi-structured Interviews	Content Analysis: Changes in Accounting Policies Notes 2017 / 2018	Content Analysis of Comment Letters to ED, written 2015	Foucauldian CDA: Power, Governmentality, Subjugation	Thesis proposal
Decision-useful	Included in title of chapter on QCs	Still included in title of QCs chapter	'Decision' excluded from title on useful financial information	'Decision' dropped from Cascino et al. (2017) onwards in article titles	Inclusion of 'decision' not critical, as felt it is implied	No direct mention of 'decision-useful'	Biased question asked by IASB on prominence of 'stewardship', ignoring 'decision-useful'	German Savings Bank question on 'decision-useful' ignored. IASB does not ask members their view	Consider reinstating in title of chapter on QCs, until members polled
Transparency	Not mentioned as a potential QC or constraint	Not mentioned as a potential QC or constraint	Not mentioned as a potential QC or constraint. 'Transparency' through Standards	Strong support as a QC from Barth (2010), through Nobes & Stadler (2014), to Williams (2018)	Users suggested 'transparency' as a constraint	No direct evidence of use, however annual report's refer to 'transparency', see Figure 5.1	Two banking associations strongly stressed 'transparency' alongside 'comparability', as a QC	Despite overwhelming support, 'transparency' as a QC is not discussed by the IASB	'Transparency' should be at least a 'constraint', a determinant to consider
Materiality	'Materiality' shown as a threshold for recognition, similar to 'constraint'	'Materiality' remains a threshold for recognition, similar to 'constraint'	'Materiality' is an entity-specific aspect of 'relevance', to be further defined by IASB's materiality project	Supports 'materiality' as both a quantitative and qualitative concept, Raziuniene & Verbickaitė (2017)	Preparer felt 'materiality' all pervasive, linking into other QCs, similar to a 'constraint'	'Materiality' directly addressed in nearly all cases (Appendix C)	No mention in Comment Letters. ED shows 'materiality' under 'relevance'	IASB unilaterally placed 'materiality' under 'relevance', not consulting on 'constraint' withdrawal	Leave both under 'relevance', and reinstate as a 'constraint'
Regulatory / Supervisory	Not mentioned as a potential QC or constraint	Not mentioned as a potential QC or constraint	Not mentioned as a potential QC or constraint	Comparability dependent on regulatory oversight, Finningham (2010)	ICM banks preparers referred to importance of regulatory constraints such as ICM FSA	Some participants noted information disclosed under national accounting regulations	Regulators simply ignored by standard-setters', Basel Committee (2015) Comment Letter	National Accounting Standards and Regulators overruled by IFRS, unless stated	Include 'Regulatory / Supervisory' as a constraint

- c. It is suggested that the adjective 'decision-useful' could be reintroduced back into the title of the second chapter of the revised Conceptual Framework, replacing 'useful' financial information. This is because financial information is nearly always likely to be used for decision-making, more so than for stewardship or financial governance calls about the running of the entity, in this case banks', by Regulators in small island economies. Decisions about the banks' financial strength or financial position, are made both by investors and by Regulators. The comment letter written by the German Savings Banks Association (s.6.4.1) highlighted the dilemma of deciding upon decision-useful versus stewardship, and the Literature Review chapter of this thesis on p. 11 stated the fact that FASB have kept the 'decision-usefulness' title to their conceptual framework.

- d. As the researched banks' accounting policies were found to be fairly standard in wording, it is recommended by the researcher that these 'standard' accounting policies could be linked to from banks' online annual report web pages, which may shorten and make more user-friendly the information actually provided to users. This idea has now been mooted within the IASB in its Staff paper for its meeting held June 2018 (IASB, 2018c). The paper suggested within the ambit of the IASB's project called 'Disclosure Initiative : Principles of Disclosure' on p. 3, that the Disclosure Initiative could 'provide flexibility to entities about where to locate information', and in paragraph 27 of the same paper stated that the Disclosure Initiative could 'help auditors to decide which accounting policies to disclose'.

- e. As already suggested by the New Zealand Accounting Standards Board (IFRS, 2019), the accounting policy options offered to preparers' of banks' financial statements in the IFRS standards could be less prescriptive (less rules-based) and more principles-based, or even one which might involve having a reduced disclosure regime.

- f. Although possibly not the most cost-effective way to address potential communication problems between the Board and users and preparers of banks' financial statements as evidenced by this thesis and the interviews held with

preparers of banks' financial statements, educational materials, webinars, articles, and other further non-mandatory guidance may be helpful (IFRS website, Supporting materials for IFRS Standards).

This contextually relevant and timely meta-analysis matters, as it both informs and inflects accounting society debate.

8.4 Limitations of the study

This thesis explored the completeness of the International Accounting Standards Board's qualitative characteristics. The decision to analyse the accounting policy choices of banks' annual reports published in the year prior to, and following the publication of the revised CF may be recognised as a limitation of the present study, for the reason that the periods chosen are discrete and limited in number which may give results that are not upheld in future annual reports or results that may have been anticipated by the early-adopters. Although the completeness of the IASB's QCs has endeavoured to be pronounced upon from the periods chosen in this thesis, an examination of annual reports accounting policy changes for the same banks' for a longer period of time than was available for this study following the publication of the revised QCs late March 2018, may provide further insight into the changes brought about by the revised CF.

It is also acknowledged that the present study is limited in its scope. The revised CF applies to all listed companies that have adopted IFRS, while this thesis is an exploration of the impact of this requirement on a sample of banks' annual reports only, and this sample, although saturating the IOM banks' that met the applicability conditions for analysis, used very few UK banks' and a singular South African bank and Australian bank. This sample could always be extended to try obtain further clarification of results, although fairly significant rich findings may be made from the original sample.

The small sample of banks' interviewed, even though the Isle of Man banks' that reported under IFRS were saturated, is also a limitation as it cannot be extrapolated to the wider island economies without the research being replicated or triangulated

using further self-governing island economies, such as the British Islands of Jersey, Guernsey or Gibraltar. Nevertheless, perhaps for the first time, an island economy's banks' have been involved in research concerning the IASB and their interaction with the governing standard-setting body.

Other limitations relate to the research methods employed in the investigation. The aim was to use content analysis and Foucauldian critical discourse analysis to analyse interviews, content analysis to analyse changes in accounting policies of the banks' annual reports chosen for the study, and an analysis of the comment letters. It is acknowledged that the use of content analysis techniques and Foucauldian CDA involve a substantial element of subjectivity, with researcher bias having a significant impact on the decisions taken when collecting, analysing and interpreting data. Further difficulties associated with the content analysis technique relate to the questions asked or the source materials available. However, these inherent elements of error may have been reduced by the suitable, reliable and accurate coding scheme that guided coding during content analysis, and the choice of the commonly used annual reports of banks' as a medium of analysis, allowing for the attempted extraction of the nature and extent of the changes in QCs of decision-useful financial information in such bank's annual report disclosures.

On reflection, as customised software was not in the main used, except for Figure 6.1 quantification of significant qualitative characteristics or potential qualitative characteristics, the robustness and transparency of the analysis can be questioned. If NVivo 11 had been used throughout, then the tasks engaged in, their sequence, role and documentation, may have been more easily illustrated than when working manually. In the event, manually looking at the changes in accounting policy notes for known existing qualitative characteristics may have been more deductive than inductive, and probably likely to be equal to the use of NVivo 11 software, with greater immersion in the data possibly allowing for greater conviction in results found.

Due to the nature of a doctoral study, the data was coded and themes identified in the data by one person and the analysis then discussed with the researcher's supervisors. This process might have allowed for consistency in the method but failed to provide multiple perspectives from a variety of people with differing expertise. This may have

been partly overcome by the use of Nobes and Stadler's (2014) coding sheets and definitions, perhaps allowing for greater validity and comparability of study findings.

This research was limited to a focus of the completeness of the QCs for both the preparer and the user groupings. User groupings were limited to Investment Analyst Society members, and did not include other user groups such as employees, lenders, suppliers, trade creditors, customers, government, and the general public. Although beyond the scope of the current thesis due to size limitations, a survey of the completeness of the QCs using other user groups may yield further insights about the QCs on revision of the CF. Nevertheless, by focussing on the main user grouping could have provided in-depth findings to emerge from the grouping which may not have been found if a smorgasbord of user groupings had been included in the study.

Finally, more robust findings might have been made by increasing the number of user groupings that were interviewed, both intra-geographical regionally and extending the interviews to Australia, to their Investment Analyst Society or Chartered Financial Advisors societies, as was proposed. However, these interviews were not granted even though requests came for them via their UK equivalent. This could be because their societies were likely not as organised or research-friendly as those encountered in the UK and South Africa. Nevertheless, potential rich findings may have been obtained from the user interviews that were held (chapter 7.2).

8.5 Opportunities for further development from the research

Below are eleven extensions identified of the present thesis as potential avenues for future research.

The first two involve the seminal Parasuraman, Zeithamel and Berry (1985) model of Service Quality. There may be a gap between the perceptions of the IASB and preparers', and the expectations of users' of financial reporting, arising because the IASB may potentially be making, on occasion, final decisions unilaterally on the QCs adopted (Figure 8.2).

Firstly, the QCs adopted, and those not adopted in the revised CF can perhaps be ranked, and from that ranking, the fundamental or enhancing categorisation as at present, may be rearranged. For many it may seem imperative to potentially ensure likely validity of the QCs and their probable completeness first, before rankings may be undertaken. Nevertheless, some researchers have just started to perform what they are terming 'operationalising' of the QCs of financial reporting (Mbobo and Ekpo, 2016), (Tasios and Bekiaris, 2012), both of which build on Van Beest et al. (2009). What is not included in these studies is the potential gap that may exist between the users' and preparers' viewpoints on the rankings of the QCs, and the potential use of the seminal Parasuraman, Zeithamel and Berry (1985) methodology to rank the QCs, all of which gave rise to SERVQUAL, the operationalisation of service quality characteristics. The Parasuraman, Zeithamel, Berry ranking and gap model may need to be researched post the revised CF, not before, as the other researchers have done, and this is where this researcher is currently using DECFIN[®], a bespoke self-designed operational quantification of the ranked QCs, used in order to obtain multivariate analysis correlations by way of the statistical tool of structured equation modelling, with the revised Conceptual Framework's QCs.

Secondly, views on the adoption of the revised CF in light of the IASB's Financial Reporting Project's aim of simplifying disclosures, may be a fruitful area for future research. Interviews with interested parties may provide further insights and may indicate whether the revised CF and the Financial Reporting Project changed preparer or user perceptions of the financial reporting regime, and whether the decision-making processes of these stakeholders may have been changed.

It was highlighted in chapter five that the full impact of the revised CF might not be ascertained until a few years following implementation from 1 January 2020. The avenue of extended research may involve extending the content analysis undertaken in the present study over a number of years following the first year of adoption of the new regime. This may provide further insights about the effect the revised CF has had on banks' financial reporting practices.

Thirdly, a cross-country comparative analysis of banks' financial reporting could be extended in an attempt to explore the implementation of the QCs from the revised CF

across the geographical regions studied. In addition, a questionnaire study may be able to provide further insights from local and international banks' on the likely application of the revised CF's QCs in different economic and cultural environments.

Fourthly, whether there might be any difference between QCs applicable to Public companies as opposed to Private companies should be researched. This thesis revealed in the literature review that The Conceptual Framework for General Purpose Financial Reporting by Public Sector Entities (2014) questioned whether the qualitative characteristics could be deemed fundamental or enhancing as to do so may, in the circumstances, place undue perceived or even unintentional weighting on a qualitative characteristic. The International Public Accounting Standards Board also questioned, as stated in the literature review, whether some qualitative characteristics applied in all cases, such as regulatory information that is not always understandable to all its users, or information so historic that it cannot be deemed 'relevant'. Researching the rationale for the differences in QCs between public and private entities, may allow for cannibalisation or cross-pollination to improve both.

Fifthly, the archaeology of the different QCs used by the IASB versus the FASB could be researched to perhaps aid further understanding of the divergence and whether there are likely areas of potential convergence as yet not implemented.

Sixthly, further group analyses, other than banks' and investment analyst societies could be chosen to widen the scope of participants to ensure research results that would encompass further stakeholders and thus have even more assurance of completeness of the QCs.

Seventh, further and fuller analysis of all comment letters that were received by the IASB before the revised CF could be undertaken. There remains the possibility that the final governmental decision may be made unilaterally by the IASB in some cases, which has particular interest groups embedded in its committees, such as that belonging to banks', who perhaps could sway those final decisions. This could lead to a review procedure embedded into the project processes which may yield that minority voices are heard and not written-out.

Eight, a full historical survey and analysis of the development of the objectives of financial reporting with particular emphasis on the concomitant qualitative characteristics proposed, from the early 1960's to date, extending the short review included in this research, could be undertaken by accounting historians. Such an investigation of events may allow for a clearer understanding of the impact of the past on the present, and hence may indicate future, qualitative characteristics.

Nine, the influence that the emerging accounting locus of control that the Far East and Malaysia are potentially able to exert on the IASB and any likely future revision of the QCs under its CF would perhaps be important to research to indicate direction of travel. It would be interesting to anticipate a move away from the present (decision-useful) objective of financial reporting towards the Far East's imperatives, and how the different culture and language use may influence future QCs of the IASB.

A tenth recommendation is that conventional Western banking and Islamic countries usury-free banking systems could be studied to ascertain whether it may be possible to provide IFRS disclosures for Islamic banking business in the absence of further supplementary financial statements (not required at present under national Islamic accounting standards), whilst maintaining attempted comparability across the different business models i.e. a universal conceptual framework for financial reporting.

An eleventh proposal by the researcher is that Hofstede's (2017, 2001) four dimensions of national culture, being, Power Distance Index, Individualism versus Collectivism, Masculinity versus Femininity, and Uncertainty Avoidance Index, as reported by Dobler and Knospe, (2016), and Jorissen et al. (2012), could be used to assess further the effect of an Island's culture on the perceived level of participation in the IASB's due process and outreach programme.

Nevertheless, despite the limitations identified and avenues for future research suggested, the current thesis represents an important contribution to the debate surrounding the implementation and impact of the QCs and the revised CF on banks' financial reporting. The current study has endeavoured to fill an existing gap in the literature by exploring:

- 1) the completeness of the QCs included in the CF;
- 2) the specific QCs and constraints which have contributed to any changes reported;
- 3) the implications of the new information for decision-useful QCs.

8.6 Conclusion

The aim of this research was to explore the completeness of the qualitative characteristics described in the revised Conceptual Framework, using Content Analysis and Foucauldian Critical Discourse Analysis. The research questions asked in Chapter One also looked at the qualitative characteristics that preparers' referred to when explaining their accounting decisions, and when they referred to the qualitative characteristics.

The theoryology, the central argument that pulls through the whole thesis, is that the typology of the Conceptual Framework's qualitative characteristics is arguably not complete, with various constraints as a minimum found to be missing. It is proposed from this research that the adjective 'decision' could be reinstated into the title describing the usefulness of the financial information, along with perhaps including the likely constraints of 'transparency', 'regulatory / supervisory', and 'materiality', Figure 8.1. It is also proposed that the IASB has a more representative working group that considers the comment letters at exposure draft stage, and that the feedback statement may be more comprehensively written to accommodate all the suggestions, whether considered further or not, unlike as at present where the IASB Project group has the last say and may not be accounting for all comments received from its members in practice or in academia, Chapter Six, 'an analysis of content of the comment letters'. Hopefully these recommendations shall be favourably considered by the International Accounting Standards Board and progressed, due to their *kairos* and *logos* from this thesis, assisting not only banks' but other corporate entities in the future when deciding on accounting policies where no Standard exists.

The results of this thesis have made an original contribution to knowledge in this field of study by exploring the completeness of the IASB's Conceptual Framework's qualitative characteristics, positioning the Foucauldian lens analysis of the power and

governmentality of the IASB such that improvements can be made from the suggestions given, and further valid constraints incorporated into the qualitative characteristics chapter on post-implementation revision. Submitting these results now to the IASB shall assist in the development and improvement of international accounting standards that use valid qualitative characteristics, set within more complete practical considerations or constraints, in order that preparers' may develop consistent accounting policies when no Standard applies to a transaction or event.

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Appendices

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Appendix A List of International Financial Reporting Standards

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List of IFRS Standards

The IFRS Foundation provides free access (through Basic registration) to the PDF files of the current year's consolidated IFRS® Standards (Part A of the Issued Standards—the Red Book), the *Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting* and IFRS Practice Statements, as well as available translations of Standards.

This section also provides high-level and non-technical summaries for the Standards.

The full Standards with all accompanying documents are available for Premium subscribers on eIFRS. For more information about what is provided for free and why, visit our unaccompanied Standards FAQ page.

Standard name

Preface to IFRS Standards

Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting

IFRS 1 First-time Adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards

IFRS 2 Share-based Payment

IFRS 3 Business Combinations

IFRS 4 Insurance Contracts

IFRS 5 Non-current Assets Held for Sale and Discontinued Operations

IFRS 6 Exploration for and Evaluation of Mineral Resources

Appendix A (Continued)

IFRS 7 Financial Instruments: Disclosures

IFRS 8 Operating Segments

IFRS 9 Financial Instruments

IFRS 10 Consolidated Financial Statements

IFRS 11 Joint Arrangements

IFRS 12 Disclosure of Interests in Other Entities

IFRS 13 Fair Value Measurement

IFRS 14 Regulatory Deferral Accounts

IFRS 15 Revenue from Contracts with Customers

IFRS 16 Leases

IFRS 17 Insurance Contracts

IAS 1 Presentation of Financial Statements

IAS 2 Inventories

IAS 7 Statement of Cash Flows

IAS 8 Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors

IAS 10 Events after the Reporting Period

IAS 11 Construction Contracts

[c://www.ifrs.org/issued-standards/list-of-standards/#](http://www.ifrs.org/issued-standards/list-of-standards/#)

Appendix A (Continued)

IAS 12 Income Taxes

IAS 16 Property, Plant and Equipment

IAS 17 Leases

IAS 18 Revenue

IAS 19 Employee Benefits

IAS 20 Accounting for Government Grants and Disclosure of Government Assistance

IAS 21 The Effects of Changes in Foreign Exchange Rates

IAS 23 Borrowing Costs

IAS 24 Related Party Disclosures

IAS 26 Accounting and Reporting by Retirement Benefit Plans

IAS 27 Separate Financial Statements

IAS 28 Investments in Associates and Joint Ventures

IAS 29 Financial Reporting in Hyperinflationary Economies

IAS 32 Financial Instruments: Presentation

IAS 33 Earnings per Share

IAS 34 Interim Financial Reporting

IAS 36 Impairment of Assets

Appendix A (Continued)

IAS 37 Provisions, Contingent Liabilities and Contingent Assets

IAS 38 Intangible Assets

IAS 39 Financial Instruments: Recognition and Measurement

IAS 40 Investment Property

IAS 41 Agriculture

Practice Statement

Practice Statement 1: Management Commentary

Practice Statement 2: Making Materiality Judgements

Disclaimer

The Board has not approved the summaries in this section, and they should not be relied on for preparing financial statements in conformity with IFRS Standards.

Appendix B IASB's policy development process

Introduction

About the IASB

The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) is an independent, private-sector body that develops and approves International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs'). The IASB operates under the oversight of the IFRS Foundation. The IASB was formed in 2001 to replace the International Accounting Standards Committee. Currently, the IASB has 14 members.

The IASB's role

Under the IFRS Foundation Constitution, the IASB from its offices in Cannon Street, London, has complete responsibility for all technical matters of the IFRS Foundation including:

- a. full discretion in developing and pursuing its technical agenda, subject to certain consultation requirements with the Trustees and the public;
- b. the preparation and issuing of IFRSs' (other than Interpretations) and exposure drafts, following the due process stipulated in the Constitution;
- c. the approval and issuing of Interpretations developed by the IFRS Interpretations Committee.

The formal objectives of the IASB, formulated in its mission statement are:

- a. to develop, in the public interest, a single set of high quality, understandable and enforceable global accounting standards that require high quality, transparent and comparable in general purpose financial statements;
- b. to promote the use and vigorous application of those standards;
- c. to work actively with national accounting standard setters to bring about convergence of national accounting standards and IFRS to high quality solutions.

Structure of the IASB

The IFRS Foundation's three-tier structure

The IFRS Foundation has a three-tier governance structure, based on an independent standard-setting Board of experts (International Accounting Standards Board), governed and overseen by Trustees from around the world (IFRS Foundation Trustees) who in turn are accountable to a monitoring board of public authorities (IFRS Foundation Monitoring Board).

The IFRS Advisory Council provides advice and counsel to the Trustees and the Board, whilst the Board also consults extensively with a range of other standing advisory bodies and consultative groups.

Table B. 1 Structure of IFRS Foundation

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Public accountability

Monitoring Board

The Monitoring Board is a group of capital market authorities and provides a formal link between the Trustees and public authorities in order to enhance the public accountability of the IFRS Foundation

The Monitoring Board was created in January 2009 with the aim of 'providing a formal link between the Trustees and public authorities' in order to enhance the public accountability of the IFRS Foundation.

The Monitoring Board's main responsibilities are to ensure that the Trustees continue to discharge their duties as defined by the IFRS Foundation Constitution, as well as approving the appointment or reappointment of Trustees. The Monitoring Board meets the Trustees at least once a year, or more often if appropriate.

The Monitoring Board consists of capital markets authorities responsible for setting the form and content of financial reporting. Through the Monitoring Board, securities regulators that allow or require the use of IFRS in their jurisdictions will be able to more effectively carry out their mandates regarding investor protection, market integrity, and capital formation.

The current members of the Monitoring Board are representatives of the Board and the Growth and Emerging Markets Committee of the International Organisation of Securities Commissions (IOSCO), the European Commission (EC), Financial Services Agency of Japan (JFSA), US Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), Brazilian Securities Commission (CVM), Financial Services Commission of Korea (FSC), and Ministry of Finance of the People's Republic of China (China MOF). The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision participates in the Monitoring Board as an observer.

The Monitoring Board is currently chaired by Jean-Paul Servais, Vice-Chair of the IOSCO Board and Chairman of the Financial Services and Markets Authority of Belgium.

The Monitoring Board carried out an independent review of the governance framework of the Monitoring Board and the IFRS Foundation in 2010-2011. The governance review allowed the Monitoring Board to review, inter alia, its own structure, whether it provides appropriate representation for relevant authorities and whether the Foundation's current governance structure functions effectively.

The Monitoring Board published the results of its Governance review in February 2012, and identified a number of enhancements to the governance framework and included an action plan for their implementation. The Monitoring Board decided to expand its membership to include additional authorities, primarily from major emerging markets (a maximum of four) and also to establish a mechanism to allocate two rotating seats in consultation with IOSCO. The Monitoring Board also introduced a periodic evaluation and assessments process for existing members every three years, beginning in 2013, against specified criteria for membership.

The Monitoring Board developed the IFRS Foundation Monitoring Board work plan and intends to update the plan periodically.

Governance

Trustees of the IFRS Foundation

The Trustees of the IFRS Foundation are responsible for the governance and oversight of the International Accounting Standards Board, including the Constitution and due process for the development of the accounting standards.

The Trustees are not involved in any technical matters relating to IFRS standards. This responsibility rests solely with the Board. The Trustees are accountable to the Monitoring Board (see below), a body of publicly accountable market authorities.

Trustees are appointed for a renewable term of three years. Each Trustee is expected to have an understanding of, and be sensitive to, international issues relevant to the success of an international organisation responsible for the development of high-quality global accounting standards for use in the world's capital markets and by other users.

Michel Prada was appointed Chairman of the IFRS Foundation Trustees, effective 1 January 2012, and his second term ran until 31 December 2017. He will remain in position until a successor is in his place.

Trustee responsibility

The Trustees' responsibilities include, but are not limited to:

- a. appointing members of the Board, the IFRS Interpretations Committee and the IFRS Advisory Council;
- b. establishing and amending the operating procedures, consultative arrangements and due process for the Board, the Interpretations Committee and the Advisory Council;
- c. reviewing annually the strategy of the Board and assessing its effectiveness; and
- d. ensure the financing of the IFRS Foundation and approve annually its budget.

In exercising their governance responsibilities, the Trustees may reconsider or amend the Board's due process or recommend, for example, improvements to the Board's outreach activities. In addition, the constitution requires the Trustees to undertake a formal, public review of the structure of the IFRS Foundation, its governance arrangements and its effectiveness in fulfilling the organisation's objectives every five years.

The Trustees are accountable to a Monitoring Board of public authorities. The Trustees' reports to the Monitoring Board are available on the Trustees' meeting pages.

Trustee distribution

The IFRS Foundation states that 'the mix of Trustees shall broadly reflect the world's capital markets and diversity of geographical and professional backgrounds'. To reflect this and ensure a broad international basis, six of the Trustees must be selected from the Asia/Oceania region, six from Europe, six from the Americas, one from Africa and three can be from any area, subject to maintaining overall geographical balance.

Africa

- a. Wiseman Nkuhlu, South Africa

Asia/Oceania

- b. Teresa Ko, Hong Kong
- c. Joji Okada, Japan
- d. Vinod Rai, India
- e. Lynn Wood, Australia
- f. Guangyao Zhu, China

Europe

- g. Else Bos, the Netherlands
- h. Colette Bowe, UK
- i. Werner Brandt, Germany
- j. Ross McInnes, France
- k. Michel Prada, France (Chair)
- l. Lucrezia Reichlin, Italy

The Americas

- m. Guillermo Babatz, Mexico
- n. Alan Beller, USA
- o. Sheila Fraser, Canada

- p. Larry Leva, USA
- q. Maria Helena Santana, Brazil
- r. Kurt Schacht, USA

Appointed from any area

- s. Dr Abdulrahman Al-Humaid, Saudi Arabia
- t. Michel Madelain, France
- u. Dr Takafumi Sato, Japan

Due Process Oversight Committee (DPOC)

The Trustees of the IFRS Foundation have a committee, the DPOC, which is responsible for overseeing the due process procedures of the Board and its Interpretations Committee.

As stated in the Board and IFRS Interpretations Committee Due Process Handbook, the DPOC is responsible for:

- a. reviewing regularly, and in a timely manner, together with the Board and the IFRS Foundation staff, the due process activities of the standard-setting activities of the Board;
- b. reviewing, and proposing updates to, the Due Process Handbook that relate to the development and review of standards, Interpretations and the IFRS Taxonomy so as to ensure that the Board procedures are best practice;
- c. reviewing the composition of the Board's consultative groups to ensure an appropriate balance of perspectives and monitoring the effectiveness of those groups;
- d. responding to correspondence from third parties about due process matters, in collaboration with the Director for Trustee Activities and the technical staff;
- e. monitoring the effectiveness of the IFRS Advisory Council (Advisory Council), the Interpretations Committee and other bodies of the IFRS Foundation relevant to its standard-setting activities; and

- f. making recommendations to the Trustees about constitutional changes related to the composition of committees that are integral to due process, as appropriate.

Independent standard-setting

International Accounting Standards Board

The International Accounting Standards Board (Board) is the independent standard-setting body of the IFRS Foundation.

The Board is an independent group of experts with an appropriate mix of recent practical experience in setting accounting standards, in preparing, auditing, or using financial reports, and in accounting education. Broad geographical diversity is also required. The IFRS Foundation Constitution outlines the full criteria for the composition of the Board, and the geographical allocation can be seen on the individual profiles.

Board members are responsible for the development and publication of IFRS standards, including the IFRS for SMEs Standard. The Board is also responsible for approving Interpretations of IFRS standards as developed by the IFRS Interpretations Committee (formerly IFRIC).

Members are appointed by the Trustees of the IFRS Foundation through an open and rigorous process that includes advertising vacancies and consulting relevant organisations.

The IASB states that:

‘We follow a thorough, transparent and participatory due process when we issue an IFRS Standard or an IFRIC Interpretation that helps companies better implement our standards. Our standard-setting entails:

- a. public Board meetings broadcast live from our London office;

- b. agenda papers that inform the Board's deliberations;
- c. discussion and decision summaries that are made available after meetings;
and
- d. comment letters received on our consultation documents.

All IFRS due-process documents are posted online. The full process is described in detail in our Due Process Handbook.'

Steps in the standard-setting process

Agenda consultation

Every five years, the Board conducts a comprehensive review and consultation to define international standard-setting priorities and develop its project work plan.

The Board can also add topics to its work plan if necessary between agenda consultations. This can include topics following Post-implementation Reviews of Standards; the IFRS Interpretations Committee may also request the Board review an issue.

Research programme

The Board begins most projects with research, explores the issues, identifies possible solutions and decides whether standard-setting is required. The Board then sets out their ideas in a discussion paper and seeks public comment.

If the Board finds sufficient evidence that an accounting problem exists, the problem is sufficiently important to warrant changing a Standard or issuing a new one and a practical solution can be found, they begin standard-setting.

Standard-setting programme

If the Board decides to amend a Standard or issue a new one, they generally review the research, including comments on the discussion paper, and propose amendments or standards to resolve issues identified through research and consultation.

Proposals for a new Standard or an amendment to a Standard are published in an exposure draft for public consultation. To gather additional evidence, members of the Board and IFRS Foundation technical staff consult with a range of stakeholders from all over the world.

The Board analyses feedback and refines proposals before the new Standard, or an amendment to a Standard, is issued.

Maintenance programme

Once a standard is issued, the Board supports implementation and maintenance of the standards.

This process includes consulting on the implementation of a new or amended standard to identify any implementation problems that may need to be addressed. If issues arise, the IFRS Interpretations Committee may decide to create an IFRIC Interpretation of the Standard or recommend a narrow-scope amendment. Such amendments follow the Board's normal due process.

Post-implementation Reviews

After a new Standard has been in use for a few years, the Board carries out research through a Post-implementation Review to assess whether the Standard is achieving its objective and, if not, whether any amendments should be considered. As a result of the Post-implementation Review, the Board may start a new research project.

IFRS Advisory Council

The IFRS Advisory Council provides a formal vehicle for further groups and individuals with diverse geographic and functional backgrounds to give advice to the Board and,

at times, to advise the Trustees. It comprises about fifty members and meets at least three times a year. It is consulted by the IASB on all major projects and its meetings are open to the public. It advises the IASB on prioritisation of its work and on the implications of proposed standards for users' and preparers' of financial statements.

IFRS Interpretations Committee

The interpretative body of the International Accounting Standards Board (Board), which works with the Board in supporting the application of IFRS standards. It deals with newly identified financial reporting issues not specifically addressed in IFRSs', or issues where unsatisfactory or conflicting interpretations have developed, or seem likely to develop. (Reference: <https://www.ifrs.org/about-us/our-structure/>)

Due process steps

As part of the lengthy process of issuing new or updated IFRS standards, the International Accounting Standards Board invites comments from a wide variety of sources. When it issues a discussion paper or exposure draft, it gets feedback from preparers, national standard-setters and accounting institutes, among others.

One of the key bodies involved in this discussion is the Global Preparers Forum (GPF), an IFRS consultative group whose members have considerable practical experience in financial reporting. It's members give valuable feedback into concepts and proposals that the IASB is developing and offer advice on the practical implications of the intended proposals for the preparers of financial statements. The individuals involved in the forum come from a variety of industries across many nations. The forum meets three times a year.

Discussion paper

The publication of a discussion document (for example a discussion paper, request for information, or a research paper) is optional per the Constitution s.37(b). A discussion paper's publication requires a simple majority of IASB members, by way of a ballot.

Exposure draft

Once the IASB has formally decided to add a project to its agenda, it proceeds to the development of an exposure draft. The exposure draft is issued for public consultation and the IASB may also undertake additional outreach activities such as meetings, discussion forums, webcasts and podcasts and roundtable meetings.

Re-deliberations and finalisation of the Standard

After the publication of an exposure draft, the IASB proceed to consider constituent feedback from the consultative process. In some cases, the IASB may decide to re-expose proposals before proceeding to a finalised pronouncement. Once deliberations have been finalised, the IASB's technical staff will prepare the final standard for balloting and voting on by the Board.

The process may also include the issue of a 'review draft' of the final pronouncement prior to it being finalised. These documents are not part of formal due process but have the purpose of allowing a 'fatal flaw' review.

The publication of a Standard requires a supermajority of IASB members, by way of ballot (requires 9 out of 15 or fewer members, or 10 out of 16 members).

Post implementation review

The IASB must conduct a post-implementation review of each new Standard or major amendment, usually after they have been applied for around two years. This means that the post-implementation review process shall commence around 2.5-3 years after the effective date of the pronouncement, a triannual review, but may be deferred in some cases. The post-implementation review process can also be initiated in other circumstances such as regulatory changes or concerns raised by other parties.

<https://www.ifrs.org/about-us/how-we-set-standards/>

The Due Process Handbook for the IASB and IFRS Interpretations Committee (IASCF, 2013) separates the steps into mandatory and non-mandatory:

Mandatory steps, summarised:

- a. Debate
- b. Draft exposed for public comment (Exposure Draft)
- c. Comment letters considered
- d. Consideration of whether the proposals should be exposed again
- e. Report to the Advisory Council
- f. Ratification of the interpretation by the IASB

Non-mandatory steps, summarised, by IASCF include:

- a. Discussion document (Discussion Paper), before an Exposure Draft is developed
- b. Consultative groups or specialist advisory groups
- c. Public hearings
- d. Fieldwork.

IASB's publication of its revised Conceptual Framework

The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) published its revised 'Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting' on 26 March 2018. Included are revised definitions of an asset and a liability as well as new guidance on measurement and derecognition, presentation and disclosure. The new Conceptual Framework does not constitute a substantial revision of the document as was originally intended when the project was first taken up in 2004. Instead the IASB focused on topics that were not yet covered or that showed obvious shortcomings that needed to be dealt with.

Background to the Conceptual Framework

The Conceptual Framework had been left largely unchanged since its inception in 1989. In 2004, the IASB and the FASB decided to review and revise the Conceptual Framework, however, changed priorities and the slow progress in the project led to the project being abandoned in 2010 after only Phase A (objectives and qualitative characteristics) of the original joint project had been finalised and introduced into the existing framework as chapters one and three in September 2010. Phase D saw the publication of a discussion paper and an exposure draft but was never finalised. The Boards' discussed Phases B and C (elements, recognition and measurement) quite extensively without any consultation document ever being issued, and Phases E (presentation and disclosure) to H (other issues) largely remained untouched.

During the 2011 agenda consultation many participants called for the IASB to reactivate and finalise the Conceptual Framework project given the multitude of open conceptual issues it is facing in many of its current projects. As a result, the IASB officially added the project to its agenda again in September 2012, this time as an IASB-only project and no longer aimed at a substantial revision of the framework but focused on those topics that are not yet covered (e.g. presentation and disclosure) or that show obvious shortcomings that need to be dealt with. As a first step, a Discussion Paper covering all aspects of the framework project was published in July 2013, followed by a comprehensive Exposure Draft in May 2015.

Table B. 2 History of the Conceptual Framework

April 1989	<i>Framework for the Preparation and Presentation of Financial Statements</i> (the Framework) was approved by the IASC Board
July 1989	Framework was published
April 2001	Framework adopted by the IASB.
September 2010	<i>Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting 2010</i> approved by the IASB
July 2013	<i>Discussion Paper</i>
May 2015	<i>Exposure Draft</i>
March 2018	<i>Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting 2018</i> (the Framework) published

Reference: Adapted from IASPlus website, IASPlus (2019b), Standards, Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting 2018. Available: <https://www.iasplus.com/en/standards/other/framework> [Accessed: 8 September 2019].

Approach to revising the Conceptual Framework

In revising the CF, the IASB sought a balance between providing high-level concepts and providing enough detail for the CF to be useful to the IASB and others. The IASB views the CF as a practical tool to help it develop standards. Hence, the CF includes concepts that help the IASB develop standards, and also discusses the factors the IASB needs to consider in making judgements when application of the concepts does not lead to a single answer.

Main changes

The revised CF introduces the following main improvements:

Table B. 3 Main improvements to revised Conceptual Framework

New	
Measurement	concepts on measurement, including factors to be considered when selecting a measurement basis
Presentation and disclosure	concepts on presentation and disclosure, including when to classify income and expenses in other comprehensive income
Derecognition	guidance on when assets and liabilities are removed from financial statements
Updated	
Definitions	definitions of an asset and a liability
Recognition	Criteria for including assets and liabilities in financial statements
Clarified	
Prudence	
Stewardship	
Measurement uncertainty	
Substance over form	

Available: <https://www.ifrs.org/-/media/project/conceptual-framework/fact-sheet-project-summary-and-feedback-statement/conceptual-framework-project-summary.pdf?la=en&hash=654CC1DE384D992926C9DC50FD2AF49C18A489C6>

[Accessed 8 September 2019]

The key content of each of the first three chapters of the revised CF is summarised below:

‘Status and purpose of the *Conceptual Framework*. The first section notes that the *Conceptual Framework*’s purpose is to assist the IASB in developing and revising IFRSs that are based on consistent concepts, to help preparers to develop consistent accounting policies for areas that are not covered by a standard or where there is choice of accounting policy, and to assist all parties to understand and interpret IFRS. It maintains that the framework does not override any specific IFRS. Should the IASB decide to issue a new or revised pronouncement that is in conflict with the framework, the IASB will highlight the fact and explain the reasons for the departure in the basis for conclusions.

Chapter 1 - The objective of general purpose financial reporting. This is the first of the two chapters that were finalised as part of the joint project with the FASB in 2010, so there are only limited changes. The chapter notes that the objective of general purpose financial reporting is to provide financial information about the reporting entity that is useful to existing and potential investors, lenders and other creditors in making decisions relating to providing resources to the entity. This is identified as information about the entity’s economic resources and the claims against the reporting entity as well as information about the effects of transactions and other events that change a reporting entity’s economic resources and claims. The chapter newly stresses that information can also help users to assess management’s stewardship of the entity’s economic resources.

Chapter 2 - Qualitative characteristics of useful financial information.

This is the second of the two chapters that were finalised as part of the joint project with the FASB in 2010 (published as chapter 3 in the 2010 Conceptual Framework). Again, changes are limited. The chapter explains the fundamental qualitative characteristics ('relevance' and 'faithful representation') and the enhancing qualitative characteristics ('comparability', 'verifiability', 'timeliness', and 'understandability') of useful financial information and notes the cost constraint. Materiality is noted as an entity-specific aspect of 'relevance'. The chapter reintroduces an explicit reference to the notion of 'prudence' and states that the exercise of 'prudence' supports 'neutrality'. 'Prudence' is defined as the exercise of caution when making judgements under conditions of uncertainty. New is also a clarification that 'faithful representation' means representation of the substance of an economic phenomenon instead of representation of its legal form only.'

Ref: <https://www.iasplus.com/en/news/2018/03/cf>

'Prudence' does not allow for overstatement or understatement of assets, liabilities, income or expenses. 'Neutrality', a tenant of 'faithful representation' along with 'complete' and 'free from error', is supported by the exercise of 'prudence'.

'Measurement uncertainty' does not prevent information from being useful. However, in some cases the most relevant information may have such a high level of 'measurement uncertainty' that the most useful information is information that is slightly less 'relevant' but is subject to lower 'measurement uncertainty'.

Amendments were also made to IFRSs' and IASs' which quote from the Conceptual Framework indicating which version of the framework they are referencing to (the IASC framework adopted by the IASB in 2001, the IASB framework of 2010, or the new revised framework of 2018), or to indicate that definitions in the standard have not been updated with the new definitions developed in the revised Conceptual Framework.

The amendments, where they actually are updates, are effective for annual reporting periods beginning on or after 1 January 2020, with earlier application permitted. The revised CF is however effective immediately for the IASB and the IFRS Interpretations Committee.

The IASB used the Accounting Standard Advisory Forum (ASAF) as its consultative group for the Conceptual Framework project. ASAF is an advisory group to the Board. It comprises national accounting standard-setters and regional bodies with an interest in financial reporting. The ASAF tested their proposals partly during discussions and case-studies held at the World Standard-setters Conference in 2016.

Even after some stakeholder feedback in the CF project suggested otherwise, the Board decreed or concluded itself that it could depart from aspects of the CF to meet the objectives of financial reporting, providing it explained the departure in the Standard's 'Basis for Conclusions'.

Some stakeholders also expressed a concern that the general approach in the 2015 Exposure Draft of using fundamental QCs of 'relevance' and 'faithful representation' as the basis for recognition, measurement and presentation decisions would not provide enough direction for the Board. They thought this approach was too abstract and subjective. The Board concluded that more rigid criteria would not improve its ability to set standards that result in useful information.

Appendix C Other Foucauldian concepts, relative to the International Accounting Standards Board.

Problematization

The history of thought is the analysis of the way an unproblematic field of experience, or a set of practices, which were accepted without question, which were familiar and 'silent', becomes a problem, and induces a crisis.

'Parrhesia' or free thought, is a significant concept for Foucault, where the relation between various socio-cultural institutions, concepts, meanings, genres and practices is rethought and negotiated in a moment of crisis. In place of those methods of scholarship and research (historical, philosophical, psychoanalytical, linguistic) that seek to identify 'formal structures with universal value', Foucault focuses on the events that have led us to constitute ourselves and to recognise ourselves as subjects of what we are doing, thinking, saying (Foucault, 1984b).

Problematization is a critical technique whereby the relation between various socio-cultural institutions, concepts, meanings, genres and practices is rethought and negotiated in a moment of crisis. A 'problematic field of experience' is a cultural space where thought and meaning temporarily have become unmoored. Problematization can be seen as an active part of the Foucauldian project, to identify problems, inconsistencies and difficulties within ideas, beliefs, and practices (Gillies, 2013). Using problematization, tools can be developed to challenge the current practice of the IASB and how the qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information to use in financial reporting have been derived.

Critique

Critique and critical inquiry allow a space to be opened up by the testing of reality in order to evaluate the possibility and desirability of change, and to determine the forms it shall take. Like Nietzsche (Foucault, 1984a), Foucault emphasised the importance of critique, which he understood both in terms of an investigation into what we are (how we think, what we value, how we understand ourselves, how we treat others)

and as a concern with thinking what else we might be (how we could be different from ourselves). Foucault's own work can be understood within this sensibility of critique, which is aimed at challenging the forces that govern us, not only in the broad political sense but also in terms of the forms of language, apparatuses of power and other forces that shape how we think and act.

In order for the state (or in our case the IASB) to gain the maximum benefit from resources, people had to be subjected to techniques that regulated and orientated thinking and general behaviour. This arises in a qualified accountant's world by having to pass exams and gain practical experience, all under the jurisdiction of a recognised professional accounting body (Evans, Lusher and Day, 2019a). This qualification and necessary practical experience hurdle enabled orientation of accountants' thinking to be channelled to herd-like group thinking.

Foucault (1997) argues that just as the imperative to govern, the arts and techniques associated with and developed in accordance with it, were colonising socio-cultural fields, there was also a response that was highly contrary; he refers to this as extensive questions and considerations regarding 'how not to be governed'. There was both the attitude of distrust and a concomitant determination to find ways and techniques of avoiding or limiting governing, which Foucault identifies as a precursor to what he refers to as the modern critical sensibility. This modern critical sensibility (of the IASB for example) can arguably be considered to be missing from modern professional accountants, and is reflected upon later in the findings from the interviews held with preparers' and users', both professional accountants, and from the earlier comment letters written in to the IASB by the banks' at the time of the exposure draft to the Conceptual Framework.

Critical inquiry, as in 'Foucault's trident' referred to in Gillies (2013, p. 22), is directed at the limitations of thought with the aim of producing freedom from the 'limits of ourselves'. The space opened up by critical inquiry must always 'put itself to the test of reality, both to grasp the points where change is possible and desirable, and to determine the precise form this change should take'. In the accounting sphere, critique can be seen as a professional responsibility to be sceptical and questioning of beliefs and assumption, of policy and practice such as that applicable to the Conceptual Framework's qualitative characteristics, whether at the level of the individual

accountant, or the institution (in this case banks', national accounting bodies or even transnational government bodies such as the IASB itself (adapted from Gillies (2013, p. 18), referencing Foucault, 2002b, p. 456).

Scepticism

The principal tools that Foucault brings to accounting discourse are scepticism, critique and problematisation, 'Foucault's trident'.

By scepticism (Veyne, 2013, p. 1) is meant:

'the expression and application of doubt as to the value of stated aims, objectives, and goals, doubt as to the effectiveness of chosen means, doubt as to the accuracy and veracity of claims, doubt as to the declared motivations, interests and purposes of relevant persons, doubt as to the value and coherence of chosen beliefs and concepts, doubt as to the nature and status of knowledge, and doubt as to the nature of reality'.

Scepticism is a suspension of judgement, a weighing of evidence both micro and macro. Scepticism is affected by unconscious bias, depending on ideology. Scepticism allows one to ask critical questions of stakeholders, their motives and values, and how this is translated into the IASB's policy documents.

A complaint made against Foucault is that he is nihilistic, that we are powerless against the forces of sceptical discourse as it is omnipresent, from birth to death. There becomes no ideal to work towards, no vision, and that the best we can do is to challenge and re-challenge. This challenge process is automatically built into the Conceptual Framework Project's Standard setting approach, with its 'Requests for Information', Discussion papers, Exposure Drafts, and Post Implementation Review. Due process is also facilitated by more informal methods such as informal meetings with IASB members and staff (Jorissen et al., 2012), webinars, live webcasts and online surveys (Huian, 2013). Nevertheless, the IASB's approach continues to receive criticism by academics, users, think tanks and governments (Wingard, Bosman and Amisi, 2016; Pelger and Spiess, 2017), and there is little evidence that the above

participation extends beyond certain banking and financial market interests, which by normal standards should allow the legitimacy of the IASB as a transnational policy-maker to be challenged (Quack, 2010). The IASB for its part has tried to re-institute organisational and governance legitimacy through its monitoring board (Figure 1.6) and commitments to due process, masking their focus on banking and capital markets, while continuing to be supported by the World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF) as transnational accounting policymakers (Carter and Warren, 2018).

Textualism

Foucault insisted in 'What is Enlightenment' in volume 1 of *The Essential Works of Michel Foucault: Ethics* p. 318, that history 'must turn away from all projects that claim to be global.' Genealogy would not aspire to objectivity or completeness, however would instead accept that it could never be more than a 'partial and local inquiry.' Foucault attacked traditional historians for their deceptions, noting that they invariably took 'unusual pains to erase the elements in their work which reveal their grounding in a particular time and place.' This method was self-consciously 'slanted, being a deliberate appraisal, affirmation, or negation' of the past. What Foucault sought in his history of systems of thought was not truth, but problematics; his inquiries were designed to expose the way particular discourses ordered and constructed the 'reality' of the past.

In Foucault's book entitled *Birth of the Clinic*, Foucault talks about language changing between periods, for example, a patient used to go to a building called a clinic, while now the building is called a hospital. So too is the idea that QCs stated in the 1970's may, over the fifty-year period to date, have changed as language changes. Indeed, the South African Institute of Chartered Accountants (SAICA) had issued its own conceptual framework statement called 'AC000, Framework for the preparation of financial statements' in the late 1970's. South Africa went on to adopt the Conceptual Framework issued by the IASC in 1989. Through textualism, practical considerations that were considered by SAICA's AC000 such as 'materiality', 'substance over form', and 'prudence', were found to be either missing from the IASC's Conceptual Framework, or under-emphasised.

Appendix D The qualitative interview – a theoretical background

The qualitative research interview, undertaken as the first strand of this research, attempts to understand the world from the participants' point of view, finding out the meaning of their experiences, uncovering their lived world for scientific explanations. 'Interviewing is an active process where interviewer and interviewee through their relationship produce knowledge' (Brinkmann and Kvale, 2015, p. 232). Qualitative interviews have the potential of being both doxastic and epistemic, that is, they can elicit important descriptions and narratives (doxa), while also producing episteme, knowledge that has been justified discursively. 'Discursive research on interviews clearly demonstrates that both parties are equally implicated in meaning making and participate jointly as active agents and agenda setters.' Gubrium et al. (2012, p. 410).

Many decisions have to be made on the spot during interviewing, requiring a high level of skill on behalf of the interviewer. The interviewer needs to be knowledgeable about the interview topic and familiar, specifically for this study, with the accounting policy options available, as well as having an understanding conceptually of producing knowledge through conversation. In this research a Socratic way of interviewing was conducted, proposing a bias towards doxastic interviewing as opposed to epistemic interviewing, as the best way to conduct the interviews. Interview statements can be ambiguous and contradictory, and the findings may not be intersubjectively reproducible because of the interviewees varying knowledge and sensitivity to the interview topic. Indeed, Foucault, as a postmodernist, believed that the qualitative interview is a 'technology of the self', a reflection upon one's experiences.

The results of an interview study shall be 'complete' if new data from further interviews reveal no new findings, with the common number of interviews tending to be around fifteen plus or minus ten (Brinkmann and Kvale, 2015). The sample size used in qualitative research methods is often smaller than that used in quantitative research methods, because an in-depth understanding is being garnered, with a focus on heterogeneities in meaning, more inductive and emergent in its process. Saturation, the point at which the data collection process no longer offers any new or relevant data, is most important (Mason, 2010).

Appendix E Participant information sheet

Appendix E Participant information sheet (PIS) (Version no.1.0, 20 February 2018, amended post-viva 17 December 2019 to reflect new title of thesis)

Study Title:

An exploration around completeness of the International Accounting Standards Board's qualitative characteristics.

Criteria for your inclusion:

You are invited to take part in the research study above because you fall into the 'Inclusion Criteria' of being a preparer or, alternatively, a user of an international bank's annual report prepared under the IASB's IFRS standards.

Study Aims:

The completeness of the IASB's revised Conceptual Framework's qualitative characteristics for decision-useful financial information is to be assessed. The information gained from this research shall be used to make recommendations for greater validity and rigour concerning the qualitative characteristics. It shall offer insights into the experiences of those preparers of financial information, specifically banks' annual reports, who need to concern themselves with the qualitative characteristics in the revised conceptual framework, as well as users of banks' annual reports. The results of the study may also lead onto further studies into the completeness, grouping and ranking of the qualitative characteristics.

What will my participation involve?

You will be asked to answer questions in a semi-structured interview for approximately 30 minutes concerning your experience and opinion of the revised qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information. As it is not a knowledge test, you shall be provided with:

1. a diagram of the revised qualitative characteristics and a table of their meanings as per the conceptual framework;
2. the draft chapter two of the revised Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting, due for publication by March 2018, entitled 'Qualitative Characteristics of Useful Financial Information',
3. chapter two of the Exposure Draft 2015/3, Basis for Conclusions, dated May 2015 'Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting', entitled 'Qualitative Characteristics of Useful Financial Information', ten pages;
4. a list of IFRS standards, their numbers and description.

The semi-structured interview will be audio-recorded, and then transcribed onto a computer by the researcher himself, and consent will be required from you for both the interview and the audio recording.

Risks:

There are no risks known to the researcher, as your confidentiality and anonymity are assured, and no distress is foreseen.

Benefits:

The information obtained from the study shall help to increase the understanding of the revised qualitative characteristics and their rigour by preparers and users of banks' annual reports. If generally accepted characteristics are found to be omitted or misinterpreted, then a revised chapter in the international Conceptual Framework on 'The qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information' could be formulated by the researcher, and submitted to the IASB for due consideration and possible implementation internationally. The IASB may possibly include and authorise the use of the QCs found to be omitted or misinterpreted within the IASB's 2018 revision of the Conceptual Framework document, after its post implementation review in a few years' time.

Will I get paid for my involvement?

There are no expense reimbursements or incentives available for your participation. Your participation is entirely voluntary.

At the end of the research I shall write a report and the results may be published in peer reviewed academic or professional journals and conference presentations. I shall provide a written summary of my overall findings to you as soon as possible, near to the time of submission of my report to the university.

Confidentiality:

In-depth interview transcripts made by the researcher, and audio recording and audio recording transcripts, will be kept in a fireproof locked filing cabinet, again by the researcher, who is the only key holder. The cabinet will be kept locked at all times within the researcher's place of employment. All computer documents will be stored, encrypted, on a password protected computer in password protected files.

Supervisors of the Professional Doctorate program shall have access to the anonymised confidential data. Such supervisors are entrusted by the University to keep such anonymised data accessed confidential and secret unless appropriate written permission is obtained from you. The university retains the anonymised data until disposed of securely after six years.

Your response will be anonymised and treated with confidentiality. Anyone who takes part in the research will be identified only by code numbers, and all identifying information, such as your organisation or the department to which you belong, will be removed. For example, your Consent Form will not be attached to your anonymised data. You can request a copy of your interview and audio recording transcripts if you wish. Your interview will be analysed by myself.

Do I have to take part?

No. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part.

Consent:

Your consent will be required for both the interview and the audio recording of the interview. Taking part in the study is entirely voluntary and you are free to withdraw from the whole study at any time without giving any reason and without any penalty. Both your interview transcript and audio recording and audio recording transcripts will be destroyed immediately on withdrawal.

Approval:

The study has been approved by the University of the West of Scotland Research Ethics Committee.

Contact details for Further Information:

If you have any questions or require more information about this study, please contact the researcher using the following contact details:

Gareth Evans

Professional Doctorate Candidate
University of the West of Scotland

[Redacted contact details]

Personal details withheld.

If you wish to make a complaint about the conduct of the study, you can contact my Director of Studies at the University of the West of Scotland for further advice and information using the details below:

Dr Joanne Lusher

Senior Lecturer in Post Graduate Studies
School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery
University of the West of Scotland
London Campus

[Redacted contact details]

Personal details withheld.

Thank you for reading this information sheet and for considering taking part in this research.

Appendix F Consent form

Appendix F Consent form (Version 1.0 20 February 2018, amended post-viva 17 December 2019 to reflect new title of thesis)

Study Number: 4325

Participant Identification Number for this trial:

CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: An exploration around completeness of the International Accounting Standards Board's qualitative characteristics.

Name of Researcher: Gareth Christopher Evans

Please initial box

- 1 I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
- 2 I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.
- 3 I understand that my interview will be audio recorded and transcribed by the researcher, and I give permission for both the interview and the audio recording of the interview. If I withdraw, my interview transcript, audio recording and audio recording transcript will be destroyed immediately.
- 4 I understand that sections of my anonymised interview notes or audio recordings and transcripts may be looked at by responsible members of the research team from the University of the West of Scotland or from regulatory authorities where it is relevant to my taking part in this research. I give permission for these individuals to have access to my anonymised data.
- 5 I understand that the transcribed interview notes and audio recording will be kept secret and destroyed by the university after six years.
- 6 I agree to take part in the above study, and I have obtained all necessary internal permissions to do so.

Name of Participant:

Signature:

Date:

Name of person taking consent (if different from researcher):

Signature:

Date:

Name of researcher: Gareth Christopher Evans

Signature:

Date:

1 copy for participant and 1 for researcher

Appendix G ESRC's six key principles of ethical research juxtapositioned against ACCA's Code of Ethics and Conduct (2011)

Principle 1: Voluntary

Research participants should take part voluntarily, free from any coercion or undue influence, and their rights, dignity and (when possible) autonomy should be respected and appropriately protected.

Professional behaviour – Members shall comply with relevant laws and regulations and shall avoid any action that may discredit the profession. The ACCA Rulebook goes further, and states that members shall 'behave with courtesy and consideration' towards all with whom they come into contact in a professional capacity.

Principle 2: Worthwhile and Non-maleficence

Research should be worthwhile and provide value that outweighs any risk or harm. Researchers should aim to maximise the benefit of the research and minimise potential risk of harm to participants and researchers. All potential risk and harm should be mitigated by robust precautions.

Professional competence and due care – Members have a continuing duty 'to maintain professional knowledge and skill at a level required to ensure that clients or employers receive competent professional service'. Members shall 'act diligently in accordance with applicable technical and professional standards when providing professional services'.

Principle 3: Information (about purpose, intended use, and risks and benefits)

Research staff and participants should be given appropriate information about the purpose, methods and intended uses of the research, what their participation in the research entails and what risks and benefits, if any, are involved.

Professional behaviour – Members shall comply with relevant laws and regulations and shall avoid any action that may discredit the profession. The ACCA Rulebook goes further, and states that members shall 'behave with courtesy and consideration' towards all with whom they come into contact in a professional capacity.

Principle 4: Anonymity and Confidentiality

Individual research participant and group preferences regarding anonymity should be respected and participant requirements concerning the confidential nature of information and personal data should be respected.

Confidentiality – *Members shall respect the confidentiality of information ‘acquired as a result of professional and business relationships’, and shall not disclose any such information to third parties ‘without proper and specific authority or unless there is a legal or professional right or duty to disclose’. Similarly, confidential information acquired as a result of professional and business relationships shall not be used to the personal advantage of members or third parties.*

Principle 5: Integrity

Research should be designed, reviewed and undertaken to ensure recognised standards of integrity are met, and quality and transparency are assured.

Integrity – *Members shall be ‘straightforward and honest in all professional and business relationships.’ The ACCA Rulebook (and the IESBA Code) goes on to state that integrity implies not merely honesty, but fair dealing and truthfulness.*

Principle 6: Independence

The independence of research should be clear, and any conflicts of interest or partiality should be explicit.

Objectivity – *Members shall not allow bias, conflicts of interest or the undue influence of others to compromise their professional or business judgement.*

Appendix H Ethical issues and challenges

Ethical issues and challenges	How the researcher might overcome the challenges
<p>Power relationships</p> <p>In-depth interviews with ‘Preparers’ and ‘Users’</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommendations received leading to a sense of obligation on the particular ‘Preparer’ or ‘User’ to participate • Reimbursement of any participation costs 	<p>In-depth interviews with ‘Preparers’ and ‘Users’</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identities of other ‘Preparers’ and ‘Users’ not revealed • Not working directly with any of the ‘Preparers’ and ‘Users’ • Abiding by Codes such as The Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC), and the ACCA Rulebook • No reimbursement considered necessary if Researcher does all the travelling
<p>Informed consent</p> <p>In-depth interviews with ‘Preparers’ and ‘Users’</p>	<p>In-depth interviews with ‘Preparers’ and ‘Users’</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of an Information Sheet and a Consent form for each individual, and records kept
<p>Positionality with respect to roles</p> <p>In-depth interviews with ‘Preparers’ and ‘Users’</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Homogeneity? • Who in the research team shall collect and handle data? 	<p>In-depth interviews with ‘Preparers’ and ‘Users’</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure ‘Preparers’ and ‘Users’ are not all members of the same professional accounting body • Use anonymisation procedures • Register research with Data Protection Officer

<p>Positionality with respect to permission</p> <p>In-depth interviews with 'Preparers' and 'Users'</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional ethics code that needs to be followed; • Other codes such as UK Research Integrity office, and the Data Protection and Freedom of Information Acts 	<p>In-depth interviews with 'Preparers' and 'Users'</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Codes such as The Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC), and the ACCA Rulebook adhered to • University ethics committee permission to undertake research granted
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Appendix I Interview Questions, both preparer and user

Questions for in-depth semi-structured interviews

(Repeat background and intent of research as covered in the Participant Information Sheet, including the study title and research questions, to participants before asking questions below).

Study Title:

An exploration around completeness of the IASB's qualitative characteristics.

Research Questions

Which QCs do Preparers refer to when explaining their accounting decisions, and when do they refer to these QCs?

And are the QCs complete?

In-depth semi-structured interviews are to be conducted to gain insights about the following questions:

To Preparers (preparers of bank's annual report)

- 1) What do you as a **Preparer** perceive to be the key qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information from **your** experience? (Note distinction between this and the next question below).
(Probe – Whatever you think is fine, and have a look at the chapter provided of the qualitative characteristics)
- 2) What do you as a **Preparer** perceive to be the key qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information from **the Users** perspective?

- 3) Do you think qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information for both **Preparers and Users** can be combined in the Conceptual Framework under the same sub-headings of 'Fundamental' and 'Enhancing'?
(Probe – Would you say that 'Fundamental' and 'Enhancing' characteristics from the chapter provided may be different from the Preparers perspective to the Users perspective?)
- 4) What further qualitative characteristics might you suggest should be included in the Conceptual Framework to improve the narrative of decision-useful financial information?
(Probe – Whatever you think is fine)
- 5) Do you think that there is in reality differences in the key qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information used between the 'voluntary narrative sections' and the 'mandatory statutory financial information sections' of banks' annual reports?
(Probe – By 'voluntary narrative sections' is meant all non-mandatory information in banks' annual reports such as any forward looking statements, strategic and financial reviews, business models, key result areas, et al.)
- 6) What are your views on the IASB no longer using the adjective '**decision-useful**' to describe qualitative characteristics of financial information? Should it have been reinstated in the Conceptual Framework, given that the information is for both corporate governance (management's stewardship of the entity's resources) and financial sustainability purposes?
- 7) What is your view on the IASB stating explicitly in the revised Conceptual Framework that 'Faithful Representation' must also represent the **substance** of an economic phenomenon, and that if the substance of an economic phenomenon and its legal form are not the same, providing information only about the **legal form** would **not** faithfully represent the economic phenomenon?
(Probe – Whatever you think is fine)
- 8) What is your view on the IASB reintroducing an explicit reference to the notion of '**prudence**' (described as caution when making judgements under conditions of uncertainty) as supporting **Neutrality**, instead of in its own right?
(Probe – Do you strongly agree, agree, disagree, or strongly disagree?)
- 9) What alternatives/ improvements might you suggest to the qualitative characteristics?
(Probe – Anything specific?)
- 10) Has your bank decided to be an **early-adopter** of the revised Conceptual Framework, or are you going to wait until 1 January 2020? And if an early adopter, what plans have you made already or do you envisage making?
(Probe – Strategy paper written? Project team formed to carry out transition?)

Foucauldian critical discourse analysis:

- 11) To what extent do you think the **power** of the IASB contributes to **subordination**, control and regulation of professional accountants?
(Probe – Would that be closer to ‘a lot’ or ‘not a lot’?)
- 12) Do you think the compilation of the IASB’s Conceptual Framework Project Committee has had any effect on the qualitative characteristics and their meanings decided upon?
- 13) What is your view on the IASB’s problematisation process (‘Requests for Information’, Discussion Papers, Exposure Drafts, and ultimately Post Implementation Review) for revising the qualitative characteristics?
(Probe – Can you be specific?)
- 14) In your view, has the IASB encouraged critique (**scepticism**) and critical inquiry (challenge) of the qualitative characteristics sufficiently?
- 15) In your view, could the epistemic knowledge of certain other plausible qualitative characteristics, put forward by the FASB or international accounting bodies before the IASB’s pre-dominance, have been subjugated by the IASB ontologically?
- 16) From your experience, has **governmentality** of the qualitative characteristics by the IASB restricted the characteristics you have used to explain accounting policy choices made and accounting standards adopted in your annual reports?
(Probe – Do you strongly agree, agree, disagree, or strongly disagree?)

To Users (Investment Analyst Societies or Chartered Financial Analyst Societies)

- 1) What do you as a **User** of banks' annual reports perceive to be the key qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information from **your** experience? (Note distinction between this and the next question below).
(Probe – Whatever you think is fine, and have a look at the chapter provided of the qualitative characteristics).
- 2) What do you as a **User** of banks' annual reports perceive to be the key qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information from **the Preparers** perspective?
*(Preparers mean **Preparers** of the bank's annual reports).*
- 3) Do you think qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information for both **Preparers and Users** can be combined in the Conceptual Framework under the same sub-headings of 'Fundamental' and 'Enhancing'?
(Probe – Would you say that 'Fundamental' and 'Enhancing' characteristics from the chapter provided may be different from the Preparers perspective to the Users perspective?)
- 4) What further qualitative characteristics might you suggest should be included in the Conceptual Framework to improve the narrative of decision-useful financial information?
(Probe – Whatever you think is fine)
- 5) Do you think that there is in reality differences in the key qualitative characteristics of decision-useful financial information used between the 'voluntary narrative sections' and the 'mandatory statutory financial information sections' of banks' annual reports?
(Probe – By 'voluntary narrative sections' is meant all non-mandatory information in banks' annual reports such as any forward-looking statements, strategic and financial reviews, business models, key result areas, et al.)
- 6) What are your views on the IASB no longer using the adjective '**decision-useful**' to describe qualitative characteristics of financial information? Should it have been reinstated in the Conceptual Framework, given that the information is for both corporate governance (management's stewardship of the entity's resources) and financial sustainability purposes?
- 7) What is your view on the IASB stating explicitly in the revised Conceptual Framework that 'Faithful Representation' must also represent the **substance** of an economic phenomenon, and that if the substance of an economic

phenomenon and its legal form are not the same, providing information only about the **legal form** would **not** faithfully represent the economic phenomenon? (*Probe – Whatever you think is fine*).

- 8) What is your view on the IASB reintroducing an explicit reference to the notion of '**prudence**' (described as caution when making judgements under conditions of uncertainty) as supporting **Neutrality**, instead of in its own right? (*Probe – Do you strongly agree, agree, disagree, or strongly disagree?*)
- 9) What alternatives/ improvements might you suggest to the qualitative characteristics? (*Probe – Anything specific?*)
- 10) Does **early adoption** (before 1 January 2020) provide a challenge when analysing banks' annual reports on a comparative basis against those that do not early adopt?

Foucauldian critical discourse analysis:

- 11) To what extent do you think the **power** of the IASB contributes to **subordination**, control and regulation of professional accountants? (*Probe – Would that be closer to 'a lot' or 'not a lot'?*)
- 12) Do you think the compilation of the IASB's Conceptual Framework Project Committee has had any effect on the qualitative characteristics and their meanings decided upon? (*I am aware that you may not necessarily know much about the compilation of the IASB governing body, as it may not have been relevant to you up to now*)
- 13) What is your view on the IASB's problematisation process ('Requests for Information', Discussion Papers, Exposure Drafts, and ultimately Post Implementation Review) for revising the qualitative characteristics? (*Probe – Can you be specific?*)
- 14) In your view, has the IASB encouraged critique (**scepticism**) and critical inquiry (challenge) of the qualitative characteristics sufficiently?
- 15) In your view, could the epistemic knowledge of certain other plausible qualitative characteristics, put forward by the FASB or international accounting bodies before the IASB's pre-dominance, have been subjugated by the IASB ontologically?

- 16) Do you think that **governmentality** of the qualitative characteristics by the IASB has restricted the characteristics used by **Preparers** to explain accounting policy choices they have made and the accounting standards they have adopted in their annual reports?
(Probe – Do you strongly agree, agree, disagree, or strongly disagree?)

Appendix J Content Analysis – Banks’ sampled and results from content analysis of their accounting policies

Table J. 1 Banks (Deposit taking, Class 1(1), licenceholders regulated by the Isle of Man Financial Services Act 2008 as amended), as at 30 June 2019.

Name of Bank/ (Deposit-taker) ¹ in the Isle of Man (saturation coverage)	Reporting under IFRS or UK GAAP	Locally incorporated, or Branch (IOM)	Interviewed	Ultimate Country of Origin	Local IOM entity content analysed ⁷ (both 2017 and 2018) (See ch.5.4)	Group entity content analysed ⁷ (both 2017 and 2018) (See ch.5.4)
Barclays Plc, Isle of Man Branch ²	IFRS	Branch of Barclays Plc ⁹	N/a - branch	UK	No ²	Yes
Cayman National Bank (Isle of Man) Limited	IFRS	Locally incorporated	Yes	Cayman Islands	Yes	No ⁸
Conister Bank Limited	IFRS	Locally incorporated, wholly owned by Manx Financial Group Plc	Yes	Isle of Man	Yes	N/a
HSBC Bank Plc	IFRS	Branch of HSBC Bank Plc	N/a - branch	UK	No ²	Yes
Lloyds Bank International Limited	IFRS	Locally incorporated	Yes	UK	Yes	Yes

Nationwide International Limited ³	IFRS	Branch of Nationwide Building Society (NBS)	Yes	UK	No ^{2,3}	Yes
Nedbank Private Wealth Limited ⁴	IFRS	Locally incorporated	No ⁴	South Africa	No ⁴	No ⁴
The Royal Bank of Scotland International Limited (RBSI) ⁵ ,	IFRS	Locally incorporated	No ⁶	UK	Yes	Yes
Santander UK Plc	IFRS	Branch of Santander UK Plc	N/a - branch	Spain	No ²	Yes
Standard Bank Isle of Man Limited	IFRS	Locally incorporated	Yes	South Africa	Yes	Yes

Notes

- 1 List of banks' / deposit takers excludes those banks' registered but in liquidation or managed.
- 2 Excluded from content analysis study at local IOM level, as its status as a branch means that its accounting policies are entirely driven by its group holding company bank, and its annual results subsumed within the group accounts.
- 3 Included in study even though its banking licence was handed back to the IOM FSA late 2017, due to researcher's interest in the group and the richness of study data obtained from NBS.
- 4 IOM entity and South African group entity excluded from study as their business is only partly private banking, and mainly investment management and fiduciary services.

- 5 Includes Natwest and IOM Bank Limited, both locally registered on the IOM with the IOM FSA as Deposit taking class 1(1) entities.
- 6 Excluded from interview as sensitive restructuring negotiations took place at time of study.
- 7 Content analysis of change in accounting policy and basis of preparation notes performed.
- 8 Excluded as banking forms a small part of group activities only.
- 9 Ring-fenced since 1 April 2018 as Barclays Bank UK Plc.

Source: Compiled from Isle of Man Financial Services Authority website <https://www.iomfsa.im/statistics/> and Isle of Man Banking Association website <http://www.iomba.org.im/Members-Directory/list.aspx> [Accessed: 9 September 2019].

Banks' sampled

The above Table J.1 illustrates that saturation coverage of the relevant IOM banks' / deposit-taking institutions has been carried out below for:

Barclays Plc

Cayman National Corporation Ltd

Manx Financial Group Plc (holding company of Conister Bank)

HSBC Bank Plc

Lloyds Bank International Limited

Nationwide International Limited

Santander UK Plc

Standard Bank Isle of Man Limited

The Royal Bank of Scotland International Limited

In addition, where the local banks' have group holding companies in further jurisdictions, these have been included. Of the total of 13 banks' or banking groups content analysed, five were local Isle of Man banks', five UK banking groups, one South African banking group, one Spanish banking group, and one Australian. The UK and South African banking groups in particular mirrored the contribution the CFA UK society and IAS SA directors respectively gave to the semi-structured interview process part of this research, with the Australian banking group (ANZ) added to ascertain any geographical or cultural differences, or even differences due to national accounting standards influences over either IFRS, IFRS as adopted by the EU, IFRS along with the requirements of the Companies Act of South Africa, or IFRS along with the Australian Accounting Standards and Corporations Regulations 2001.

Results from content analysis of banks' sampled accounting policies

(In order of list of banks' sampled above as shown in Table J.1, with ANZ Bank placed at the end due to no direct presence on the IOM from which the sample originates).

Barclays Plc

Extract from Barclays Plc Annual Report - 31 December 2017, p. 242, (pre revised CF):

'New and amended standards and interpretations

The accounting policies adopted are consistent with those of the previous financial year, with the exception of the accounting treatment of own credit on financial liabilities designated at fair value through profit or loss under the fair value option. Barclays has elected to early adopt the presentation of Barclays own credit gains and losses in other comprehensive income as allowed by IFRS 9 Financial Instruments, from 1 January 2017. This will have no effect on net assets, and any changes due to own credit in prior periods have not been restated. The cumulative own credit amount has been reclassified from retained earnings to a separate reserve. Any realised and unrealised amounts recognised in other comprehensive income will not be reclassified to the income statement in future periods; refer to Note 32 for further details.

There were no other material or amended standards or interpretations that resulted in a change in accounting policy.'

As the change affected recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, all the QCs can be implied: relevance, faithful representation, completeness, neutrality, prudence, free from error, substance over form, comparability, consistency, verifiability, timeliness, understandability. The qualitative characteristic of comparability is directly addressed.

Extract from Barclays Bank UK Plc Annual Report - 31 December 2018, p. 24, (post revised CF):

'New and amended standards and interpretations

*The accounting policies adopted are **consistent** with those of the previous financial year, with the exception of the adoption of IFRS 9 Financial Instruments including the early adoption of Prepayment Features with Negative Compensation (Amendments to IFRS 9), IFRS 15 Revenue from Contracts with Customers and the amendments to IFRS 2 Share-based Payment from 1 January 2018.*

IFRS 9 Financial Instruments

IFRS 9 Financial Instruments replaces IAS 39 Financial Instruments: Recognition and Measurement. IFRS 9 introduces key changes in the following areas:

- g. Classification and measurement – requiring asset classification and measurement based upon both business model and product characteristics*
- h. Impairment – introducing an expected credit loss model using forward looking information which replaces an incurred loss model. The expected credit loss model introduces a three-stage approach to impairment as follows:*

Stage 1 – the recognition of 12 month expected credit losses (ECL), that is the portion of lifetime expected credit losses from default events that are expected within 12 months of the reporting date, if credit risk has not increased significantly since initial recognition;

Stage 2 – lifetime expected credit losses for financial instruments for which credit risk has increased significantly since initial recognition; and

Stage 3 – lifetime expected credit losses for financial instruments which are credit impaired.

Refer to Note 8 for further details regarding the impairment requirements of IFRS 9.

*As required by IFRS 9 the Barclays Bank UK Group applied IFRS 9 retrospectively by adjusting the opening balance sheet at the date of initial application, and **comparative** periods have not been restated. There were no significant impacts from the adoption of IFRS 9.*

The following voluntary changes in presentation have been made as a result of the review of accounting presentation following the adoption of IFRS 9, and is expected to provide more relevant information to the users of the financial statements. These presentational changes have no effect on the measurement of these items and therefore had no impact on retained earnings or profit for any period. The effect of these presentational changes on transition are included in the consolidated balance sheet on page 108 and are noted below.

- i. 'Loans and advances to banks' and 'loans and advances to customers' have been disaggregated and are now reported in 'loans and advances at amortised cost' and 'cash collateral and settlement balances'; and*
- j. The available for sale assets which were previously reported in 'financial investments/available for sale investments' are now reported in 'financial assets at fair value through other comprehensive income'.*

IFRS 15 Revenue from Contracts with Customers

*IFRS 15 Revenue from Contracts with Customers replaces IAS 18 Revenue and IAS 11 Construction Contracts. IFRS 15 establishes a more systematic approach for revenue measurement and recognition by introducing a five-step model governing revenue recognition. The five-step model includes: 1) identifying the contract with the customer, 2) identifying each of the performance obligations included in the contract, 3) determining the amount of consideration in the contract, 4) allocating the consideration to each of the identified performance obligations and 5) recognising revenue as each performance obligation is satisfied. There were no significant impacts from the adoption of IFRS 15 in relation to **the timing** of when the Barclays Bank UK Group recognises revenues or when revenue should be recognised gross as a principal or net as an agent.*

IFRS 2 Share-based Payment— Amendments to IFRS 2

The IASB issued amendments to IFRS 2 Share-based Payment that address three main areas: the effects of vesting conditions on the measurement of a cash-settled share-based payment transaction; the classification of a share-based payment transaction with net settlement features for withholding tax obligations; and accounting where a modification to the terms and conditions of a share-based payment transaction changes its classification from cash settled to equity settled. The amendments are effective for annual periods beginning on or after 1 January 2018. Adoption of the amendments did not have a significant impact on the Barclays Bank UK Group.'

As the changes affected recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, all the QCs can be implied: relevance, faithful representation, completeness, neutrality, prudence, free from error, substance over form, comparability, consistency, verifiability, timeliness, understandability. The qualitative characteristics of consistency, comparability, and timeliness, along with the constraint of materiality, are directly addressed.

Manx Financial Group Plc (holding company of Conister Bank)

Extract from Manx Financial Group Plc Annual Report - 31 December 2017, p. 24, (pre revised CF):

'The Group has continued to apply the accounting policies used for the 2016 annual report, with the exception of those detailed below.

The Group has adopted the following new standards and amendments to standards, including any consequential amendments to other standards, with a date of initial application of 1 January 2017:

□ Disclosure initiative (Amendments to IAS 7);

□ Recognition of Deferred Tax Assets for Unrealised Losses (Amendments to IAS 12); and

□ Annual Improvements to IFRSs 2014-2016 Cycle (Amendments to IFRS 12 Disclosures of Interests in Other Entities).

There are no significant changes following the implementation of these standards and amendments.'

The group has made no significant change in accounting policy and accordingly reasons given were for amendments made to the standards themselves by the IASB. These amendments to standards apply to all banks' annual reports selected for the year ended 31 December 2017.

Extract from Manx Financial Group Plc Interim Report - 30 June 2018, p. 10, (post revised CF):

'The Group has adopted IFRS 9 'Financial Instruments' as issued by the IASB in July 2014 with a date of transition of 1 January 2018 which resulted in changes in accounting policies and adjustments to the amounts previously recognised in the financial statements. The Group did not early adopt any of IFRS 9 in previous periods. A number of other new standards are effective from 1 January 2018 but they do not have a material effect on the Group's financial assets.

The changes to accounting policies affected the recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities and impairment of financial assets. IFRS 9 also significantly amends other standards dealing with financial instruments such as 'IFRS 7: Financial Instruments: Disclosures'.

The changes in accounting policies are also expected to be reflected in the Group's consolidated financial statements as at and for the year ended 31 December 2018. Set out below are disclosures relating to the impact of the adoption of IFRS 9 on the Group.'

Although the group did adopt IFRS 9 in its Interim Report, no reason was given further than that 1 January 2018 was the implementation date as set by the IASB. As the change affected recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, all the QCs can be implied: relevance, faithful representation, completeness, neutrality, prudence, free from error, substance over form, comparability, consistency, verifiability, timeliness, understandability. The constraint of materiality is directly addressed:

'A number of other new standards are effective from 1 January 2018 but they do not have a material effect on the Group's financial assets.'

Cayman National Corporation Ltd

Extract from consolidated financial statements - 30 September 2017 (pre revised CF):

No changes in accounting policies note, and hence no explicit or implied QCs apply for this period.

Extract from consolidated financial statements - 30 September 2018 (post revised CF):

No changes in accounting policies note, and hence no explicit or implied QCs apply for this period. It was further noted that early adoption of the following three standards issued and applicable from 1 January 2019 have not been made: IFRS 9, IFRS 15, and IFRS 16.

HSBC Holdings Plc

Extract from annual report – 31 December 2017, p.186, (pre revised CF):

‘Compliance with International Financial Reporting Standards

The consolidated financial statements of HSBC and the separate financial statements of HSBC Holdings have been prepared in accordance with IFRSs as issued by the IASB, including interpretations issued by the IFRS Interpretations Committee, and as endorsed by the European Union (EU). At 31 December 2017, there were no unendorsed standards effective for the year ended 31 December 2017 affecting these consolidated and separate financial statements, and HSBC’s application of IFRSs results in no differences between IFRSs as issued by the IASB and IFRSs as endorsed by the EU.

Standards adopted during the year ended 31 December 2017

*HSBC has adopted the requirements of IFRS 9 ‘Financial Instruments’ relating to the presentation of gains and losses on financial liabilities designated at fair value from 1 January 2017 in the consolidated financial statements. As a result, the effects of changes in those liabilities’ credit risk is presented in other comprehensive income with the remaining effect presented in profit or loss. As permitted by the transitional requirements of IFRS 9, **comparatives** have not been restated. Adoption increased profit after tax by \$2,024m and basic and diluted earnings per share by \$0.10 with the opposite effect on other comprehensive income and no effect on net assets. These requirements were adopted in the separate financial statements of HSBC Holdings in 2016. There were no other new standards applied in 2017. However, during 2017, HSBC adopted a number of interpretations and amendments to standards which had an **insignificant effect** on the consolidated financial statements of HSBC and the separate financial statements of HSBC Holdings.’*

As the change to IFRS 9, commented on in above extract, affected recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, all the QCs

can be implied: relevance, faithful representation, completeness, neutrality, prudence, free from error, substance over form, comparability, consistency, verifiability, timeliness, understandability. The qualitative characteristic of comparability and the constraint of materiality is directly addressed by the quantification of the increase in the profit after tax.

Extract from annual report – 31 December 2018, p.186, (post revised CF):

‘Standards adopted during the year ended 31 December 2018

*HSBC has adopted the requirements of IFRS 9 ‘Financial Instruments’ from 1 January 2018, with the exception of the provisions relating to the presentation of gains and losses on financial liabilities designated at fair value, which were adopted from 1 January 2017. This includes the adoption of ‘Prepayment Features with Negative Compensation (Amendments to IFRS 9)’, which is effective for annual periods beginning on or after 1 January 2019 with early adoption permitted. The **effect of its adoption is not significant**. IFRS 9 includes an accounting policy choice to remain with IAS 39 hedge accounting, which HSBC has exercised. The classification and measurement, and impairment requirements, are **applied retrospectively** by adjusting the opening balance sheet at the date of initial application. As permitted by IFRS 9, HSBC has **not restated comparatives**. Adoption reduced net assets at 1 January 2018 by \$1,647m as set out in Note 37 of the Annual Report and Accounts 2018.*

*In addition, HSBC has adopted the requirements of IFRS 15 ‘Revenue from contracts with customers’ and a number of interpretations and amendments to standards, which have had an **insignificant effect** on the consolidated financial statements of HSBC and the separate financial statements of HSBC Holdings.*

IFRS 9 transitional requirements

The transitional requirements of IFRS 9 necessitated a review of the designation of financial instruments at fair value. IFRS 9 requires that the

designation is revoked where there is no longer an accounting mismatch at 1 January 2018 and permits designations to be revoked or additional designations created at 1 January 2018 if there are accounting mismatches at that date. As a result:

- fair value designations for financial liabilities were revoked where the accounting mismatch no longer exists, as required by IFRS 9; and*
- fair value designations were revoked for certain long-dated securities where accounting mismatches continue to exist, but where HSBC has revoked the designation as permitted by IFRS 9 since it will better mitigate the accounting mismatch by undertaking fair value hedge accounting.*

The results of these changes are included in the reconciliation set out in Note 37.

Changes in accounting policy

*While not necessarily required by the adoption of IFRS 9, the following voluntary changes in accounting policy and presentation were made as a result of reviews carried out in conjunction with its adoption. The effect of presentational changes at 1 January 2018 is included in the reconciliation set out in Note 37, and **comparatives have not been restated**.*

- We considered market practices for the presentation of certain financial liabilities, which contain both deposit and derivative components. We concluded that it would be appropriate to change the accounting policy and presentation of 'trading customer accounts and other debt securities in issue', to **better align with the presentation of similar financial instruments by peers**. This therefore provides more **relevant** information about the effect of these financial liabilities on our financial position and performance. As a result, rather than being classified as held for trading, we designate these financial liabilities as at fair value through profit or loss since they are managed and their performance evaluated on a fair value basis. A further consequence of this*

change in presentation is that the effects of changes in the liabilities' credit risk are presented in 'Other comprehensive income', with the remaining effect presented in profit or loss in accordance with Group accounting policy adopted in 2017 (following the adoption of the requirements in IFRS 9 relating to the presentation of gains and losses on financial liabilities designated at fair value).

*• Cash collateral, margin and settlement accounts have been **reclassified** from 'Trading assets' and 'Loans and advances to banks and customers' to 'Prepayments, accrued income and other assets' and from 'Trading liabilities' and 'Deposits by banks' and 'Customer accounts' to 'Accruals, deferred income and other liabilities'. The change in presentation for financial assets is in accordance with IFRS 9 and the change in presentation for financial liabilities is considered to provide more **relevant** information, given the change in presentation for the financial assets. The change in presentation for financial liabilities has had **no effect** on the measurement of these items and therefore on retained earnings or profit for any period. • Certain stock borrowing assets have been reclassified from 'Loans and advances to banks and customers' to 'Trading assets'. The change in measurement is a result of the determination of the global business model for this activity and will align the presentation throughout the Group. • Prior to 2018, foreign exchange exposure on some financial instruments designated at fair value was presented in the same line in the income statement as the underlying fair value movement on these instruments. In 2018, we have grouped the presentation of the entire effect of foreign exchange exposure in profit or loss and presented it within 'Net income from financial instruments held for trading or managed on a fair value basis'. **Comparative data has been re-presented.**'*

As the changes to IFRS 9 and IFRS 15, commented on in above extract, affected recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, all the QCs can be implied: relevance, faithful representation, completeness, neutrality, prudence, free from error, substance over form, comparability, consistency, verifiability, timeliness, understandability. The qualitative characteristics of relevance and comparability were mentioned directly a few times, and consistency (told that certain accounts were reclassified), as well as the constraint of materiality (adoption of IFRS 9 reduced net assets by \$1.6m, and other effects disclosed as not significant).

Lloyds Bank International Limited

Extract from annual report – 31 December 2017 (pre revised CF):

‘There are no new or amended accounting standards that have required a change to accounting policies for the 2017 financial year.’

Extract from annual report – 31 December 2018, pp. 52,53, (post revised CF):

‘The Company adopted IFRS 9 from 1 January 2018. In accordance with the transition requirements of IFRS 9, comparative information for 2017 has not been restated and transitional adjustments have been accounted through retained earnings as at 1 January 2018, the date of the initial application; and as a result shareholders’ equity reduced by £3,272,000, driven by the effects of the additional impairment provisions following the implementation of the expected credit loss methodology. It is not practical to quantify the impact of adoption of IFRS 9 on the results for the current period.’

As the change to IFRS 9, commented on in above extract, affected recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, all the QCs can be implied: relevance, faithful representation, completeness, neutrality, prudence, free from error, substance over form, comparability, consistency, verifiability, timeliness, understandability. The constraint of materiality is directly addressed by the quantification of the reduction in shareholders’ equity.

It was also noted that IFRS 15 Revenue from Contracts with Customers was also adopted from 1 January 2018, and that *‘IFRS 15 had no impact on the Company.’* The constraint of materiality is thus addressed directly, along with comparability being able to be inferred.

Lloyds Banking Group

Extract from annual report – 31 December 2017, p.173, (pre revised CF):

'Note 2: Accounting policies The Group's accounting policies are set out below. These accounting policies have been applied consistently.'

Extract from annual report – 31 December 2018, p.177, (post revised CF):

'Basis of preparation

The Group has adopted IFRS 9 and IFRS 15 with effect from 1 January 2018.

(i) IFRS 9 Financial Instruments IFRS 9 replaces IAS 39 and addresses classification, measurement and derecognition of financial assets and liabilities, the impairment of financial assets measured at amortised cost or fair value through other comprehensive income, expected credit loss provisions for loan commitments and financial guarantee contracts and general hedge accounting.

Impairment: IFRS 9 replaces the IAS 39 'incurred loss' impairment approach with an 'expected credit loss' approach. The revised approach applies to financial assets including finance lease receivables, recorded at amortised cost or fair value through other comprehensive income; loan commitments and financial guarantees that are not measured at fair value through profit or loss are also in scope. The expected credit loss approach requires an allowance to be established upon initial recognition of an asset reflecting the level of losses anticipated after having regard to, amongst other things, expected future economic conditions. Subsequently the amount of the allowance is affected by changes in the expectations of loss driven by changes in associated credit risk.

Classification and measurement: IFRS 9 requires financial assets to be classified into one of the following measurement categories: fair value through profit or loss, fair value through other comprehensive income and amortised cost. Classification is made on the basis of the objectives of the entity's business model for managing its financial assets and the contractual cash flow

characteristics of the instruments. The requirements for derecognition are broadly unchanged from IAS 39. The standard also retains most of the IAS 39 requirements for financial liabilities except for those designated at fair value through profit or loss whereby that part of the fair value change attributable to the entity's own credit risk is recorded in other comprehensive income. The Group **early adopted** this requirement with effect from 1 January 2017.

General hedge accounting: The new hedge accounting model aims to provide a better link between risk management strategy, the rationale for hedging and the impact of hedging on the financial statements. The standard does not explicitly address macro hedge accounting solutions, which are being considered in a separate IASB project – Accounting for Dynamic Risk Management. Until this project is finalised, the IASB has provided an accounting policy choice to retain IAS 39 hedge accounting in its entirety or choose to apply the IFRS 9 hedge accounting requirements. The Group has elected to continue applying hedge accounting as set out in IAS 39.

In adopting IFRS 9, the Group has **reclassified** loans and advances to banks with a maturity of less than three months totalling £2,274 million to financial assets measured at fair value through profit or loss, resulting in a corresponding reduction in cash and cash equivalents at 1 January 2018 compared to the amount previously reported at 31 December 2017.

(ii) IFRS 15 Revenue from Contracts with Customers

IFRS 15 has replaced IAS 18 Revenue and IAS 11 Construction Contracts. The core principle of IFRS 15 is that revenue reflects the transfer of goods or services to customers in an amount that reflects the consideration to which an entity expects to be entitled. The recognition of such revenue is in accordance with five steps to: identify the contract; identify the performance obligations; determine the transaction price; allocate the transaction price to the performance obligations; and recognise revenue when the performance obligations are satisfied.

Details of the impact of adoption of IFRS 9 and IFRS 15 are provided in note 54.

*Details of those IFRS pronouncements which will be **relevant** to the Group but which were not effective at 31 December 2018 and which have not been applied in preparing these financial statements are given in note 55.*

Note 2: Accounting policies

*The Group's accounting policies are set out below. These accounting policies have been applied **consistently**.*

As the changes to IFRS 9 and IFRS 15, commented on in above extract, affected recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, all the QCs can be implied: relevance, faithful representation, completeness, neutrality, prudence, free from error, substance over form, comparability, consistency, verifiability, timeliness, understandability. The qualitative characteristics of relevance and consistency were mentioned directly, and comparability indirectly (told that certain accounts were reclassified), as well as the constraint of materiality (adoption of IFRS 9 reduced cash and cash equivalents by £2.3m).

Nationwide Building Society

Extract from Nationwide Building Society Annual Report - 4 April 2018, p. 174, (considered pre revised CF):

'Change to accounting policies

Following the Group's decision to wind down its commercial lending business, and the strategic review outlined in the Annual Report and Accounts 2017, the segmental reporting policy has been updated to better reflect the way in which the Executive Committee, as chief operating decision maker, now manages the business. As a result, no segmental disclosure is provided.'

The reasons for this change include the QCs of relevance, faithful representation, understandability, all implied, as well as from Nobes and Stadler (2014), firm event, effect on financial statements, and economic/managerial environment. Although the above extract is after the revised CF was issued on 26 March 2018, NBS's year end was too soon afterwards to incorporate any new effect from the CF.

Extract from Nationwide Building Society Interim Report - 30 September 2018, pp. 53-54, (post revised CF):

'Basis of preparation

The consolidated interim financial statements of the Group for the half year ended 30 September 2018 have been prepared in accordance with the Disclosure and Transparency Rules of the Financial Conduct Authority and with International Accounting Standard (IAS) 34 'Interim Financial Reporting' as adopted by the EU. The consolidated interim financial statements should be read in conjunction with the Group's annual financial statements for the year ended 4 April 2018, which were prepared in accordance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) as adopted by the EU.'

This is the first period in which the Disclosure and Transparency Rules of the Financial Conduct Authority have taken effect, supporting, in the researcher's opinion, the transparency constraint now required to the revised CF on post-implementation review.

'Accounting policies

*The accounting policies adopted by the Group in the preparation of these consolidated interim financial statements and those which the Group currently expects to adopt in the Annual Report and Accounts 2019 are **consistent** with those disclosed in the Annual Report and Accounts 2018, except in relation to the adoption of the following new standards:*

□ IFRS 9 'Financial Instruments'

□ IFRS 15 'Revenue from Contracts with Customers'.

Further information on the impacts of adopting these new standards is set out below, including revised accounting policies in relation to IFRS 9.'

*'In addition, a number of amendments and improvements to accounting standards have been issued by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) with an effective date of 1 January 2018. Those **relevant** to these consolidated interim financial statements, being minor amendments to IFRS 2 'Classification and Measurement of Share-based Payment Transactions' and IAS 40 'Transfers of Investment Property', were adopted with no significant impact for the Group.'*

IFRS 9 'Financial Instruments'

*'As permitted by IFRS 9, **comparatives** have not been restated following adoption.*

IFRS 15 'Revenue from Contracts with Customers'

'The Group has applied IFRS 15 'Revenue from Contracts with Customers' from 5 April 2018. The standard applies to all contracts with customers but does not apply to financial instruments, lease contracts or non-monetary exchanges. IFRS 15 has introduced a principles-based approach for revenue recognition, with revenue being recognised as the related obligations are satisfied.'

*The Group has assessed revenue streams within the scope of IFRS 15 and concluded that the **timing** of revenue recognition is unchanged under the new standard. There is therefore no transitional impact from adopting this standard.'*

QCs directly referred to include relevance, consistency, comparability and timeliness. QCs inferred include, faithful representation, substance over form (reference to 'principles-based approach' above), prudence ('revenue being recognised as the related obligations are satisfied'), and completeness ('The standard applies to all contracts with customers but does not apply to...').

RBS Plc

Extract from annual report – 31 December 2017, p.182, (pre revised CF):

'The consolidated accounts are prepared under uniform accounting policies.'

Extract from annual report – 31 December 2018, p.177, (post revised CF):

'Adoption of IFRS 9

Refer to Note 33 for details of the adoption of IFRS 9.

Other amendments to IFRS

*IFRS 15 'Revenue from Contracts with Customers' has been adopted with effect from 1 January 2018. The Accounting policy is updated to reflect the terminology in the new standard but it has had **no effect on financial information reported** in the current or comparative periods. Interest income and expense continues to be recognised using the effective interest rate method for financial instruments measured at historical cost. There has been **no restatement** of profit or loss for comparative periods.*

*Other amendments to IFRS effective for 2018, including IFRS 2 'Share-based payments' and IAS 40 'Investment Property' have **not had a material effect** on the Group's financial statements.'*

As the changes to IFRS 9 and IFRS 15, commented on in above extract, affected recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, all the QCs can be implied: relevance, faithful representation, completeness, neutrality, prudence, free from error, substance over form, comparability, consistency, verifiability, timeliness, understandability. The qualitative characteristics of comparability and consistency were mentioned indirectly ('no effect on financial information reported' and 'no restatement'). The constraint of materiality was referred

to directly with reference to the remaining two standards adjusted for being IFRS 2 and IAS 40.

Santander UK Plc

Extract from annual report - 31 December 2017, p. 151, (pre revised CF):

'Change in accounting policy

*During the year, management changed the accounting policy for business combinations between entities under common control. Previously, the Santander UK group applied acquisition accounting under IFRS 3 where the acquisition was for cash consideration. Where the acquisition was for non-cash consideration, the acquisition was accounted for in a manner **consistent** with group reconstruction relief under the UK GAAP (merger accounting). Management has elected to account for all business combinations between entities under common control at their book values in the acquired entity by including the acquired entity's results from the date of the business combinations and not restating **comparatives**. Management believes changing to this basis of accounting is more **relevant** to accounting for business combinations between entities under common control. Applying acquisition accounting to such transactions where all of the businesses are ultimately controlled by the same party both before and after the business combinations is seen as being less relevant as there are no parties external to Banco Santander SA. For the Santander UK group, the effect of changing the accounting policy is to reduce goodwill by £631m and reduce retained earnings by the same amount, this amount representing the difference between the purchase price and the aggregate book value of the assets and liabilities of Santander Cards Limited, Santander Cards (UK) Limited (and its subsidiaries), Santander Cards Ireland Limited and Santander Consumer (UK) plc, which were acquired from Banco Santander SA in 2010. For the Company, the effect is to reduce goodwill by £456m and reduce retained earnings by the same amount, this amount representing the difference between the purchase price and the aggregate book value of the assets and liabilities of Santander Cards Limited, Santander Cards (UK) Limited (and its subsidiaries) and Santander Cards Ireland Limited. Each of the **comparative** periods presented has been restated to reflect the change in accounting policy. The application of the*

change in accounting policy did not result in any material change to the accounting for the acquisition of Alliance & Leicester plc from Banco Santander SA in 2009.'

QCs directly referred to include relevance, consistency and comparability

QCs inferred include, materiality constraint ('...did not result in any material change...'), and understandability ('the effect of changing the accounting policy is to reduce goodwill by £631m and reduce retained earnings by the same amount').

Extract from annual report - 31 December 2018, p. 142, (post revised CF):

'Recent accounting developments

On 1 January 2018, the Santander UK group adopted IFRS 9 'Financial Instruments' (IFRS 9) and IFRS 15 'Revenue from Contracts with Customers' (IFRS 15). The new or revised accounting policies are set out below.

The impact of applying IFRS 9 is disclosed in Note 44. The accounting policy changes for IFRS 9, set out below, have been applied from 1 January 2018. Comparatives have not been restated. As a result of the change from IAS 39 to IFRS 9, some disclosures presented in respect of certain financial assets are not comparable because their classification may have changed between the two standards. This means that some IFRS 9 disclosures are not directly comparable and some disclosures that relate to information presented on an IAS 39 basis are no longer relevant in the current period. As explained in Note 44, the classification and measurement changes to financial assets that arose on adoption of IFRS 9 have been aligned to the presentation in the balance sheet. The Santander UK group decided to continue adopting IAS 39 hedge accounting and consequently there have been no changes to the hedge accounting policies and practices following the adoption of IFRS 9. However, additional hedge accounting disclosure requirements of IFRS 7 'Financial Instruments: Disclosures' (IFRS 7) have been included in these financial statements.'

And:

'The application of IFRS 15 had no material impact on the Santander UK group as there were no significant changes in the recognition of in-scope income. The accounting policy changes for IFRS 15 are set out in the Revenue recognition policy below.'

As the change to IFRS 9, commented on in the first extract immediately above, affected recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, all the QCs can be implied: relevance, faithful representation, completeness, neutrality, prudence, free from error, substance over form, comparability, consistency, verifiability, timeliness, understandability. The constraint of materiality is directly addressed within note 44 to the annual report of Santander UK Plc for 31 December 2018.

Standard Bank Isle of Man Limited

Extract from summary financial statements - 31 December 2017 (pre revised CF):

No change in accounting policy note.

Extract from summary financial statements - 31 December 2018, p. 3, (post revised CF):

'Revenue

...Additionally, interest income arising from treasury bills was previously classified in 'fair value gains' prior to the adoption of IFRS 9. The adoption of IFRS 9 resulted in the classification of treasury bills as assets held at amortised cost and consequently, the related income is classified as NII for the current year and going forward.

Other income decreased by 33.0% year-on-year. This was a reflection of the reclassification of interest income on the treasury bills, previously classified as fair value gains.'

No specific change in accounting policy note disclosed, however, the presentation effects of IFRS 9 have been disclosed in the Revenue note. The QC of comparability is thus referred to, and materiality, a constraint, indirectly referred to by the presenting of the decrease percentage in other income.

Standard Bank Group

Extract from summary financial statements - 31 December 2017, p. 28, (pre revised CF):

‘Changes in accounting policies

*The accounting policies are **consistent** with those reported in the previous year except as required in terms of the adoption of the following:*

Adoption of new and amended standards effective for the current financial period

*The accounting policies are **consistent** with those reported in the previous year except as required in terms of the adoption of the following amendments effective for the current period:*

- *Annual improvements 2014 – 2016 clarification to IFRS 12 Disclosure of Interests in Other Entities (IFRS 12): amendment clarifies that an entity is not required to disclose summarised financial information for a subsidiary, joint venture or associate when classified (or included in a disposal group that is classified) as held for sale in terms of IFRS 5 Non-current Assets Held for Sale and Discontinued Operations (IFRS 5).*

Early adoption of revised standards:

- *Amendment to IFRS 2 Classification and Measurement of Share-based Payment Transactions (IFRS 2): the amendments eliminate diversity in practice in three main areas, namely: (1) effects of vesting conditions on the measurement of a cash-settled share-based payment transaction; (2) classification of a share-based payment transaction with net settlement features for withholding tax obligations; and (3) accounting where a modification*

to the terms and conditions of a share-based payment transaction changes its classification from cash-settled to equity-settled.

- *Annual improvements 2014 – 2016 clarification to IFRS 1 First-time Adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS 1) and IAS 28 Investments in Associates and Joint Ventures (IAS 28). The clarification to IAS 28 clarifies that an entity may make an election separately for each associate or joint venture, that is a venture capital organisation, or a mutual fund, unit trust and similar entities including investment-linked insurance funds, at initial recognition to measure that associate or joint venture at either at fair value through profit or loss in accordance with IAS 39 or the equity method in accordance with IAS 28.*

- *Amendment to IAS 40 Investment Property (IAS 40): amendments clarifies the requirements on transfers to, or from, investment property when, and only when, there is a change in use. A change in use occurs when the property meets, or ceases to meet, the definition of investment property and there is evidence of the change in use.*

*The abovementioned amendments to the IFRS standards, adopted on 1 January 2017, **did not have any effect** on the group's previously reported financial results or disclosures and had **no material impact** on the group's accounting policies.'*

The qualitative characteristic of consistency and the constraint of materiality are both directly and separately addressed.

'Extract from summary financial statements - 31 December 2018, pp. 28-29, (post revised CF):

Changes in accounting policies

The accounting policies are **consistent** with those reported in the previous year except as required in terms of the adoption of the following:

Adoption of new and amended standards effective for the current financial period

The accounting policies are **consistent** with those reported in the previous year except for the adoption of the following standards and amendments effective for the current period:

- *IFRS 4 Insurance Contracts (amendment) (IFRS 4), the amendment to applying IFRS 9 Financial Instruments with IFRS 4 introduced two approaches: an overlay approach and a deferral approach. The amended standard will provide all companies that issue insurance contracts the option to recognise in other comprehensive income, rather than profit or loss, the volatility that could arise when IFRS 9 is applied before the new insurance contracts standard is issued; and provide companies whose activities are predominantly connected with insurance an optional temporary exemption from applying IFRS 9 until 2021. The entities that defer the application of IFRS 9 will continue to apply the existing financial instruments standard IAS 39. The amendments to IFRS 4 supplement existing options in the standard that can already be used to address the temporary volatility. **The group did not apply the optional temporary exemption from applying IFRS 9 until 2021.***

- *IFRS 15 Revenue from Contracts with Customers (IFRS 15), with effect from 1 January 2018, replaces the existing revenue standards and the related interpretations. The standard sets out the requirements for recognising revenue that applies to all contracts with customers (except for contracts that are within the scope of the standards on leases, insurance contracts or financial instruments). The core principle of the standard is that revenue recognised reflects the consideration to which the company expects to be entitled in exchange for the transfer of promised goods or services to the customer. The standard incorporates a five step analysis to determine the amount and **timing** of revenue recognition. The group adopted IFRS 15 on 1 January 2018 and, as*

*permitted by IFRS 15, did not restate its **comparative** financial results. The standard does not apply to revenue associated with financial instruments, and therefore does not impact the majority of the group's revenue.*

- *IFRIC 22 Foreign Currency Transactions and Advance Consideration (IFRIC 22) provides guidance on how to determine the date of the transaction for the purpose of determining the exchange rate to use on initial recognition of the related asset, expense or income (or part of it) on the derecognition of a non-monetary asset or non-monetary liability arising from the payment or receipt of advance consideration in a foreign currency.*

*The above mentioned standards and interpretation to the IFRS standards, adopted on 1 January 2018, **did not affect the group's previously reported financial results**, disclosures or accounting policies and **did not impact the group's results** upon transition.*

- *IFRS 9 with effect from 1 January 2018, replaced IAS 39. IFRS 9 introduced new requirements which included an ECL impairment model and new requirements for the classification and measurement of financial assets. IFRS 9, adopted on 1 January 2018, impacted the group's results upon transition. The impact to the group's reserves upon transition to IFRS 9 **materially** relates to IFRS 9's ECL impairment requirements. IFRS 9's classification and measurement requirements resulted in an **immaterial** impact to the group upon transition. Refer to the IFRS 9 transition for more detail.'*

As the change to IFRS 9, commented on in the extract immediately above, affected recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, all the QCs can be implied: relevance, faithful representation, completeness, neutrality, prudence, free from error, substance over form, comparability, consistency, verifiability, timeliness, understandability. The qualitative characteristics of consistency, comparability and timeliness are directly addressed, along with the constraint of materiality.

The Royal Bank of Scotland International Limited

Extract from summary financial statements - 31 December 2017, p. 13, (pre revised CF):

No change in accounting policy note.

Extracts from summary financial statements - 31 December 2018, pp. 13, 60, (post revised CF):

'IFRS 15 "Revenue from Contracts with Customers" has been adopted with effect from 1 January 2018 and replaces IAS 18 "Revenue". The Accounting policy is updated to reflect the terminology in the new standard but it has had no effect on financial information reported in the current or comparative periods.'

The constraint of materiality is thus addressed directly ('no effect'), along with comparability being able to be inferred.

'Note 23. The adoption of IFRS 9

The Bank's accounting policies have significantly changed on the adoption of IFRS 9 'Financial Instruments' with effect from 1 January 2018. Prior years are re-presented but there has been no restatement of prior year data.

IFRS 9 changed the classification categories of financial assets from IAS 39. Held-for-trading assets were classified to mandatory fair value through profit or loss; loans and receivables were classified to amortised cost; and available-for-sale assets were classified as fair value through other comprehensive income unless they were deemed to be in a fair value business model or failed the contractual cash flow requirements under IFRS 9.

There were no changes in the classification and measurement of financial liabilities.

The day 1 net increase to loan impairments from IAS 39 to IFRS 9 was £3m under the expected credit loss requirements. The impact on the Group's balance sheet at 1 January 2018 and the key movements in relation to the impact on classification and measurement are as follows:

As the change to IFRS 9, commented on in above extract, affected recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, all the QCs can be implied: relevance, faithful representation, completeness, neutrality, prudence, free from error, substance over form, comparability, consistency, verifiability, timeliness, understandability. The constraint of materiality has been directly addressed by the quantification of the net increase to loan impairments of £3m.

Australia and New Zealand Banking Group Limited

Extract from summary financial statements – 30 September 2017, p. 71-74, (pre revised CF):

There was no Changes in Accounting Policy note, however there was the following note, summarised, on Accounting Standards Not Early Adopted:

‘A number of new standards, amendments to standards and interpretations have been published but are not mandatory for the financial statements for the year ended 30 September 2017, and have not been applied by the Group in preparing these financial statements. We have identified four standards where this applies to the Group and further details are set out below.’

These four standards are discussed under their respective headings in the annual report:

AASB 9 Financial Instruments (AASB 9)

AASB 15 Revenue from Contracts with Customers (AASB 15)

AASB 16 Leases (AASB 16)

AASB 17 Insurance Contracts (AASB 17)

In all four of the above cases, the annual report stated that the Group was either in the process of assessing the impact of the application of the standards and had not yet been able to reasonably estimate the impact on its financial statements, or the Group had not (yet) determined which transition approach it would adopt.

As the change to the bank’s accounting policies being brought about by rewritten or new standards to be adopted, above, are in conformity with Australian auditing and assurance standards options offered in the respective Standard, recognition,

classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, can be assumed. This means that all the QCs can be implied: relevance, faithful representation, completeness, neutrality, prudence, free from error, substance over form, comparability, consistency, verifiability, timeliness, understandability. However, for the Standard AASB 9 Financial Instruments, 'comparability' technically cannot be inferred, as the note in the annual report goes on to state 'ANZ does not intend to restate comparatives'. (It is noted that although comparatives were not restated, the bank did adjust opening retained earnings at 1 October 2018).

Extract from summary financial statements – 30 September 2018, p. 77, (post revised CF):

Although there was not a Change in Accounting Policies note, the four standards that were not early adopted last year, were readdressed again for this year end.

AASB 9 Financial Instruments (AASB 9)

As the change to AASB 9, commented on in the publicly available annual report in some detail, affected recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, all the QCs can be implied.

AASB 15 Revenue from Contracts with Customers (AASB 15)

As the change to AASB 15, commented on in the publicly available annual report, affected recognition, classification and measurement of financial assets and financial liabilities, all the QCs can be implied.

AASB 16 Leases (AASB 16)

'The Group is in the process of assessing the impact of the application of AASB 16 and is not yet able to reasonably estimate the impact on its financial statements.'

AASB 17 Insurance Contracts (AASB 17)

'The final version of AASB 17 was issued in July 2017 and is not effective for the Group until 1 October 2021. It will replace AASB 4 Insurance Contracts, AASB 1023 General Insurance Contracts and AASB 1038 Life Insurance Contracts. AASB 17 establishes principles for the recognition, measurement, presentation and disclosure of insurance contracts.'

The measurement, presentation and disclosure requirements under AASB 17 are significantly different from current accounting standards. Although the overall profit recognised in respect of insurance contracts will not change, it is expected that the timing of profit recognition will change.

The Group is not yet able to reasonably estimate the impact of AASB 17 on its financial statements.'

Appendix K Content Analysis - Decision Rules for accounting policy changes

(See Content Analysis of Accounting Policy Changes s.5.3)

General

The content analysis sample of IFRS reporting banks' was drawn from UK banks' represented on the IOM by their branch, a South African bank also represented on the Isle of Man, an Australian bank, and all Isle of Man banks' for whom the study sample parameters applied (reporting under IFRS and regulated by the IOM FSA holding a Class 1(1) licence permitting deposit taking activities, similar to the content analysis based on methodology previously adopted in studies undertaken by Dunne et al. (2008) and Finningham (2010), and latterly by Nobes and Stadler (2014). It was felt important to include UK banks' and a South African banking group due to the semi-structured interviews that had been held with the CFA UK society and the IAS SA directors. For further geographical spread, the Australian bank was also included, one which had also written in to the IASB and whose comment letter précis has been included in the study, The Australia and New Zealand Banking Group Limited.

Evidence

Disclosure may be either the exact qualitative characteristic (QC) term, or a synonym, or a phrase from the definition of the QC, or QC implied from the paragraph or phrase.

Location in the Annual Report

Either the Change in Accounting Policies note, or the Basis of Preparation note or similar note to the financial statements shown in the Notes to the Accounts.

Memo

For any additional information or disclosure worth highlighting.

Appendix L Content Analysis – Template for identifying qualitative characteristics

Data collection and coding procedures – Change in Accounting Policies

This appendix provides details of how data was collected on changes in accounting policies within the sample banks' annual reports both before and after the revised CF was issued, and how explanations of policy changes were coded. This is an extract of Nobes and Stadler's (2014) procedures, mainly because Nobes and Stadler (2014) went further to look at all information in the financial statements, and had different codes applicable to the year in which the study was carried out, and in terms of their studies priorities and hypotheses.

Nobes and Stadler (2014) searched all the notes of their sample companies if no or insufficient information was found in the financial statements or the accounting policy section of the notes, while this study has singularly kept to the Change in Accounting Policy notes (or the Basis of Preparation note or similar note to the financial statements shown in the Notes to the Accounts) as it is in these notes that explanations for IFRS and other policy changes are generally to be found. Several QCs (for example 'faithful representation', 'understandability' and 'transparency') are not only scored if they are explicitly stated, but also if inferred. For example:

'Faithful representation (inferred)' includes any reference to better presentation of information, 'understandability (inferred)' includes any reference to improved clarity of information, 'transparency (inferred)' includes enhanced disclosure, additional information, and improved visibility.

This appendix provides three examples below of how Nobes and Stadler (2014) coded the explanations of policy changes they found, and their procedures for identifying the QC reasons for such IFRS policy changes:

- (1) 'The directors of the Company are of the view that the change in accounting method for interests in jointly controlled entities would provide

more reliable, relevant and comparable information [...]’ (Shenzhen Expressway, Annual Report 2007, p. 109)

(2) ‘We believe this revised presentation will provide users of our financial statements with a better understanding of our business.’ (Imperial Tobacco, Annual Report and Accounts 2007, p. 71)

(3) ‘This change provides information that is clearer and more relevant.’ (Unilever, Annual Report and Accounts 2011, p. 68)

The first example contains three reasons: ‘reliability’, ‘relevance’ and ‘comparability’. The second example has one reason: better understanding, which Nobes and Stadler (2014) scored as ‘understandability’.¹⁵

Several explanations do not explicitly refer to particular QCs but can still be coded on an ‘inferred’ basis. For instance, the third example shows (in addition to ‘relevance’) what Nobes and Stadler (2014) labelled ‘understandability (inferred)’; i.e., they inferred from the reference to ‘clearer’ that one of the reasons for the change was to improve ‘understandability’.

Examples of reasons for accounting policy changes under IFRS arising from this study:

Faithful representation (inferred): ‘Following the Group’s decision to wind down its commercial lending business, and the strategic review outlined in the Annual Report and Accounts 2017, the segmental reporting policy has been updated to better reflect the way in which the Executive Committee, as chief operating decision maker, now manages the business. As a result, no segmental

¹⁵ Nobes and Stadler (2014) argued that ‘better understanding of our business’ refers to faithful representation as understandability is an enhancing characteristic of faithful representation, even if faithful representation is not explicitly stated in the accounting policy.

disclosure is provided'. Nationwide Building Society Annual Report and Accounts 2018. 'Relevance' and 'comparability' are also inferred.

Relevance: 'The group adopted IFRS 15 on 1 January 2018 and, as permitted by IFRS 15, did not restate its comparative financial results. The Standard does not apply to revenue associated with financial instruments, and therefore does not impact the majority of the group's revenue'. Standard Bank Group analysis of financial results for the year ended 31 December 2018. 'Comparability' is also stated.

Materiality: 'A number of other new standards are effective from 1 January 2018 but they do not have a material effect on the Group's financial assets'. Conister Bank (part of Manx Financial Group plc, Interim Report 30 June 2018).

Completeness: 'Management has elected to account for all business combinations between entities under common control at their book values in the acquired entity by including the acquired entity's results from the date of the business combinations and not restating comparatives'. Santander UK plc Notes to the Financial Statements 2017. 'Comparability' is also stated.

Comparability: 'Accrued interest on these liabilities was previously included in 'Accruals and deferred income'. Accrued interest is now presented within 'Subordinated liabilities' and 'Subscribed capital' to provide a consistent presentation with other financial instruments held at amortised cost'. Nationwide Building Society Annual Report and Accounts 2018. 'Consistency' is also stated.

Consistency: 'The accounting policies have been applied consistently with those presented in the Annual Report for the year ended 31 December 2017 and comply with IFRSs and IFRIC interpretations applicable to companies reporting under IFRS as adopted by the EU'. Conister Bank (part of Manx Financial Group plc, Interim Report 30 June 2018). 'Comparability' is also inferred.

Timeliness: 'Revenue from Contracts with Customers (IFRS 15), with effect from 1 January 2018, replaces the existing revenue standards and the related

interpretations'. Standard Bank Group analysis of financial results for the year ended 31 December 2018. 'Relevance', and 'comparability' are also inferred.

Understandability: 'The impact on the Group's balance sheet at 1 January 2018 and the key movements in relation to the impact on classification and measurement are as follows': Royal Bank of Scotland International Report of Directors and Financial Statements 31 December 2017.

Transparency (inferred): 'As stated in the Group's Interim Results for the period ended 30 September 2016, the derivatives and hedge accounting policy includes additional wording in respect of the classification of cash collateral.' Nationwide Building Society Annual Report and Accounts 2017.

Appendix M Chapter Two of the Conceptual Framework for financial reporting

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR FINANCIAL REPORTING

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from paragraph

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Introduction

- 2.1 The qualitative characteristics of useful financial information discussed in this chapter identify the types of information that are likely to be most useful to the existing and potential investors, lenders and other creditors for making decisions about the reporting entity on the basis of information in its financial report (financial information).
- 2.2 Financial reports provide information about the reporting entity's economic resources, claims against the reporting entity and the effects of transactions and other events and conditions that change those resources and claims. (This information is referred to in the *Conceptual Framework* as information about the economic phenomena.) Some financial reports also include explanatory material about management's expectations and strategies for the reporting entity, and other types of forward-looking information.
- 2.3 The qualitative characteristics of useful financial information⁵ apply to financial information provided in financial statements, as well as to financial information provided in other ways. Cost, which is a pervasive constraint on the reporting entity's ability to provide useful financial information, applies similarly. However, the considerations in applying the qualitative characteristics and the cost constraint may be different for different types of information. For example, applying them to forward-looking information may be different from applying them to information about existing economic resources and claims and to changes in those resources and claims.

Qualitative characteristics of useful financial information

- 2.4 If financial information is to be useful, it must be relevant and faithfully represent what it purports to represent. The usefulness of financial information is enhanced if it is comparable, verifiable, timely and understandable.

Fundamental qualitative characteristics

- 2.5 The fundamental qualitative characteristics are relevance and faithful representation.

Relevance

- 2.6 Relevant financial information is capable of making a difference in the decisions made by users. Information may be capable of making a difference in a decision even if some users choose not to take advantage of it or are already aware of it from other sources.
- 2.7 Financial information is capable of making a difference in decisions if it has predictive value, confirmatory value or both.
- 2.8 Financial information has predictive value if it can be used as an input to processes employed by users to predict future outcomes. Financial information

⁵ Throughout the *Conceptual Framework*, the terms 'qualitative characteristics' and 'cost constraint' refer to the qualitative characteristics of, and the cost constraint on, useful financial information.

need not be a prediction or forecast to have predictive value. Financial information with predictive value is employed by users in making their own predictions.

- 2.9 Financial information has confirmatory value if it provides feedback about (confirms or changes) previous evaluations.
- 2.10 The predictive value and confirmatory value of financial information are interrelated. Information that has predictive value often also has confirmatory value. For example, revenue information for the current year, which can be used as the basis for predicting revenues in future years, can also be compared with revenue predictions for the current year that were made in past years. The results of those comparisons can help a user to correct and improve the processes that were used to make those previous predictions.

Materiality

- 2.11 Information is material if omitting it or misstating it could influence decisions that the primary users of general purpose financial reports (see paragraph 1.5) make on the basis of those reports, which provide financial information about a specific reporting entity. In other words, materiality is an entity-specific aspect of relevance based on the nature or magnitude, or both, of the items to which the information relates in the context of an individual entity's financial report. Consequently, the Board cannot specify a uniform quantitative threshold for materiality or predetermine what could be material in a particular situation.

Faithful representation

- 2.12 Financial reports represent economic phenomena in words and numbers. To be useful, financial information must not only represent relevant phenomena, but it must also faithfully represent the substance of the phenomena that it purports to represent. In many circumstances, the substance of an economic phenomenon and its legal form are the same. If they are not the same, providing information only about the legal form would not faithfully represent the economic phenomenon (see paragraphs 4.59–4.62).
- 2.13 To be a perfectly faithful representation, a depiction would have three characteristics. It would be complete, neutral and free from error. Of course, perfection is seldom, if ever, achievable. The Board's objective is to maximise those qualities to the extent possible.
- 2.14 A complete depiction includes all information necessary for a user to understand the phenomenon being depicted, including all necessary descriptions and explanations. For example, a complete depiction of a group of assets would include, at a minimum, a description of the nature of the assets in the group, a numerical depiction of all of the assets in the group, and a description of what the numerical depiction represents (for example, historical cost or fair value). For some items, a complete depiction may also entail explanations of significant facts about the quality and nature of the items, factors and circumstances that might affect their quality and nature, and the process used to determine the numerical depiction.

- 2.15 A neutral depiction is without bias in the selection or presentation of financial information. A neutral depiction is not slanted, weighted, emphasised, de-emphasised or otherwise manipulated to increase the probability that financial information will be received favourably or unfavourably by users. Neutral information does not mean information with no purpose or no influence on behaviour. On the contrary, relevant financial information is, by definition, capable of making a difference in users' decisions.
- 2.16 Neutrality is supported by the exercise of prudence. Prudence is the exercise of caution when making judgements under conditions of uncertainty. The exercise of prudence means that assets and income are not overstated and liabilities and expenses are not understated.⁶ Equally, the exercise of prudence does not allow for the understatement of assets or income or the overstatement of liabilities or expenses. Such misstatements can lead to the overstatement or understatement of income or expenses in future periods.
- 2.17 The exercise of prudence does not imply a need for asymmetry, for example, a systematic need for more persuasive evidence to support the recognition of assets or income than the recognition of liabilities or expenses. Such asymmetry is not a qualitative characteristic of useful financial information. Nevertheless, particular Standards may contain asymmetric requirements if this is a consequence of decisions intended to select the most relevant information that faithfully represents what it purports to represent.
- 2.18 Faithful representation does not mean accurate in all respects. Free from error means there are no errors or omissions in the description of the phenomenon, and the process used to produce the reported information has been selected and applied with no errors in the process. In this context, free from error does not mean perfectly accurate in all respects. For example, an estimate of an unobservable price or value cannot be determined to be accurate or inaccurate. However, a representation of that estimate can be faithful if the amount is described clearly and accurately as being an estimate, the nature and limitations of the estimating process are explained, and no errors have been made in selecting and applying an appropriate process for developing the estimate.
- 2.19 When monetary amounts in financial reports cannot be observed directly and must instead be estimated, measurement uncertainty arises. The use of reasonable estimates is an essential part of the preparation of financial information and does not undermine the usefulness of the information if the estimates are clearly and accurately described and explained. Even a high level of measurement uncertainty does not necessarily prevent such an estimate from providing useful information (see paragraph 2.22).

Applying the fundamental qualitative characteristics

- 2.20 Information must both be relevant and provide a faithful representation of what it purports to represent if it is to be useful. Neither a faithful representation of an irrelevant phenomenon nor an unfaithful representation of a relevant phenomenon helps users make good decisions.

⁶ Assets, liabilities, income and expenses are defined in Table 4.1. They are the elements of financial statements.

- 2.21 The most efficient and effective process for applying the fundamental qualitative characteristics would usually be as follows (subject to the effects of enhancing characteristics and the cost constraint, which are not considered in this example). First, identify an economic phenomenon, information about which is capable of being useful to users of the reporting entity's financial information. Second, identify the type of information about that phenomenon that would be most relevant. Third, determine whether that information is available and whether it can provide a faithful representation of the economic phenomenon. If so, the process of satisfying the fundamental qualitative characteristics ends at that point. If not, the process is repeated with the next most relevant type of information.
- 2.22 In some cases, a trade-off between the fundamental qualitative characteristics may need to be made in order to meet the objective of financial reporting, which is to provide useful information about economic phenomena. For example, the most relevant information about a phenomenon may be a highly uncertain estimate. In some cases, the level of measurement uncertainty involved in making that estimate may be so high that it may be questionable whether the estimate would provide a sufficiently faithful representation of that phenomenon. In some such cases, the most useful information may be the highly uncertain estimate, accompanied by a description of the estimate and an explanation of the uncertainties that affect it. In other such cases, if that information would not provide a sufficiently faithful representation of that phenomenon, the most useful information may include an estimate of another type that is slightly less relevant but is subject to lower measurement uncertainty. In limited circumstances, there may be no estimate that provides useful information. In those limited circumstances, it may be necessary to provide information that does not rely on an estimate.

Enhancing qualitative characteristics

- 2.23 Comparability, verifiability, timeliness and understandability are qualitative characteristics that enhance the usefulness of information that both is relevant and provides a faithful representation of what it purports to represent. The enhancing qualitative characteristics may also help determine which of two ways should be used to depict a phenomenon if both are considered to provide equally relevant information and an equally faithful representation of that phenomenon.

Comparability

- 2.24 Users' decisions involve choosing between alternatives, for example, selling or holding an investment, or investing in one reporting entity or another. Consequently, information about a reporting entity is more useful if it can be compared with similar information about other entities and with similar information about the same entity for another period or another date.
- 2.25 Comparability is the qualitative characteristic that enables users to identify and understand similarities in, and differences among, items. Unlike the other qualitative characteristics, comparability does not relate to a single item. A comparison requires at least two items.

- 2.26 Consistency, although related to comparability, is not the same. Consistency refers to the use of the same methods for the same items, either from period to period within a reporting entity or in a single period across entities. Comparability is the goal; consistency helps to achieve that goal.
- 2.27 Comparability is not uniformity. For information to be comparable, like things must look alike and different things must look different. Comparability of financial information is not enhanced by making unlike things look alike any more than it is enhanced by making like things look different.
- 2.28 Some degree of comparability is likely to be attained by satisfying the fundamental qualitative characteristics. A faithful representation of a relevant economic phenomenon should naturally possess some degree of comparability with a faithful representation of a similar relevant economic phenomenon by another reporting entity.
- 2.29 Although a single economic phenomenon can be faithfully represented in multiple ways, permitting alternative accounting methods for the same economic phenomenon diminishes comparability.

Verifiability

- 2.30 Verifiability helps assure users that information faithfully represents the economic phenomena it purports to represent. Verifiability means that different knowledgeable and independent observers could reach consensus, although not necessarily complete agreement, that a particular depiction is a faithful representation. Quantified information need not be a single point estimate to be verifiable. A range of possible amounts and the related probabilities can also be verified.
- 2.31 Verification can be direct or indirect. Direct verification means verifying an amount or other representation through direct observation, for example, by counting cash. Indirect verification means checking the inputs to a model, formula or other technique and recalculating the outputs using the same methodology. An example is verifying the carrying amount of inventory by checking the inputs (quantities and costs) and recalculating the ending inventory using the same cost flow assumption (for example, using the first-in, first-out method).
- 2.32 It may not be possible to verify some explanations and forward-looking financial information until a future period, if at all. To help users decide whether they want to use that information, it would normally be necessary to disclose the underlying assumptions, the methods of compiling the information and other factors and circumstances that support the information.

Timeliness

- 2.33 Timeliness means having information available to decision-makers in time to be capable of influencing their decisions. Generally, the older the information is the less useful it is. However, some information may continue to be timely long after the end of a reporting period because, for example, some users may need to identify and assess trends.

Understandability

- 2.34 Classifying, characterising and presenting information clearly and concisely makes it understandable.
- 2.35 Some phenomena are inherently complex and cannot be made easy to understand. Excluding information about those phenomena from financial reports might make the information in those financial reports easier to understand. However, those reports would be incomplete and therefore possibly misleading.
- 2.36 Financial reports are prepared for users who have a reasonable knowledge of business and economic activities and who review and analyse the information diligently. At times, even well-informed and diligent users may need to seek the aid of an adviser to understand information about complex economic phenomena.

Applying the enhancing qualitative characteristics

- 2.37 Enhancing qualitative characteristics should be maximised to the extent possible. However, the enhancing qualitative characteristics, either individually or as a group, cannot make information useful if that information is irrelevant or does not provide a faithful representation of what it purports to represent.
- 2.38 Applying the enhancing qualitative characteristics is an iterative process that does not follow a prescribed order. Sometimes, one enhancing qualitative characteristic may have to be diminished to maximise another qualitative characteristic. For example, a temporary reduction in comparability as a result of prospectively applying a new Standard may be worthwhile to improve relevance or faithful representation in the longer term. Appropriate disclosures may partially compensate for non-comparability.

The cost constraint on useful financial reporting

- 2.39 Cost is a pervasive constraint on the information that can be provided by financial reporting. Reporting financial information imposes costs, and it is important that those costs are justified by the benefits of reporting that information. There are several types of costs and benefits to consider.
- 2.40 Providers of financial information expend most of the effort involved in collecting, processing, verifying and disseminating financial information, but users ultimately bear those costs in the form of reduced returns. Users of financial information also incur costs of analysing and interpreting the information provided. If needed information is not provided, users incur additional costs to obtain that information elsewhere or to estimate it.
- 2.41 Reporting financial information that is relevant and faithfully represents what it purports to represent helps users to make decisions with more confidence. This results in more efficient functioning of capital markets and a lower cost of capital for the economy as a whole. An individual investor, lender or other creditor also receives benefits by making more informed decisions. However, it is not possible for general purpose financial reports to provide all the information that every user finds relevant.

- 2.42 In applying the cost constraint, the Board assesses whether the benefits of reporting particular information are likely to justify the costs incurred to provide and use that information. When applying the cost constraint in developing a proposed Standard, the Board seeks information from providers of financial information, users, auditors, academics and others about the expected nature and quantity of the benefits and costs of that Standard. In most situations, assessments are based on a combination of quantitative and qualitative information.
- 2.43 Because of the inherent subjectivity, different individuals' assessments of the costs and benefits of reporting particular items of financial information will vary. Therefore, the Board seeks to consider costs and benefits in relation to financial reporting generally, and not just in relation to individual reporting entities. That does not mean that assessments of costs and benefits always justify the same reporting requirements for all entities. Differences may be appropriate because of different sizes of entities, different ways of raising capital (publicly or privately), different users' needs or other factors.

Appendix N My learning journey

Reflecting on my existing work and professional accounting and auditing experiences over forty years, including Deloitte IOM and the numerous listed company group accounts needing accounting policies and changes in accounting policies that I have audited, the desire to challenge accepted practice arose.

I chose to do a professional doctorate because I wanted to look at the world through different eyes. I wanted to embrace the social sciences world in conjunction with my accounting and managerially trained mind, to expose myself to a 'new' way of thinking, developing fresh ideas by reflection. My aim during the course of my doctoral studies has been to develop a significant and original contribution to my profession of accountancy, a contribution that may have international implications if approved and adopted, and which may accordingly be applied by banks' and other corporate entities when changing accounting policies and motivating the use of accounting standards chosen in the compilation of their annual reports. Much of my work activities has involved financial reporting responsibilities, often in a banking environment, and it is envisaged that I become a thought leader in this field.

My research topic is an area of interest to me, and it is my background from a South African point of view that led to the Conceptual Framework's qualitative characteristics being studied and researched. South Africa, as explained in the Literature Review chapter, had 'leap-frogged' the first world Western countries by adopting its own Conceptual Framework ahead of that introduced by the American Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB). The similarity of the seminal Parasuraman et al. service quality characteristics study, in which I read for my masters, influenced the present research immeasurably, as the determinants of service quality, Access, Communications, Competence, Courtesy, Credibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Security, Tangibles, Understanding the Customer, (Parasuraman et al., 1985), can be deemed to be analogous, in description and number, to the qualitative characteristics (see Figure 8.1). Employment within significant banking groups in South Africa, and thereafter two and a half decades employment within financial accounting on the Isle of Man, latterly in the world's largest building society, and presently within the highly

regulated environment of the Government of the Isle of Man's Treasury Department, influenced my research.

It is of use to my community of practice and is in an area where I have the potential to make a contribution and to demonstrate impact. This doctoral project makes a significant original contribution to knowledge and to practice. The project has a clear purpose and satisfies a clear need. It is in an area that warranted exploration and thus the potential to fill a current gap in knowledge. It is timely in that it is a current topic (the revised Conceptual Framework has been published just over a year and a half ago by the IASB), of interest and relevance to myself and my community of practice.

This study hopefully demonstrates that I have developed my profession, and that others can learn from my work. I wish to signal my intention to become a researching professional, with a critical curiosity about my professional world, eager to contribute to the development of my profession and to share that development with others. I wish to look at challenges through a 'fresh lens', to come up with novel and imaginative solutions to professional problems or challenges, demonstrating effective thought-leadership.

As I progressed through the doctorate, I sought to develop the attributes of mindfulness, curiosity and imagination, whilst experiencing a personal intellectual transformation through the development of an enquiring mind, unfettered by the traditional boundaries of my accountancy profession.

Due to my analysis engaging in a critical conversation over the use of power, governmentality, and subjectification, my epistemological framework lent itself to that of Foucauldian critical discourse analysis (CDA). As it is difficult to find coherent descriptions of how one might go about CDA using Foucault, the adopted framework may possibly be called CDA using a 'Foucauldian lens', what Graham, 2011, 2005, describes as a 'discourse analysis informed by the use of Foucault'. Claiming to use Foucauldian CDA is a paradox, in that Foucault was not clear with his methods. Consequently, if I was to use prescriptive models so that my research can be repeated or triangulated in order to be taken seriously and counted as quality research, my work might be considered by some to be unFoucauldian (Graham, 2011, 2005).

In the context of my research, Foucauldian CDA is an exercise in explicating statements that function to place a construction rhetorically. I found that there has been little self-regularity and self-government by professional accountants, as the IASB has codified certain practices such as the QCs to such an extent that accountants have subjectified themselves to what the accounting standards say must be disclosed when they make changes in their accounting policies and publicise same in their annual reports. Accountants have been shown through my research not only to come to occupy spaces in the social hierarchy beneath the IASB, but through continual subjectification, come to know and accept their place.

During my research I came to understand conceptual frameworks as a mechanism or an argument about why the means proposed to study my topic is appropriate and rigorous. It allowed me to make what I saw as reasoned, defensible choices as to how I might explore my themes which had not previously been explored. My own conceptual framework guided me about the ways in which I collected, analysed and interpreted my data, and of the importance and limitations of my findings. It provided evidence that my study has potential significance for practice and policy, contributing knowledge that shall drive an aspect of the post-implementation review of the IASB's CF possibly as soon as 2021. In the interim, ongoing discourse about the QCs and the constraints over them, stimulated by my research, shall enable the IASB to reflect on their publication as well as their procedure in getting it produced.

My conceptual framework did not change during the course of my study. The information I gathered did however lead me to new ideas, perspectives and understandings, as did the interaction with my critical friendship group and academic writing group, which led me to question parts of my conceptual framework. Positioned as I am in a cohort at the University and in my Critical Friendship Group that contained many researchers in the health sciences and education, my overarching research method started to be questioned. I started off using both Content Analysis and Foucauldian CDA, to be more specifically situated under structured Content Analysis and a CDA using a Foucauldian lens. I came to realise that these two methods, carried out by me by way of reflective semi-structured interviews, analyses of banks' annual reports changes in accounting policy notes, and analyses of comment letters to the IASB, contained an element of phenomenology, specifically interpretive

phenomenology, (Crowther et al., 2017; Heidegger, 1962), due mainly to the interpretive nature of my results. Thus, I came to consider situating my research under this banner, tacitly rather than formally, as I knew my research methods chosen originally worked, just not that well without interpretation to the degree I needed to use it. This reinterpretation or iteration of the lens with which I viewed my data, my conceptual framework, informed my data analysis. My understanding of what I was studying was profoundly shaped by how I went about studying it. I tried to create the conditions necessary for the most rigorous, valid, reliable and authentic research possible (Ravitch and Riggan, 2017). My evolved conceptual framework supported my development as a researcher, giving me both reason and rigour in order that the usefulness and impact of my research would be determined by the evidence supporting it, and the strength of my argument. Throughout my studies I was critically aware that my progress as a researcher and my personal development plan were enabled by alignment to the Vitae Researcher Development Framework domains of 'Knowledge and intellectual abilities', 'Personal effectiveness', 'Research governance and organisation', and 'Engagement influence and impact'. The senior role I played within the IOM Government's Treasury Division for most of the time of my doctorate, also enhanced and supported my personal development.

The reason why I chose to do my research in the social science world, a professional doctorate, outside of accountancy and the normal doctorate in business administration, was that accountancy professionals come from particular cultural backgrounds, bringing specific, exclusive prejudices to bear in the standards they maintain. I am unfettered by such prejudices and standpoint which I maintain the IASB seek to govern by. I wish the role of evidence I obtain for both credibility and plausibility to exert a persuasive force on the IASB, resulting in a revision of accepted wisdom and the eventual overthrow of dominant paradigms'. My research aims to improve the QCs and constraints noted in the CF, on post implementation review, through evidence from my study, exposed to critical readership, along with the judgements and methodological decisions I made in the course of the research, which together with the research community, shall possibly persuade the IASB to change the QCs and the constraints under which they are applied, based on my truthful, applicable, consistent, and neutral, authentic research.

Post hoc personal reflections

I personally have gained, as a result of undertaking the professional doctorate process, not only an increased reputation amongst my professional community of practice derived from a greater understanding of the research process and rigour involved and evidenced, but a fulfilment of my *raison d'être* for undertaking the professional doctorate in the first place, to look for new knowledge by coming at an accounting problem from a social sciences direction, unfettered by professional governmentality restrictions if a normal DBA or PhD had been the qualification framework for my research.

During my research I came to understand conceptual frameworks as a mechanism or an argument about why the means proposed to study my topic is appropriate and rigorous. It allowed me to make what I saw as reasoned, defensible choices as to how I might explore my themes which had not previously been explored. My conceptual framework guided me about the ways in which I collected, analysed and interpreted my data, and of the importance and limitations of my findings. It provided evidence that my study has potential significance for practice and policy, contributing knowledge that shall drive an aspect of the post-implementation review of the IASB's CF possibly within a year and a half's time. In the interim, ongoing discourse about the QCs, stimulated by my research, shall enable the IASB to reflect on their publication as well as their procedure in getting it produced.

My personal portfolio locates my current learning journey, from a priori knowledge, towards posteriori, Mode 2 knowledge, indicative of more reflective learning, integrating theory and practice. Accordingly, I have listed earlier in this thesis the research papers I have published and am presently in the process of publishing, and recommendations for future research. My professional development over the course of undertaking this professional doctorate has allowed me to achieve a significant original contribution to knowledge within my profession of accountancy, hopefully demonstrating my capacity for independent, critical thinking, allowing me to go on to further research in my field.

Appendix O Published articles

International Accounting Standards Board's Qualitative Characteristics under the microscope

The Qualitative Characteristics (QCs) of decision-useful financial information, as set out in the Conceptual Framework (CF) for financial reporting of the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), are fundamental for standard setting. Companies rely on the use of QCs when making accounting policy changes and choices. The CF states that there are two fundamental characteristics of decision-useful financial information: Relevance, affected by materiality; and Faithful Representation, being financial information that is complete, neutral and free from error, which are enhanced by the QCs of comparability, consistency, verifiability, timeliness and understandability. This commentary presents the opinion that the present CF remains incomplete and there is a lack of emphasis on important concepts such as prudence and matching. We propose a revalidation of the QCs to gain a deeper sense of what is still missing from them, particularly as far as constraints go, whilst ensuring that the voices of both users and preparers are listened to.

Academics have reflected upon the QC of transparency, meaning enhanced disclosure, additional information, and improved visibility of information, and non-secrecy by companies and countries of registration, having been omitted from the present QCs¹. Indeed, the Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) has recently issued its own disclosure and transparency rules for its regulated banks. It is therefore imperative that any significant QC omissions are considered in the context of robust scientific research. Investigators across the globe have attempted to operationalise the QCs by ranking them²⁻⁴, however, despite using sophisticated statistical procedures, findings remain flawed due to the evident and remaining gap between preparers and users' rankings.

We are in the process of analysing data, which we believe will further elucidate the inclusion conundrum⁵. We trust that a revised chapter in the international CF on the QCs of decision-useful financial information is clearly on the cards and entice readers to watch this space for what we think will lead to a freshly formulated and newly submitted chapter for consideration by the IASB, with potential for implementation on an international level. Our research will likely point to further validated QCs being considered as appropriate by preparers of international and domestic banks annual reports. It has yet to be concluded whether further QCs can be identified with confidence, yet the incorporation of Foucauldian critical discourse analysis has given us our boldest attempt because this method allows us to focus on power relationships in accounting society, as expressed through language and practices of the IASB who ultimately decide on the QCs, and the IASB's interaction with professional accountants preparing international banks annual reports. In addition, geographical and cultural spread has been adequately attained by examining the annual reports of both building societies and regulated banks listed on the UK FTSE, Johannesburg and Australian stock exchange main boards. Finally, using content analysis allows for the extraction of the nature and extent of the changes in QCs of decision-useful financial information found in the international and domestic UK banks annual report disclosures, compared to those found since publication of the revised CF.

It is now time to multiply the magnification of our qualitative lens, and in anticipation of the conclusions that can be drawn from our emerging data, we intend this commentary to prompt some fresh thinking on the effectiveness of the updated QCs.

Gareth Evans, Joanne Lusher and Stephen Day (University of the West of Scotland)

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